

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

**AGROECOLOGical strategies for an efficient functioning
of plant - soil biota interactions to increase SOC
sequestration**

AGROECOseqC

Final Continuous reporting

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AUTHOR: Alessandra Trinchera, Sebastien Fontaine, Valentina Baratella, Elena Testani, Skaidre Suproniene, Sara Sanchez-Moreno, Margarita Ros, Carmen Trasar Cepeda, Jim Rasmussen, Marjoleine Hanagraaf, Akin Un, Simon Sail, Flavio Fornasier, Isabelle Bertrand, Luisa Manici, Antonio Rodriguez-Hernandez, Dylan Warren Raffa, Joaquin Cobos, Ángel Carrascosa Robles, Ludovica Saccà, Corrado Ciaccia, Alessandro Paletto, Raphael Martin, Leanne Peixoto, Alvyra Šlepetienė, Ona

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Auškalnienė, Gabin Piton, Bruno
Huyghebaert, Sahimerdan Turkolmez, Hatice
Kara, Saddam Kalkan, Abdulkadir Bal, Rebecca
Hood

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- **Basic project information**

Project title:	AGROECOseqC
Acronym:	AGROECOLOGICAL strategies for an efficient functioning of plant -soil biota interactions to increase SOC sequestration
Duration:	01/11/2021-31/10/2024
Topic:	CM5 – - Effects of the soil biome on the persistence SOC storage and its drivers
Project type:	Medium-sized research project
Project coordinator:	Alessandra Trinchera, CREA Co-coordinator: Sebastien Fontaine, INRAE
Abstract:	Soil fauna and microbial communities drive key ecosystem functions, such as nutrient supply to primary production and SOC accumulation. However, plant diversity shapes soil biota composition and activity via rhizodeposition and N-P uptake, microbial symbioses, and trophic cascades. In EU experimental sites network, AGROECOseqC studied how the agroecological intensification of cropping systems regulates degradation/resynthesis of soil organic matter, nutrient cycling, mediated by soil fauna and microbial diversity. Advantages and disadvantages of such agroecological systems were compared to less conservative ones for plant-soil fauna microbial functional diversity, biomass production, N leaching, soil C-stable pools, and soil Carbon Use Efficiency.
Key words:	Plant diversity, soil fauna, soil microbiome diversity, root mycorrhization, plant demand-microbial supply synchrony, soil C and nutrient fluxes, SOC storage, agroecological multi-indicators, modelling.
Key Takeaways:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Plant diversity and functional diversity of soil fauna and microbiota are key drivers in C and nutrient fluxes in soil, able to modulate SOC sequestration in agricultural systems.2. By introducing suitable agroecological practices, based on crop diversification, the synchrony between plant uptake and nutrient availability in soil will be increased by soil microbial community, shaped in a way to reduce SOC mineralization and increase C-storage.

List of project partners: Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA); Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement (INRAE); Aarhus University, Danish Centre for Food and Agriculture (AU-AGRO); General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies of the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (TAGEM); Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC); Stichting Wageningen Research (WR); Walloon Agricultural Research Centre (CRAW); Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC); and University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU).

- **Reporting**

Reporting period: 01.02.2024 – 31.10.2024

a. **State of progress**

At end of September 2024, AGROECOseqC project was concluded without major deviations from the stated program. At the end of June 2024, the analytical activities were concluded, and the overall dataset already generated, while within half of September the results were descriptively analysed by WP leaders.

On 1-2 October, the AGROECOseqC final meeting will be organized in Rome (Italy) to discuss about all collected results and related publications.

At M57 more than 40 deliverables were submitted to EJPSOIL - WP3 (some of them included into the AGROECOseqC Handbook), within the 31st of October 2024 (EJPSOIL/WP3/Projects/AGROECOseqC/Deliverables with DOI/). These deliverables were put under embargo period up to 31st October 2025 (12 months) as stated into the AGROECOseqC DMP (released as public D1.4).

On January 2025, **11 AGROECOseqC articles** and the **AGROECOseqC Handbook** (as internal working document) were released as “Scientifically meaningful deliverables”, while other **5 original articles are currently submitted to ISI journals** (submitted version under embargo period).

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Regarding the WP6 – D6.2.2 by CREA-VE, it was not delivered due to issues found using the respirometer equipment. The setup of the device required, in addition to a lot of time, the consumption of nearly all the amount of soil sample provided. The D6.2.2 deliverable was justified also into the Deliverables list and in WP6 reporting section.

b. **Summary report**

EJPSoil AGROECOseqC project – 15th September 2024

WP2.- Plant Diversity and Functional Traits, mycorrhizal colonization and P.solubilizing fungi

Low-intensity management activates mechanisms like those found in natural ecosystems, enhancing plant communities' resilience and functionality. Root mycorrhizal colonization is more prominent in no-till, highly diversified systems, where mycorrhizal hyphae networks are established within the upper 0.20 cm of soil. Furthermore, under the highest levels of agroecological intensification, phosphorus-solubilizing microorganisms are most abundant, contributing to improved nutrient cycling.

WP3 - Macro-, Meso-, and Microfauna Diversity

Significant differences were observed in the taxonomic composition and functional traits of macro-, meso-, and microfauna communities. Soil organic carbon (SOC) positively correlated with the relative abundance of predator and omnivore nematodes, while negatively correlating with the total abundance of bacterivores and fungivores, highlighting the impact of SOC on faunal community dynamics.

WP4 - Soil Microbial Functional Diversity

Agroecological intensification did not significantly increase bacterial and fungal diversity, with variations depending on both the experimental site and treatments. However, bacteria with growth-promoting and biocontrol activities, as well as those involved in key nutrient cycles, increased under agroecological management. No significant effects were observed on beneficial fungi. The abundance of functional groups involved in the carbon (C) cycle varied based on the functional group and sampling site.

The increase in specific functional genes contributed to soil bacteria's assimilation and utilization of carbon, although the variation caused by intensification was relatively small. The fungal community exhibited a higher abundance of saprophytes and endo- and ectomycorrhizal fungi, regardless of the agroecological treatment or site. A positive correlation between fungal β -glucosidase activity and the corresponding fungal gene was noted, revealing the distinct roles of microbial groups in organic carbon turnover. Soil tillage significantly affects carbon metabolism, with soil organic matter (SOM) accumulation, being strongly influenced by vegetation cover. Although *Basidiomycetes* are often underestimated in their role in degrading plant polysaccharides, *Ascomycota* (microfungi) displayed a wider enzyme profile and greater enzymatic variability, indicating their adaptability in metabolizing crop residues and litter.

WP5 - Synchrony Between Plant Nutrient Demand, Soil Nutrient Fluxes, and SOM Dynamics

Differences in plant nitrogen (N) demand across sites, demand periods, and agroecological treatments suggest promising indicators for future studies of the synchrony between plant nutrient demand and ecosystem processes. Increased soil microbial carbon (C), respiration, and carbon use efficiency (CUE) varied across treatments, offering insight into the relationship between plant nutrient demand and ecosystem processes. At two sites, PLFA (phospholipid fatty acid) analysis showed that agroecological intensification rapidly incorporated carbon into soil microbial biomass, whereas the organic farm management was optimal and did not allow further C-incorporation.

WP6 - Soil Carbon Retention Through Stable Aggregates and Microbial Biomass Activity

A complex relationship was observed between soil structure, microbial biomass, and carbon cycling across different environmental conditions and agricultural practices. Strong correlations were found between SOC, water-extractable organic carbon (WEOC), microbial biomass C, and water-stable aggregates. This underscores the key role of soil organic matter stability in regulating ecosystem processes. No-tillage practices increased both root mycorrhization and the abundance of fine macroaggregates (0.25-1.0 mm), indicating that mycorrhizal mycelium plays a significant role in soil particle aggregation, though these results are site-dependent. Agronomic practices also affected soil basal respiration (CO₂ emissions), with variation based on plant nutrient demand and sampling time. These patterns were further influenced by pedoclimatic conditions and the agroecological intensification gradient applied in the study.

WP7 - Integration of Plant Functional Traits, Soil Microbial, and Faunal Parameters with Soil Properties (MVA)

Redundancy analysis (RDA) identified that specific plant functional traits and microbial functional groups were associated with SOC and WEOC and explained about 60% of the variation in C pools. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) revealed that plant functional traits had a significant effect on microbial functional groups. The Specific Leaf Area, the presence of perennial species and Grass-like species significantly influenced (i) arbuscular mycorrhiza, litter saprotroph and dung saprotroph fungal groups, and (ii) non-photosynthetic and fermentation bacterial groups. The selected bacterial and fungal groups showed significant negative effects on soil carbon levels. Furthermore, farm management practices were found to impact both plant and microbial functional groups.

A more detailed report of the main AGROECOseqC scientific results obtained by WP1-WP2-WP3-WP4-WP5-WP6-WP7-WP8 activities on 15th September 2024.

WP1 - Project management and coordination – CREA, INRAE.

Tasks 1.1 - 1.2 - 1.3 - From February to October 2024, coordinators followed the last activities of data collection, dataset organization, deliverable, and milestone submission, contact with AGROECOseqC and EJP-SOIL PCR. On 23rd of May 2024, the annual meeting was held to align the presentation and take-home messages to be presented at Riga Annual Science Days 2024 and to discuss on how to valorise results generated by AGROECOseqC activities. Other Team's meetings were performed among WPs/tasks leader to discuss about obtained results, their statistical evaluation, and final data exploitation. The AGROECOseqC final meeting will be held on 1-2 October 2024 in Rome (Italy): each WP will report on their activity and results. A rotating session is planned for promoting a face-to-face discussion between WPs, followed by a "Policy brief" session to collect take-home messages deriving from AGROECOseqC results.

AGROECOseqC overall database - Collected data from WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7 activities were used to fill the AGROECOseqC overall dataset, refreshed on 15th September 2024 (EJP-SOIL – WP3 - AGROECOseqC INRAE repository and Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org/communities/agroecoseqc/settings>, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14525072). The overall dataset (under embargo period up to 31 October 2025) consists in:

Sheet 1: List of selected AGROECOseqC parameters and indicators and related units.

Sheet 2: Dataset_Experiment A: 9 core-sites x 3 treatments/site x 4 blocks/treatment = 108 plots, corresponding to 108 soil / vegetable / root samples collected at MAX and 108 soil/vegetable at MIN plant demand, for a total of 216 soil / vegetable/ root samples. Soil parameters and indicators were determined at MAX, or at MIN, or at both MAX / MIN plant demand in function of their relevance in the project, as described into the AGROECOseqC Handbook. Each sample was a composite sample, obtained after mixing 4 sub-samples collected in each plot.

Sheet 3: Dataset_Experiment B: 3 core-sites x 2 treatments / site x 3 blocks / treatments x 3 replicates/blocks = 54 plots, corresponding to 108 soil / vegetable / root samples collected only at MAX plant demand. Each sample was an elementary sample of the four collected in each plot.

Sheet 4: Dataset CS4_Task 2.2 – This dataset is related only to CS4 experiment, where two additional treatments were added to evaluate the effect of increased plant diversity in field and N supply (high/low) on root mycorrhizal colonization (n. 16 root samples).

Sheet 5: Dataset_WP4 – Bacteria functionality. This dataset is related to all core-sites on 108 soil samples (Experiment A), collected at MAX plant demand.

Sheet 6: Dataset_WP4 – Bacteria functionality. This dataset is related to CS1, CS5, CS7 on 54 soil samples (Experiment B), collected at MAX plant demand.

Sheet 7: Dataset_WP4 – Fungi functionality. This dataset is related to all core-sites on 108 soil samples (Experiment A), collected at MAX plant demand.

Sheet 8: Dataset_WP4 – Fungi functionality. This dataset is related to CS1, CS5, CS7 on 54 soil samples (Experiment B), collected at MAX plant demand.

Starting from collected database, on 20th December 2024, the article “**Context-Driven**

“Context-Driven Agroecological Intensification to support Soil Health and C accrual: Insights from Multi-site Experiment” by Trinchera and AGROECOseqC colleagues (D1.5) was recently submitted to European Journal of Soil Science (EJSS–868-24) to the Special Issue III “Soil Health: Current Status and Future Challenges”. In AGROECOseqC CS1, CS2, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 experimental sites, representative of different pedoclimatic regions, the soil density, pH, texture, SOC, water-extractable C, microbial C, water stable aggregate, soil NO₃ and NH₄, available P, bacterial and fungal richness (CHAO), bacterial and fungal diversity (Shannon index), and mycorrhizal colonization of plant roots (M) were measured as responsive to a gradient of agroecological (AE) intensification, applied by introducing conservative management practices such as no-tillage, service crops, introduction of legumes, organic amendments and/or residues restitution, fungi inoculant.

PCA applied on the eight AGROECOseqC sites (**A**) well discriminated the selected indicators in function of the tested experimental sites (e.g., different climatic context, soil type, cropping system), but not in function of the applied AE intensification (**B**).

Contrastingly, the PCA run on each experimental site well separated the obtained clusters in function of the applied AE intensification (T1 and T2, where AE T1 < AE T2), compared to the control (No AE, T3). These results evidenced the role of pedoclimate conditions on affecting the selected soil indicators more than the management practices.

PCA biplots ordering the (**A**) AGROECOseqC experimental sites (IT, FR, ES, LT, DK, NL, BE, TK countries, regardless AE treatments), and (**B**) AE intensification (T1, T2, T3-control, regardless the sites) in function of the following soil parameters and bioindicators (SD, SOC, WEOC, WSA, NH₄, NO₃, available P as P2O₅, Cmic, Shan_BC, Shan_FN, Chao_BC, Chao_FN, M).

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A good correlation between SOC and Cmic was found in the experimental sites tested ($r = 0.51993$; $p=3.4285 \times 10^{-19}$), confirming that Cmic is a fast, sensitive indicator of soil C accumulation.

A synthesis of the effect of applied AE on the AGROECOseqC experimental sites is graphically summarized in the following figure, where the EU country, the level of AE intensification (soil

tillage/no tillage, cover crop, crop rotation, multicropping, mineral/organic fertilization, crop residues restitution, fungi inoculant), the tested indicators, the expected supplied ecosystem services, and the different AE management practices are shortly described.

Effect of AE intensification (No AE; Low AE, High AE) on some selected indicators (WP2, WP4, WP6) measured in AGROECOseqC experimental sites (Trinchera et al., 2025, submitted to EJSS).

Sites	AE intensity	Supplied ecosystem services											
		SOC accrual				Nutrient availability				Biodiversity			
		SOC	%	WEOC g kg ⁻¹	C _{mic} mg kg ⁻¹	WSA %	NH ₄ mg kg ⁻¹	NO ₃ mg kg ⁻¹	P ₂ O ₅ mg kg ₁	M %	Chao_BC	Chao_FN	Shan_BC
S1 - IT	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S2 - FR	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S3 - BE	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S4 - NL	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S5 - LT	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S6 - ES	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S7 - DK	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												
S8 - TK	No AE												
	Low AE												
	High AE												

No-tillage emerged as the most relevant factor affecting SOC accrual, able to increase it of 20% (compared to no AE control systems) in Mediterranean cropping systems over ten years, favouring also plant root mycorrhization, fine macroaggregates (0.25-1.0 mm) abundance and fungi abundance in field. *Fabaceae* and *Poaceae* species positively contributed to SOC accrual in soil, contemporary increasing fungi richness, P-cycling, and crop root mycorrhization. *Brassicaceae* species instead increase soil bacteria richness, decrease fungi one by supporting N cycle, although depressing root mycorrhization. Below, a graphic synthesis of main results is reported.

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Take-home message – AGROECOseqC results showed that agroecological intensification in EU must be always considered in a context of regionalization of the environmental measures of the CAP, appropriately designed and implemented on each agroecosystem, considering the pedoclimate, the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the soil, as well as the production system. This approach will ensure a proper application of the Soil Health Directive and effectively face the soil C and biodiversity loss on long term.

WP2 - Plant communities and rhizosphere plant-microbe interactions – CREA, TAGEM

Task 2.1 - Plant functional diversity and effect on soil C inputs and retention – CREA

Introduction - The objective of the Task was to analyze spontaneous flora communities across the project European Case Studies (CSs) and assess their potential for C sequestration in the context of agroecological (AE) intensification. The study specifically investigated the distribution of diversity indices and functional traits related to C sequestration to test hypotheses that:

1. the response of spontaneous flora would vary according to the specific pedoclimatic conditions of each site;
2. these communities would have higher diversity and lower dominance in response to agroecological intensification;
3. agroecological intensification would enhance carbon sequestration potential of spontaneous flora communities.

Each project CS employs different systems and treatments. Treatments were categorized by varying agroecological practices: T1 (low AE intensification), T2 (high AE intensification), and T3 (control, with no AE intensification). Spontaneous flora assessments were performed at two phenological stages, representing minimum and maximum plant nutrient uptake, to understand temporal variations and to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem's carbon sequestration potential, as it reflects both the peak carbon assimilation period (spring - MAX) and the period of carbon storage and resource conservation (late summer - MIN).

By using a trait-based analysis, we selected key plants' characteristics such as canopy height (CH), specific leaf area (SLA), % of grass-like species, supporting arbuscular mycorrhiza and perennials. These traits are linked to mechanisms by means plants can provide C sequestration, including

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biomass productivity and quality, investment in C storage structures in the soil and mycorrhizal associations. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey tests, confirmed significant differences in trait values between treatments. In cases where binary data were present, Chi-square tests and Fisher's Exact Test provided insights into species distribution and functional trait prevalence.

Our findings indicated that, according to our first hypothesis, ecological and environmental variables significantly shaped spontaneous flora communities, often overshadowing the effects of intensification treatments. For instance, agroforestry systems (e.g., CS1 and CS3) demonstrated higher species richness and greater structural diversity compared to arable and vegetable systems. The reduced soil disturbance and shaded microenvironments in these systems supported a more diverse flora, enhancing ecosystem functions like C sequestration through stable root systems and increased organic matter inputs.

In CS1 higher SLA and canopy height in no-till treatment was also found at the MAX stage, as well as in no-till CS5 treatments, aligning with increased aboveground biomass potential. Meanwhile, in vegetable systems like CS8, cover crops and fungi inoculation influenced SLA traits, albeit within a narrow range, demonstrating the need for optimal environmental conditions to maximize growth and C input.

In no-till treatments (e.g., T1 in CS1 and T1 and T2 in CS5 and CS7), SAM species were also favored, leading to greater mycorrhizal colonization and improved soil structure.

Trait analysis also revealed that grass-like species in undisturbed systems can contribute to soil organic C storage, emphasizing the role of root exudates and decomposing matter in forming stable soil aggregates. These systems seemed to show a functional profile akin to natural ecosystems, where stable plant communities optimize C storage. This contrasts with tilled environments, where annual and pioneer species dominate due to frequent soil disturbance, disrupting microbial networks essential for C sequestration. However, in some cases, such as CS9, low species richness and limited trait variation suggested that organic matter management alone may not suffice without broader ecosystem management strategies. No clear trends were found for the perennial trait among CSs.

In conclusion, the research demonstrates that spontaneous flora, traditionally seen as a hindrance in agriculture, can be strategically managed to enhance soil health and carbon dynamics. By

integrating these plant communities into agroecological practices, farmers can promote a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system. The results underscore the complexity of interactions between plant traits, management practices, and environmental conditions, highlighting the need for site-specific strategies to maximize ecosystem benefits.

Take-home message - Spontaneous flora is an important actor of the agroecosystem that can contribute to its diversity and functionality. Although this result requires further confirmation through systematic studies, it suggests that low-intensity management can activate mechanisms akin to those found in natural ecosystems, enhancing both the resilience and functionality of the system.

Task 2.2. Mycorrhizal extra-radical mycelium development and effect on soil aggregates formation - CREA, LAMMC

Objective - The mycorrhizal extra-radical hyphae account for up to two-third of new C inputs to soil (about 79-153 g/m³ per year) of mycelia-derived C, stored in SOM pools (Zhang et al., 2019). In AGROECOseqC we hypothesize that mycorrhizal fungi, through external hyphal mycelium, were able to extend the root lifespan and boost the C stock in fine soil macroaggregates (0.25-1.0 mm).

Sampling and methodology – To achieve our goal, Task 2.2 preliminary worked on determination of plant mycorrhization in field. Thus, in all the nine core-sites, the effect of applied agroecological practices, based on reduced soil disturbance (no tillage) and higher plant diversity in field (cover crop, crop rotation), were evaluated in terms of root mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%) and presence of external mycelial network on collected roots.

Mycorrhizal colonization intensity of plant roots - The database of mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%) of plant roots, collected in all the 9 core-sites as affected by considered treatments, is uploaded into both the CREA AGROECOseqC overall dataset and into INRAE EJPSoil/WP3/AGROECOseqC repository (D2.2.1.2). The overall results are below reported (Figure 1):

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Figure 1. Mycorrhizal colonisation intensity of main crop in all AGROECOseqC core-sites (CSs), as affected by treatments. T1 = lower agroecological intensification; T2 = highest agroecological intensification; T3 = lowest or no agroecological intensification (control).

Crop root mycorrhization was affected by the introduced agroecological intensification: as hypothesized, in CS1, CS3, CS5, CS7, CS8, and CS9, M in T1 was higher than in the control T3 (at $p < 0.05$). Instead, in CS2, M in T1 was the lowest compared to T2 and T3, probably due to the functional traits of the plant species constituting the mixture. In fact, in CS4, T2 gave the same M of T1, although significantly lower than T3: in T3, the *Lolium perenne* L., a plant species with supporting arbuscular mycorrhizal (SAM) trait, evidently favoured the root mycorrhization in field, which was partially “diluted” in T1 and T2 plant mixtures. Apparently, the presence of plant SAM trait of coexisting species in field makes the difference: introducing non-host AM plants (such as *Brassicaceae* species) in natural coverage or as cover crops, can induce a suppressive effect on root mycorrhization, perceived also by the AM-host main crop (as the vetch in T2, CS6).

Going to the effect played by specific agronomic practices on root mycorrhization, considering CS1, CS5 and CS7 (AGROECOseqC LTEs, where no tillage was compared to tillage), we observed a significant increase of M% ($p = 0.05$), due to the absence of soil disturbance (NT) (Figure 2, left side). The increased plant diversity in T1 and T2, compared to the control T3, did not determine a significant effect on M, although a trend to increase in T1 and T2 was noticed (Figure 2, right side).

Figure 2. Effect of soil disturbance (NT = no-tillage; T = tillage in CS1, CS5, CS7) and of crop diversification (T1, T2, T3 in CS1, CS2, CS3, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7, CS8, CS9) on the mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%) recorded on plant root collected in field.

Study of mycorrhizal extra-radical mycelium on plant roots - After determination of M% (D2.2.1.2), in 108 (Exp. A) + 57 (Exp B) on root samples collected at MAX demand in 9 core-sites, from February to September 2024, the undisturbed soil samples containing plant root fragments collected from the field (and sent to CREA-AA from all the core-sites) were analyzed using the scanning electron microscopy SEM EVO MA10 Zeiss, equipped with a new LaB₆ filament (electron -source) and back-scattered electrons (BSE) detector. This analysis did not generate a database since it was based on electronic images of roots and mycorrhizal extra-radical mycelium on root surface. Obtained SEM images were compared to those obtained using the optical microscope Ellipse 100 Nikon on collected root fragments, after staining them with methylene-blue when determining the mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%).

Results of microscopic analysis of mycorrhizal extra-radical mycelium - The comparison among root images obtained using optical microscopy and SEM shows that the staining process allows to distinguish between mycorrhizal fungi hyphae and saprotroph/pathogenic fungi hyphae. On the other hand, SEM image allowed to evidence the hyphal mycelium development more than optical microscope, due to the high magnification of the object (1.3KX, instead of 100X, Figure 3). This result suggests applying both the microscopic techniques for avoiding misleading interpretation about the origin of fungi mycelium growth.

Figure 3. Root images obtained using optical microscopy (Mag: 100X) and SEM (Mag.: 1.3 KX): mycorrhizal hyphal mycelium is evidenced in blue color by optical microscopy and in white color (see arrows) by SEM.

Among the core-sites, mycorrhizal extra-hyphal mycelium was mainly found in no-tilled systems (T1) and in cover cropped ones (T2), while it was reduced (or sometimes not detected) in long-term experiment where tillage at 30 cm was applied. Cereals (wheat, barley) and legumes (Persian clover, vetch, etc.) promoted the mycorrhizal mycelium formation on root surface, while the presence of Brassica plants in field (radish, oilseed rape sprouts) significantly reduced it. The relationship with M%, root mycorrhizal mycelium development and data related to soil aggregates dimension and C% are discussed in Task 6.1 reporting action.

In relation to the extra-budget request for Task 2.2 activity, CREA evaluated the mycorrhizal colonization intensity of soil samples collected in 2023 from CS4 in relation to five treatments, instead of three ones:

T1 = *Lolium perenne* (Lp), at 75N

T2 = *Lolium perenne* + white clover (Tr), at 75N

T3 = 6 species mixture (MS6), at 75N

T4 = 18 species mixture (M18)

T5 = *Lolium perenne*, at 300N

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In Figure 4, M% recorded on plant root systems collected under T1, T2, T3, T4 and T5 is reported.

Figure 4. Plant root M% recorded in CS4 - T1, T2, T3, T4, T5 treatments.

As expected, a strong effect of N supply was observed on depressing plant root mycorrhization in Lp 300N compared to Lp 75N ($p < 0.01$) (Blanke et al., 2005). In addition, the increase of plant species mixture

boosted M% in M18, compared to M6 and Lp + Tr: these results confirmed those by Leon et al., 2021, who verified that community mycorrhization, which is sensitive to soil fertility (N), can be modulated by community composition in temperate grasslands, probably by enhancing the most dominant AM-host plant species in the community.

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Task 2.3. Plant-microbe beneficial symbioses and effect on crop N-P uptake – TAGEM/AU

Objective

In this task, soil samples collected at different periods in AGROECOseqC core-sites were analyzed to determine and compare different parameters and indicators, including soil available phosphorus (Pav), nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), and colony-forming fungi. Each soil from core site was examined for its specific fungal species as affected by T1, T2 and T3 treatments, and these were systematically compared across two sampling periods: at minimum (MIN) and maximum plant nutrient demand. This comprehensive approach not only provides insights into the temporal

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variations of soil nutrient content and fungal populations but also highlights the importance of monitoring these factors for understanding soil health and fertility. By identifying and comparing the types and concentrations of these parameters, the analysis enhances our ability to well manage the soil and support the decision-making process to optimize agricultural practices.

Obtained results were inserted into the overall AGROECOseqC dataset. In each core-site, statistical evaluation was performed, considering the “treatment” as main factor.

Phosphorus Availability (Pav) at Max and Min Uptake Periods

The phosphorus availability (Pav) in soil samples provided by project partners was assessed to understand the nutrient status and its potential impact on plant growth. This study aimed to determine the phosphorus levels in the soils using the Olsen method (Olsen et al., 1954), which is widely recognized for its effectiveness in extracting available phosphorus in neutral to alkaline soils. By evaluating Pav, the research sought to provide insights into soil fertility, nutrient management, and overall soil health, which are critical factors in sustainable agricultural practices and optimizing crop productivity.

Results

CS1: CREA, Italy

The Pav values for CS1 indicate that Treatment 2 (T2) had the highest available phosphorus during the maximum uptake period (66.57 mg/kg), followed by Treatment 1 (T1) at 57.75 mg/kg, and Treatment 3 (T3) at 47.52 mg/kg. This suggests that T2 soils had the best phosphorus availability during the critical period of plant growth, indicating that this treatment could be more effective in supporting phosphorus

uptake in crops.

During the minimum uptake period, the phosphorus availability was lower across all treatments, with T2 still maintaining the highest Pav (51.48 mg/kg), followed by T3 (46.21 mg/kg) and T1 (39.92 mg/kg). The ability of T2 to maintain a relatively high phosphorus level during the low uptake period

suggests better phosphorus retention, likely contributing to better crop productivity in the following growing season.

CS2: INRAE-Clermont Ferrand, France

In CS2, Treatment 3 (T3) showed the highest phosphorus availability during the maximum uptake period, with a Pav of 44.35 mg/kg, followed by T2 (28.12 mg/kg) and T1 (26.95 mg/kg). The lower phosphorus availability in T1 and T2 indicates that crops in these treatments might experience limited phosphorus supply during the peak growth periods, potentially impacting growth and yield.

During the minimum uptake period, T3 still exhibited the highest phosphorus availability at 36.83 mg/kg, followed by T1 (18.66 mg/kg) and T2 (17.58 mg/kg). The results show that phosphorus availability in CS2 is generally low across all treatments and growth periods and, therefore, soil amendments might be necessary to improve Pav levels, particularly in T1 and T2.

CS3: INRAE- Montpellier, France

For CS3, Treatment 3 (T3) exhibited slightly higher Pav during the maximum uptake period, reaching 37.61 mg/kg, compared to Treatment 2 (T2) with 33 mg/kg. While the moderate phosphorus levels in both treatments seem sufficient for crop growth, additional P fertilizer application could further enhance yield potential.

In the minimum uptake period, Pav values dropped significantly, with T2 falling to 12.99 mg/kg and T3 to 15.60 mg/kg. This reduction in phosphorus availability suggests that phosphorus is being depleted at a faster rate than it is replenished, which may potentially affect long-term soil fertility unless mitigated through appropriate management practices.

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CS4: Aarhus University (AU), Denmark

CS4 exhibited relatively consistent phosphorus availability across all treatments. In the maximum uptake period, T1 had the highest Pav (69.11 mg/kg), while T2 and T3 showed very similar Pav values (66.56 mg/kg and 68.21 mg/kg, respectively). In the minimum uptake period, T1 showed a similar trend with slightly higher Pav compared to T2 and T3, with values of 73.40, 70.43, and 65.40 mg/kg,

respectively. This consistency highlights the stability of phosphorus availability in CS4 soils, which is advantageous for sustained crop productivity.

The high Pav levels observed during the minimum uptake period suggest that phosphorus is well-retained in these soils, reducing the need for excessive phosphorus fertilization. This could result in efficient nutrient management and improved long-term soil fertility.

CS5: INIA-CSIC, Spain

In CS5, Treatment 1 (T1) showed the highest phosphorus availability in the maximum uptake period (69.69 mg/kg), followed by T2 (64.91 mg/kg) and T3 (44.89 mg/kg). The high phosphorus levels in all treatments indicate favorable conditions for crop growth during this critical uptake period.

However, during the minimum uptake period, Pav values decreased substantially, with T1 dropping to 24.04 mg/kg, T2 to 22.97 mg/kg, and T3 to 17.04 mg/kg. This sharp decline suggests that while Pav levels are sufficient during peak growth periods, the phosphorus reserves are being rapidly depleted, possibly necessitating additional phosphorus inputs to maintain soil fertility.

CS6: Wageningen University, Netherlands

For CS6, Pav levels were relatively stable across the treatments, with T1 showing the highest value in the maximum uptake period (53.55 mg/kg), closely followed by T2 (51.35 mg/kg) and T3 (47.75 mg/kg). This indicates moderate phosphorus availability across all treatments, which should adequately support crop growth.

The minimum uptake period showed a similar trend, with Pav values only slightly reduced. T1 again had the highest Pav (52.65 mg/kg), followed by T2 (50.73 mg/kg) and T3 (50.33 mg/kg). The stability of phosphorus levels in CS6 indicates efficient phosphorus retention and availability across both uptake periods, suggesting that these soils are well-suited for long-term crop production without significant

phosphorus supplementation.

CS7: LAMMC, Lithuania

In CS7, T2 exhibited the highest Pav during the maximum uptake period, at 68.94 mg/kg, followed closely by T1 (66.31 mg/kg) and T3 (61.53 mg/kg). These values suggest that phosphorus availability is generally high in all treatments, providing favorable conditions for crop uptake during the critical growth stages.

During the minimum uptake period, Pav levels decreased across all treatments, with T3 maintaining the highest Pav (61.70 mg/kg), followed by T1 (49.67 mg/kg) and T2 (42.61 mg/kg), where the decrease in Pav was more pronounced. Although the levels dropped, they remained relatively high, indicating that the soils in CS7 have good phosphorus retention capacity.

CS8: TAGEM, Türkiye

CS8 results show that T2 had the highest Pav during the maximum uptake period (52.89 mg/kg), closely followed by T3 (50.91 mg/kg) and T1 (46.38 mg/kg). The moderate phosphorus availability across all treatments suggests that crops in CS8 soils are unlikely to suffer from phosphorus deficiency during peak uptake periods.

During the minimum uptake period, phosphorus availability (Pav) levels increased significantly in T2, reaching 80.49 mg/kg. In T1, Pav values were maintained at 50.74 mg/kg, while in T3, they dropped to 32.94 mg/kg. The significant difference between the max and min uptake periods suggests that T1 and T3 soils have a greater capacity to retain phosphorus than T2, making them optimal treatments for maintaining phosphorus soil fertility across growth cycles.

CS9: CRAW, Belgium

CS9 results indicate that T3 had the highest Pav during the maximum uptake period (68.95 mg/kg), followed closely by T2 (63.76 mg/kg) and T1 (62.14 mg/kg). These values indicate that phosphorus availability is high across all treatments, which should support vigorous crop growth during critical stages.

During the minimum uptake period, Pav levels declined across all treatments, but the decrease was minimal at T1. As a result, T1 had the highest Pav (62.36 mg/kg), followed by T3 (33.43 mg/kg) and T2 (32.36 mg/kg). Despite the reduction in phosphorus levels, the Pav values in CS9 remain sufficient to support crop productivity. However, phosphorus management strategies may be necessary to sustain long-term soil fertility.

Conclusion:

Phosphorus at Maximum Uptake Period:

Across the different treatments (T1, T2, and T3), the maximum phosphorus availability (Pav) across all the core sites (CS1 to CS9) reveals several trends. CS5 and CS4 exhibit the highest phosphorus availability, particularly in Treatment 1 (T1), where Pav reaches 69.69 mg/kg and 69.11, respectively,

indicating optimal conditions for phosphorus uptake. This is followed by CS9 (T3) with 68.95 mg/kg and CS7 (T2) with 68.94 mg/kg.

These results suggest that treatments in CS4, CS5, CS7 and CS9 maintain excellent phosphorus availability during the critical plant uptake periods, supporting optimal plant growth. The high Pav in these areas indicates that phosphorus is readily available for plants during the maximum growth period, which is essential for ensuring high yields and nutrient efficiency.

Phosphorus at Minimum Uptake Period:

In the minimum uptake period, phosphorus availability declines across all core sites, with noticeable reductions observed. However, CS4 demonstrates resilience, with T1 maintaining 70.43 mg/kg Pav, closely followed by CS1 with 51.48 mg/kg in T2. CS8 shows its highest value in the T2 treatment at the minimum uptake period, as the available phosphorus level increased from 52.89 mg/kg during the maximum uptake period to 80.49 mg/kg in the minimum uptake period.

This increase, observed after the maximum uptake period, indicates that the T2 treatment is an effective method for enhancing phosphorus availability. Despite

lower phosphorus uptake in the minimum period, these sites sustain higher P_{av} , indicating better phosphorus retention in the soil.

On the other hand, in CS5 and CS3, lower P_{av} levels were recorded during the minimum uptake period compared to the maximum uptake period, suggesting that phosphorus is more rapidly depleted in these soils. This highlights the potential need for phosphorus replenishment strategies to support sustainable long-term agricultural productivity.

Nitrate (NO_3) and Ammonium (NH_4) Availability during Max and Min Uptake Periods:

The nitrate (NO_3) and ammonium (NH_4) concentrations in soil samples provided by project partners were evaluated to assess the nitrogen status and its influence on plant growth. The study employed the KCl extraction method, which is widely recognized for its efficiency in extracting available nitrogen in the form of NO_3 and NH_4 from soil. This method allowed for precise quantification of nitrogen availability during both maximum and minimum plant uptake periods. By analyzing NO_3 and NH_4 levels, the study aimed to provide valuable insights into soil fertility, nitrogen management, and the overall health of the soil ecosystem, which are essential for sustainable agricultural practices and optimizing crop productivity.

Results:

CS1: CREA, Italy

The NH_4 availability during the maximum and minimum uptake periods for CS1 reveals key trends across the treatments. In the maximum uptake period, Treatment 1 (T1) exhibited the lowest NH_4 availability at 53.9 mg/kg, while Treatment 3 (T3) and Treatment 2 (T2) showed relatively higher NH_4 levels of 62.3 mg/kg and 61.6 mg/kg, respectively. These results suggest that T3 and T2 provide slightly better ammonium availability during the peak plant growth periods, which is essential for supporting crop nitrogen demands in ammonium-absorbing plants.

During the minimum uptake period, NH_4 availability significantly increased for all treatments, with T1 showing the highest NH_4 value of 80.15 mg/kg, followed by T3 (72.1 mg/kg) and T2 (67.55 mg/kg).

During the minimum uptake period, NH_4 availability significantly increased for all treatments, with T1 showing the highest NH_4 value of 80.15 mg/kg, followed by T3 (72.1 mg/kg) and T2 (67.55 mg/kg).

This suggests that despite lower plant uptake during the minimum growth phase, NH_4 remains highly available, potentially allowing for better nitrogen retention in the soil. This is advantageous for crops that may require nitrogen in subsequent growing periods or seasons.

For NO_3 availability in CS1, the maximum uptake period results show that T1 had the highest nitrate concentration (42.08 mg/kg), followed by T3 (34.44 mg/kg) and T2 (32.34 mg/kg). This indicates that T1 supports the best nitrate availability during critical plant uptake periods, which is vital for crop productivity as nitrate is the most common form of nitrogen used by plants.

During the minimum uptake period, nitrate availability increased across all treatments. T2 showed the highest NO_3 concentration at 84.95 mg/kg, followed closely by T3 (81.29 mg/kg) and T1 (46.40 mg/kg). This suggests that even though plant uptake decreases during this period, nitrate levels remain high in the soil, especially in T2 and T3. This could be due to reduced nitrogen uptake, leading to the accumulation of nitrate in the soil.

CS2: INRAE-Clermont Ferrand, France

NH_4 availability for CS2 during the maximum uptake period highlights a distinct difference in ammonium concentrations across treatments. T1 exhibits the highest NH_4 concentration at 73.85 mg/kg, followed by T2 with 58.8 mg/kg, and T3 with 54.6 mg/kg. This indicates that T1 provides a more substantial nitrogen reservoir for plant uptake during the critical growth phase. Ammonium is a key form of nitrogen readily absorbed by plants, particularly during early stages of development, and the higher levels in T1 suggest better support for crop growth.

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In contrast to the ammonium data, the NO₃ availability graph for CS2 shows remarkably stable nitrate levels across both the maximum and minimum uptake periods. For all treatments, the nitrate concentration remains nearly constant, with T3 showing a slightly higher value (14.73 mg/kg) compared to T1 and T2 (around 12.7 mg/kg). The stability of nitrate levels across treatments and periods suggests that nitrogen in the form of nitrate is either not being fully utilized by the plants or that nitrate is being replenished at a similar rate to its uptake.

The lack of significant variation in nitrate levels raises questions about the soil's nitrification process or plant nitrogen demand. Since nitrate is a highly mobile form of nitrogen, more fluctuation between uptake periods would typically be expected. A closer examination of the soil microbial community, specifically nitrifying bacteria activity, may explain why nitrate levels remain stable.

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CS4: Aarhus University (AU), Denmark

For the maximum uptake period, the NH₄ availability is highest in T3 at 42.35 mg/kg, while T1 and T2 show relatively lower concentrations, around 38.85 mg/kg and 37.1 mg/kg, respectively. This trend indicates that ammonium availability remains relatively stable across treatments but peaks slightly in T3 during the maximum uptake period. This moderate variation suggests that T3 might provide marginally better nitrogen availability for plant uptake during critical growth periods.

During the minimum uptake period, a significant increase in NH₄ availability is observed, with T1 showing the highest ammonium concentration at 88.2 mg/kg, followed by T2 at 57.4 mg/kg, and T3 at 38.85 mg/kg. The larger increase in T1's ammonium levels during the minimum uptake period could suggest that plants are not effectively using the available nitrogen,

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leading to higher residual ammonium in the soil. Such findings could imply the need for better nitrogen management practices during non-peak periods to prevent nitrogen losses or inefficient use.

The NO₃ availability for CS4 shows some variability across treatments during both the maximum and minimum uptake periods. For the maximum uptake period, T2 exhibits the highest nitrate concentration at 29.46 mg/kg, followed by T1 at 24.04 mg/kg, and T3 at 22.48 mg/kg. The relatively higher NO₃ availability in T2 suggests that it could provide better nitrate-based nitrogen for plant uptake during the maximum uptake period, which is critical for ensuring optimal crop growth.

In the minimum uptake period, nitrate levels increased considerably in all treatments, with T2 showing the highest concentration at 44.63 mg/kg, followed by T3 at 42.20 mg/kg, and T1 at 38.43 mg/kg. The consistent increase in NO₃ during the minimum uptake period could indicate that plant nitrogen uptake decreases during this phase, resulting in the accumulation of nitrate in the soil. A need for careful nitrogen

management strategies is suggested to prevent nitrate leaching or environmental losses during periods of low plant nitrogen demand.

CS5: INIA-CSIC, Spain

The graph for NH₄ availability during maximum and minimum uptake periods in CS5 demonstrates consistent ammonium levels across treatments. In the maximum uptake period, the T1 and T3

treatments show the highest NH₄ concentration at 43.75 mg/kg, with T2 following closely at 43.4 mg/kg and T3 at 40.95 mg/kg. This suggests that all treatments provide relatively stable ammonium availability during the critical growth phases, ensuring sufficient nitrogen availability for plant development.

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For the minimum uptake period, the results are slightly lower across treatments, with the lowest NH₄ availability in T1 at 33.25 mg/kg and T3 showing the highest ammonium retention at 43.75 mg/kg. The consistent availability of NH₄ in T3 throughout both periods suggests a balanced nitrogen management system, which could help maintain soil fertility. These results also highlight the importance of treatment selection in ensuring stable nitrogen availability.

For NO₃ (nitrate) availability in CS5, the treatments display significant variation between the maximum and minimum uptake periods. During the maximum uptake period, the NO₃ concentrations are notably lower compared to the minimum period. T1 presents the highest nitrate concentration at 16.17 mg/kg, followed by T3 with 15.17 mg/kg, and T2 with 14.73 mg/kg. These results indicate that,

during the peak nitrogen demand phase, all treatments provide sufficient nitrate levels to support plant growth, though the overall concentrations are modest.

In contrast, during the minimum uptake period, nitrate availability increases across all treatments. T1 again leads with 25.14 mg/kg, closely followed by T2 at 24.92 mg/kg, and T3 at 21.48 mg/kg. The elevated NO₃ levels during the minimum period suggest that nitrate remains in the soil despite the reduced plant uptake, which could lead to environmental risks such as nitrate leaching, especially in T1 and T2 where the levels are highest. This highlights the need for improved nitrate management strategies to prevent potential nutrient losses and ensure sustainable nitrogen availability.

CS6: Wageningen University, Netherlands

In the CS6 graph for NH₄, the results highlight that the maximum uptake period showed a gradual increase in NH₄ levels across the three treatments, with T3 registering the highest value of 45.5 mg/kg, followed by T2 at 41.65 mg/kg and T1 at 39.9 mg/kg. The close range between the treatments suggests that the soil samples from CS6 have relatively balanced ammonium levels, which is critical for

plant nitrogen uptake during this growth phase. Since ammonium is a significant source of nitrogen for plants, the consistent levels across treatments are a good indication of the soil's ability to supply nitrogen.

The nitrate (NO₃) levels in the CS6 graph indicate much lower concentrations compared to ammonium, with T1 showing the highest value of 13.07 mg/kg, followed by T2 at 11.3 mg/kg, and T3 at 9.19 mg/kg. The data for the minimum uptake period mirrors these findings, with no significant deviations between max and min periods. The lower NO₃ levels in soil may be due to nitrate leaching or denitrification processes in the soil, which

can lead to reduced nitrate availability for plants during the growing period.

The limited variation in NO₃ values across treatments suggests that there may not be a significant impact of these treatments on nitrate availability. However, the relatively low nitrate levels compared to ammonium suggest that nitrogen in the CS6 soil samples is predominantly available in the ammonium form, probably affected by the soil pH and the microbial community composition (WP4 results).

CS7: LAMMC, Lithuania

In the analysis of NH₄ levels for CS7, we observe that the maximum uptake periods (T1, T2, and T3) show slight variations. T2 treatment exhibited the highest NH₄ concentration at 44.10 mg/kg, followed closely by T1 (43.05 mg/kg) and T3 (42.70 mg/kg). The difference between the treatments is relatively lower, indicating consistent NH₄ levels during the maximum uptake period. However, it is important to note that the NH₄ levels for T2 are marginally higher, which could suggest improved nitrogen availability under this treatment during the max uptake period.

During the minimum uptake period, NH₄ concentrations show more consistency, with T3 still leading at 45.16 mg/kg, but T2 and T1 following closely behind at 42.7 mg/kg and 41.3 mg/kg, respectively. The minimal variations between the treatments suggest that NH₄ availability remains relatively stable throughout different periods of plant uptake, providing steady nitrogen nutrition to plants

under CS7 conditions.

The NO₃ concentrations for CS7 during the max uptake period show notable differences among the treatments. T3 treatment displayed the lowest NO₃ levels, reaching 17.39 mg/kg, while T2 and T1 exhibited similar concentrations at 21.82 mg/kg and 20.16 mg/kg, respectively. This suggests that the T2 and T3 treatments provide better NO₃ availability during the max uptake period, potentially enhancing

nitrogen uptake efficiency for plants during this critical growth stage.

For the min uptake period, NO₃ levels show a consistent downward trend in T1 and T2 and increase in T3 compared to the max period. T3 shows the highest concentration at 26.91 mg/kg, followed by T2 (17.50 mg/kg) and T1 (16.17 mg/kg). The differences between the treatments are narrower in the max period, suggesting that NO₃ availability becomes more uniform during periods of high plant nitrogen demand. However, T3 consistently outperforms the other treatments, indicating a potential advantage for plant growth and nitrogen use efficiency.

CS8: TAGEM, Turkiye

In the NH₄ data for CS8, the concentrations for the maximum uptake period are relatively consistent across treatments, with T2 showing the highest value of 45.85 mg/kg, followed closely by T3 (45.5 mg/kg) and T1 (43.4 mg/kg). The minimum NH₄ levels show a slightly larger variation, with T2 being the lowest at 39.9 mg/kg, followed by T1 (38.5 mg/kg), and T3 (40.95 mg/kg). This uniformity suggests that all treatments provide a relatively stable supply of ammonium, though T2 may offer a marginal advantage in NH₄ availability during the max uptake period.

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For NO₃ concentrations, CS8 shows a more variable pattern between treatments. T2 has the highest NO₃ availability during the maximum uptake period, reaching 13.29 mg/kg, while T1 shows 10.52 mg/kg, and T3 has the lowest value of 11.85 mg/kg. During the min uptake period, T2 again leads with 15.5 mg/kg, followed by T1 (9.53 mg/kg), and T3, which drops sharply to 5.98 mg/kg. These results indicate that T2 may be more effective in maintaining nitrate availability in the soil.

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CS9: CRAW, Belgium

In CS9, the NH₄ levels exhibit minimal variation between the treatments, with all values close to each other. The maximum NH₄ values are 43.75 mg/kg for T2 and 42.35 mg/kg for T1, while T3 displays a slightly lower maximum value of 40.25 mg/kg. The minimum NH₄ values follow a similar trend, staying within the 40-44 mg/kg range, with T3 showing the lowest minimum value at 40.25 mg/kg.

The overall stability in NH₄ levels suggests a consistent availability of ammonium in the soil across the different treatments, which could be beneficial for plant uptake during the entire growth cycle.

The NO₃ levels in CS9 reveal more variation compared to NH₄, with the highest NO₃ levels observed in T2 (22.04 mg/kg) and T1 (21.48 mg/kg) during the maximum uptake period. The lowest NO₃ concentrations are recorded during the minimum uptake periods, especially in T1 (7.31 mg/kg) and T2 (11.07 mg/kg). This drop in NO₃ levels during the minimum uptake periods confirms nitrate availability to be more dynamic than

NH₄, with plants utilizing more nitrate during peak growth stages, leaving less available during the minimum periods.

Conclusion:

The analysis of NH₄ and NO₃ levels during both max and min uptake periods reveals critical insights into nitrogen management and soil fertility across different regions. NH₄, being a more stable form of nitrogen, is retained in the soil for longer periods, while NO₃ is more readily available but prone to leaching. Managing the balance between these nitrogen forms is crucial for sustaining soil fertility and ensuring that crops have access to adequate nitrogen throughout the growing season.

For sustainable agriculture, maintaining optimal levels of NH₄ and NO₃ is essential for plant health, yield optimization, and environmental protection. Adequate nitrogen levels support vigorous plant growth and enhance soil health by promoting microbial activity and nutrient cycling. However, inefficient nitrogen management can lead to nitrogen loss through leaching and volatilization, resulting in environmental harm and reduced crop productivity. Therefore, monitoring NH₄ and NO₃ levels and implementing appropriate nitrogen management strategies, such as precise fertilizer application and soil amendments, is crucial for sustainable agricultural practices.

NH₄ and NO₃ at Maximum Uptake Period

During the max uptake period, CS2 recorded the highest NH₄ concentration at 73.85 mg/kg, followed by CS1 with 62.3 mm/kg, which indicated optimal nitrogen availability in the form of ammonium for plant uptake. This result suggests that the soil in CS2 and CS1 have sufficient nitrogen levels to meet plant requirements, contributing to enhanced plant growth and productivity. CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7, and CS8 also demonstrated considerable NH₄ concentrations ranging between 37 to 45 mg/kg, signifying that nitrogen levels in these regions are adequate to support crop development.

demonstrated considerable NH₄ concentrations ranging between 37 to 45 mg/kg, signifying that nitrogen levels in these regions are adequate to support crop development.

In the max uptake period, CS1 again exhibited the highest NO₃ levels at 42.08 mg/kg, indicating efficient mineralization and nitrate availability for plants. This high nitrate concentration suggests that nitrogen cycling is active, and plants can readily access this essential nutrient. In contrast, sites such as CS5, CS7, and CS9 had much lower NO₃ levels, pointing to slower nitrate release or reduced nitrogen availability

in these soils.

NH₄ and NO₃ at Minimum Uptake Period

During the min uptake period, NH₄ levels were slightly lower overall, but CS1 still maintained the high concentration at 80.15 mg/kg. This highlights the soil's ability to retain NH₄ over time, providing plants with nitrogen throughout the growing season. CS4 also showed highest NH₄ levels (82.2 mg/kg), supporting the soil's nitrogen retention capacity.

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During the min uptake period, CS1 continued to display the highest NO₃ concentration at 84.95 and 81.29 mg/kg, demonstrating the soil's capacity to maintain nitrate levels even in periods of reduced plant uptake. Other sites, including CS4, CS7, and CS9, maintained moderate NO₃ levels, indicating that nitrogen availability persisted, albeit at reduced concentrations. However, NO₃ was nearly absent in

CS8 during this period, suggesting that these soils may face significant challenges in sustaining nitrate availability, potentially limiting plant growth and productivity during critical stages of development.

Phosphorus-solubilizing microorganisms

The presence and effectiveness of phosphorus-solubilizing microbial organisms were investigated in soil samples provided by project partners. In this study, aimed at identifying phosphorus-solubilizing microorganisms, Pikovskaya Agar (Pikovskaya et al., 1948) medium was used to evaluate the effects of soil health and microbial diversity.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Soil Samples

One gram of soil samples, sent by project partners, was inoculated onto Pikovskaya Agar medium. The samples were incubated at 25 °C for 7 days.

Microbial Isolation

At the end of the incubation period, the zones formed due to phosphorus solubilization were examined, and the colonies were purified for morphological analyses.

Colony Counting and Analysis

The number of colonies that developed in each petri dish was recorded, and the morphological characteristics of the isolates were observed under a microscope and grouped accordingly. The

number of colony-forming units (CFUs) was calculated using the formula from Christensen (1981). The ability to solubilize phosphorus was analyzed in liquid Pikovskaya medium.

Images of zones formed by phosphorus-solubilizing microorganisms on Pikovskaya medium

Results

In following table, the average values of CFU by dominated fungi and its phosphate Solubilization Efficiency are reported. Fungi that do not possess phosphate solubilization abilities are listed in the "Dominated Fungi" column but were not included in the efficiency calculations.

Table: Results of CFU by dominated fungi and its phosphate Solubilization Efficiency

Core-site	Treatment	CFU/g	Dominated Fungi	Phosphate Solubilization Efficiency (mg/L)
CS1	T1	234,29	Mucor spp., Rhizophus spp., Fusarium spp., Bipolaris spp.	49.5
	T2	371,02	Talaromyces spp., Cercospora spp., Trichoderma spp., Aspergillus spp.	79.5
	T3	163,92	Rhizoctonia spp., Penicillium spp., Fusarium spp.	38.0
CS2	T1	155,86	Bipolaris spp., Trichoderma spp., Rhizophus spp., Penicillium spp.	10.5
	T2	246,00	Aspergillus spp., Fusarium spp., Clonostachys spp., Alternaria spp.	12.20
	T3	267,45	Cladosporium spp., Penicillium spp., Mucor spp., Rhizoctonia spp.	11.20
CS4	T1	108,53	Trichoderma spp., Pythium spp., Phytophthora spp., Cercospora spp.	7.34
	T2	117,27	Mucor spp., Aspergillus spp., Penicillium spp.	9.30
	T3	179,41	Rhizophus spp., Fusarium spp., Mucor spp.	0.0

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	T1	221,27	Fusarium spp., Alternaria spp., Penicillium spp.	28.91
CS5	T2	288,33	Penicillium spp., Rhizoctonia spp., Aspergillus spp., Rhizopus spp.	7.25
	T3	119,87	Trichoderma spp., Pythium spp., Phytophthora spp., Aspergillus spp.	9.05
	T1	132,41	Mucor spp., Aspergillus spp., Cladosporium spp., Fusarium spp.	6.2
CS7	T2	169,15	Penicillium spp., Rhizopus spp., Pythium spp., Trichoderma spp.	20.6
	T3	112,62	Penicillium spp., Verticillium spp., Fusarium spp., Rhizopus spp.	11.6
	T1	137,90	Rhizopus spp., Fusarium spp., Mucor spp.	5.44
CS8	T2	208,12	Aspergillus spp., Fusarium spp., Talaromyces spp.	76.99
	T3	88,849.5	Penicillium spp.	68.80
	T1	0	Not Detectable	0
CS9	T2	0	Not Detectable	0
	T3	181,702.	Aspergillus spp., Penicillium spp.	14.95

Observed Dominated Fungi:

Mucor spp.: This fungus, commonly found in soil and decaying organic matter, contributes to the decomposition of organic material, thereby enhancing soil health. However, it can also lead to soft rot in stored agricultural products.

Rhizopus spp.: Rhizopus, prevalent in soil and decomposing organic matter, plays a significant role in breaking down organic materials, which benefits soil health. Nonetheless, it can cause soft rot in stored fruits and vegetables.

Fusarium spp.: *Fusarium* is a soil-borne plant pathogen that causes root rot and wilting, resulting in significant yield loss. Additionally, some *Fusarium* species produce mycotoxins, which pose health risks to humans and animals.

Bipolaris spp.: This plant pathogen is known for causing leaf spot diseases, particularly in crops such as maize and rice, which adversely affects plant health and productivity.

Talaromyces spp.: Found in soil, *Talaromyces* aids in the decomposition of organic matter, contributing to soil health. Some species are used in biotechnology, although others can cause spoilage in stored products.

Cercospora spp.: *Cercospora* is associated with leaf diseases, including leaf spots and early leaf drop in crops like sugar beet and beans, leading to reduced crop yield.

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Trichoderma spp.: This beneficial soil fungus is widely used in biological control to manage plant pathogens and promote plant growth. It typically does not have harmful effects.

Aspergillus spp.: Aspergillus is found in soil and organic matter, where it contributes to the breakdown of organic materials and has applications in biotechnology. However, some Aspergillus species produce aflatoxins, which are harmful to health.

Rhizoctonia spp.: A soil-borne plant pathogen, *Rhizoctonia* causes root rot and damping-off diseases, leading to decreased plant yield and health.

Penicillium spp.: Present in soil and organic matter, *Penicillium* contributes to the decomposition process and is used in antibiotic production. However, some species can cause spoilage and produce mycotoxins in stored products.

Alternaria spp.: Known for causing leaf spots and rots, *Alternaria* affects crops by leading to reduced yield, particularly under humid conditions.

Clonotachys spp.: This soil-borne fungus is used in biological control to combat plant pathogens and supports soil health through its antagonistic properties.

Cladosporium spp.: Found on plant surfaces and in soil, *Cladosporium* can cause leaf spots and decay, although some species are utilized in biotechnology.

Phytophthora spp.: A significant plant pathogen, *Phytophthora* causes root rot and leaf drop, resulting in substantial crop loss and compromised plant health.

Pythium spp.: *Pythium* is a soil-borne pathogen responsible for root rot and damping-off diseases, leading to severe yield reductions in affected crops.

Verticillium spp.: This pathogen causes wilt and root rot, impacting plant health and reducing crop yields significantly.

Results:

CS1: CREA, Italy

Upon examination of samples from organically managed CS1 site (Italy), it was observed that the soil is characterized by very high biological activity and richness. Although harmful fungi such as *Fusarium* were among the dominant species observed, their phosphorus solubilization capabilities were also investigated. It was found that these fungi possess significant phosphorus solubilization abilities, and the density of the colonies formed was notably high across all treatments.

The graph showed the colony-forming units (CFU/g) of T1, T2, and T3 treatments for CS1 separately. As illustrated in the graph, the T2 treatment has the highest average colony count at 371,028 CFU/g, followed by T1 at 234,296 CFU/g and T3 at 163,925 CFU/g. Additionally, the results show the Phosphate Solubilization Efficiency of the fungi, revealing that the highest phosphorus solubilizers are found in the T2

treatment. Identifying these fungi at the species level and categorizing them by genus is anticipated to offer valuable guidance for future research.

CS2: INRAE-Clermont Ferrand, France

Analysis of soil samples from CS2 site (France) shows the soil is rich in biological activity. However, it was found that the phosphorus-solubilizing capabilities of the dominant fungi are low. Fungi such as *Fusarium* spp., *Alternaria* spp., and *Bipolaris* spp., which are among the dominant species, are thought to potentially cause diseases and yield losses in crops grown in these soils. Despite a high

soil biological activity observed, these fungi may have pathogenic effects, underscoring the need for an effective plant protection program.

The graph showed the colony-forming units (CFU/g) of T1, T2, and T3 treatments for CS2 separately. As illustrated in the graph, the T3 treatment has the highest average colony count at 267,457 CFU/g, followed by T2 at 246,002 CFU/g and T1 at 155,864 CFU/g. Additionally, the provided results reveal that, despite the high colony densities of phosphorus-solubilizing fungi, their ability to solubilize phosphorus remains

insufficient. This situation can be interpreted because of the high density of fungi classified as harmful.

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CS3: INRAE- Montpellier, France

Soil samples from INRAE- Montpellier, France, did not exhibit detectable levels of biological activity.

CS4: Aarhus University (AU), Denmark

Analysis of soil samples from CS4 (Denmark), indicates that the soil exhibits moderate biological activity. However, it has been determined that the phosphorus-solubilizing capabilities of the dominant fungi are low. While the samples include beneficial fungi, there is a notable presence of harmful fungi, which form more dominant colonies compared to the beneficial ones. These fungi may potentially cause diseases and yield losses in crops grown in the soil. Despite the moderate levels of biological activity in terms of beneficial fungi, the presence of potentially pathogenic fungi highlights the need for an effective plant protection program.

The graph showed the colony-forming units (CFU/g) of

T1, T2, and T3 treatments for CS4 separately. As illustrated in the graph, the T3 treatment has the highest average colony count at 179,415 CFU/g, followed by T2 at 117,274 CFU/g and T1 at 108,535 CFU/g. Additionally, the obtained data indicate that, despite the moderately high colony densities of phosphorus-solubilizing fungi, their ability to solubilize phosphorus remains insufficient.

CS5: INIA-CSIC, Spain

Analysis of soil samples from INIA-CSIC, Spain, indicates that the soil is rich in biological activity. However, the phosphorus-solubilizing capabilities of the dominant fungi have been found to be low. Among the dominant fungi, while there are beneficial species present, harmful fungi are also identified, with the latter forming more dominant colonies compared to the beneficial ones. These harmful fungi may potentially cause diseases and yield losses in crops grown in the soil. Despite the moderate levels of biological activity concerning beneficial fungi, the presence of potentially pathogenic fungi underscores the need for an effective plant protection program.

The graph showed the colony-forming units (CFU/g) of T1, T2, and T3 treatments for CS5 separately. As illustrated in the graph, the T2 treatment has the highest average colony count at 288,334 CFU/g, followed by T1 at 221,279 CFU/g and T3 at 119,877 CFU/g. Additionally, results reveal that, despite the moderately high colony densities of phosphorus-solubilizing fungi, their ability to solubilize phosphorus remains insufficient.

CS6: Wageningen University, Netherlands

Soil samples from Wageningen University, Netherlands, did not exhibit detectable levels of biological activity.

CS7: LAMMC, Lithuania

Analysis of soil samples from LAMMC, Lithuania, indicates that the soil is moderately rich in biological activity. However, the phosphorus-solubilizing capabilities of the dominant fungi have been found to be low.

The graph showed the colony-forming units (CFU/g) of T1, T2, and T3 treatments for CS7

separately. As illustrated in the graph, the T2 treatment has the highest average colony count at 169,156 CFU/g, followed by T1 at 132,418 CFU/g and T3 at 112,623 CFU/g. Again, results show that, despite the moderately high colony densities of phosphorus-solubilizing fungi, their ability to solubilize phosphorus remains insufficient.

CS8: TAGEM, Türkiye

Analysis of soil samples from CS8 (Turkey), indicates that the soil is moderately rich for T1 and T3 treatments and rich for T2 treatment in biological activity. Additionally, among the colony-forming fungi, it was observed that colonies from the T2 and T3 treatments exhibited high phosphorus-

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solubilizing capabilities. Identifying these fungi at the species level and categorizing them by genus is anticipated to offer valuable guidance for future research. The graph showed the colony-forming units (CFU/g) of T1, T2, and T3 treatments for CS8 separately. As illustrated in the graph, the T2 treatment has the highest average colony count at 208,122 CFU/g, followed by T1 at 137,909

CFU/g and T3 at 88,849 CFU/g. Here, the table shows the Phosphate Solubilization Efficiency of the fungi, revealing that the highest phosphorus solubilizers are found in T2 and T3 treatment.

CS9: CRAW, Belgium

The analysis of soil samples from CRAW, Belgium, revealed that biological activity was only observed in the T3 treatments. While these activities can be considered indicative of relatively rich biological activity, they are insufficient to allow for a comprehensive comparison or meaningful conclusions regarding the overall core site.

Conclusion

When evaluating phosphorus-solubilizing microorganisms, it is evident that the treatment with the

highest concentration of colony-forming fungi, excluding CS2, is consistently T2. However, in all soils except those from CREA, pathogenic fungi were more prevalent than beneficial fungi. Phosphorus-solubilizing efficiency was notably higher in fungi isolated from the soil samples sent by CREA and TAGEM.

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Among these, prominent species identified in CREA include *Aspergillus* spp. (96.08 mg/L), *Talaromyces* spp. (87.92 mg/L), *Trichoderma* spp. (68.06 mg/L), *Cercospora* spp. (65.92 mg/L), and *Rhizoctonia* spp. (60.15 mg/L). Similarly, in TAGEM samples, *Talaromyces* spp. (87.92 mg/L), *Fusarium* spp. (77.13 mg/L), *Penicillium* spp. (73.17 mg/L), and *Aspergillus* spp. (65.92 mg/L) stood out. Notably, fungi traditionally associated with pathogenic effects, such as *Fusarium* spp., *Rhizoctonia* spp., *Penicillium* spp., and *Cercospora* spp., displayed unexpectedly high phosphorus-solubilizing capabilities. This paradoxical observation suggests that despite their harmful effects, these species may still play a significant role in phosphorus cycling, warranting further investigation into their dual impact on soil health and crop productivity.

WP3 - Soil macro- meso- and microfauna functional diversity – CSIC-INIA, CSIC-EBD

Task 3.1. Soil microfauna functional diversity - CSIC-INIA, CSIC-EBD

Nematodes were extracted by Baermann funnels (Barker, 1985) from soil samples collected in 8 core sites. Once extracted, all nematodes in each sample were counted under a binocular and 100 individuals were classified into functional groups. All nematode abundances were expressed as no. of nematodes /100 g of dry soil. To check for differences in nematode functional group composition across CS, linear models were used, while linear mixed models were used to assess the effects of treatments on nematode numbers with CS and block and random factors. All analyses were run on the R software (R core team, 2022).

Nematodes were classified into six functional groups (Yeates, 1993; Ferris et al., 2001):

- **Opportunistic bacterivores:** Bacterial-feeding nematodes that respond rapidly to increases in bacterial biomass. When the soil is fertilized or amended with organic products, bacterial

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biomass rapidly increases, and such increase is followed by a rapid enhancement of opportunistic bacterivore populations

- Generalist bacterivores: Bacterial-feeding nematodes that do not respond so fast to enrichment, with more stable populations and extremely resistant to environmental perturbation.
- Fungal feeding nematodes: Nematodes that feed on soil fungi by piercing fungal hyphae with a stylet.
 - Root associates: plant-feeding nematodes that feed on root hair, with a limited damage potential to plant health.
 - Plant-parasitic nematodes: Endo- and ecto-parasites that feed on plant root with medium to high damage potential to plant health.
 - Omnivores: nematodes able to feed in plants and other soil animals by piercing the food source with a stylet.
 - Predators: nematodes that feed on other soil animals (including other nematodes) either by piercing with a stylet or by ingesting them.

Total nematode abundances ranged between 331.1 and 6311.8 nematodes/100 g of dry soil. Mean nematode abundances per core site ranged between 885.1 (CS1, Italy) to 3186.2 (CS3, France) (Fig.1) and an absolute mean of 1751.3 nematodes per 100g dry soil. Nematode numbers significantly varied across CS ($F=5.68$, $p<0.05$).

Fig. 1. Total no. of nematodes /100 g of dry soil (tot) at different CS1 (CREA, Italy), CS2 (INRAE, France), CS3 (INRAE, France), CS4 (Aarhus Univ., Denmark), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, The Netherlands), CS7 (LAMMC, Lithuania), and CS9 (CRAW, Belgium).

Total no. of nematodes also varied across treatments. Nematode abundances at T1 (*first agroecological practice*) was significantly lower ($t = -2.21$, $p < 0.05$) than T3 (conventional practice) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Total no. of nematodes /100 g of dry soil (tot) at agroecological practices (T1, T2) compared to a standard control (T3).

A constrained redundancy analysis was used to test whether functional group community composition varied across CS and treatments. The resulting ordination (Fig. 3) was significant ($F=7.45$, $p<0.05$), with CS presenting a stronger influence on the ordination ($F=9.02$, $p>0.05$) than treatments ($F=1.93$, $p=0.07$).

Fig. 3. Constrained RDA ordination showing the influence of CS and treatments on nematode community functional composition. Ba = bacterivores, Fu = fungivores, Pp = plant-parasites, Root = Root-associates, Om = Omnivores, P = predators, Ben_pest = ratio beneficial to pest nematodes. Rel = relative abundances.

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The effect of treatments on the absolute and relative abundances of nematode functional groups and on the ratio beneficial to pest nematodes was assessed in the whole data set with linear mixed models with CS and block as random factors. Only 3 variables responded to the agroecological treatments (Fig. 4). The relative abundance of root associates was significantly ($t=-2.26$, $p>0.05$) higher in T2 (14.5%) compared to T3 (9.7%), probably responding to increased plant and root biomass in such treatment. The total abundance of omnivores was significantly higher in T1 (4.6%, $t=2.75$, $p>0.05$) than in T3 (2.8%), while the abundance in T2 (3.4%) was marginally significant ($t=1.94$, $p=0.05$). Finally, the ratio beneficial to herbivore nematodes was significantly ($t=-2.26$, $p<0.05$) lower (6.8) in T2 than in T3 (7.11).

Fig. 4. Relative abundance of root associates, absolute abundances of omnivores, and ratio beneficial to herbivore nematodes in the agroecological treatments across all CS. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

The relatively low response of nematode communities at the large -scale level, probably due to the experimental design heterogeneity, requires the analyses of each case study separately. At CS2 (INRAE) no differences were detected among soil management practices.

CS1 (CREA)

At the CREA experiment, only the relative abundance of plant-parasites responded to treatments, showing a significant ($F= 4.56$, $p<0.05$) increase in T2, the treatment with mixed cover crops in between-tree alleys (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Relative abundances of plant-parasitic nematodes (Pp_rel) at different agroecological management practices.

CS3 (INRAE)

The experiment at CS2 (INRAE) only compared two agroforestry systems: a system with a crop rotation in the tree alleys with tillage (T3) and a system with no tillage and perennial grass in the alleys. Nematodes greatly responded to such practices, showing a significantly lower no. of total nematodes ($F = 24.42$, $p < 0.05$), total and relative abundances of opportunistic bacterivores ($F = 170.8$ and $F = 13.35$, $p < 0.05$), total fungivores abundances ($F = 12.65$, $p > 0.05$), higher relative and absolute abundances of omnivores ($F = 11.53$ and $F = 2498$, $p < 0.05$), and a marginally significantly higher relative abundances of root-associates ($F = 5.19$, $p = 0.09$) and lower ratio beneficial to pest nematodes ($F = 4.71$, $p = 0.09$) in the agroecological treatment compared to the control. Some of these differences are shown in Fig. 6.

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Fig. 6. Relative abundances nematode functional groups at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS4 (AU)

The experiment at Aarhus University compares a monoculture (*Lolium perenne*) crop with two diversified systems with 2 and 6 plant spp. The relative abundance of opportunistic nematodes ($F = 5.38$, $p < 0.05$) and of omnivore nematodes ($F = 4.24$, $p < 0.05$) significantly increased in T1 compared to T3 (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Relative abundances of opportunistic bacterivores nematodes and omnivores at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS5 (INIA-CSIC)

The CS5 (INIA-CSIC) compares different tillage and crop rotation combinations. The control (T3) consists of wheat monoculture with minimum tillage, T1 consists of wheat monoculture with no-tillage and T2 is a crop rotation and no-tillage system. The comparison among treatments showed significantly lower nematode numbers ($F = 4.31, p < 0.05$), and abundances of bacterivores ($F = 4.56, p < 0.05$) and fungivores ($F = 4.16, p < 0.05$), in T1 and T2 compared to the control, while the absolute ($F = 9.85, p < 0.05$) (Fig. 8) and relative ($F = 4.89, p < 0.05$) abundances of omnivores were significantly higher (Figure 8).

Fig. 8. Absolute abundances of total nematodes and bacterivores, fungivores, and omnivore nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS6 (WUR)

The experiment at WUR compares 2 cover crop systems with 2 (T1) and 3 (T2) plant species with a fallow control (T3). In such systems, only the relative abundance of fungivores responded to management, showing significantly ($F = 5.01, p < 0.05$) higher values in the agroecological treatments (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Relative abundances of fungivores nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

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CS7 (LAMMC)

The management practices tested at LAMMC only showed significant effects on a single nematode group. The experiment compares a conventional tillage system (T3) with no tillage (T1) and no-tillage plus cover crops (T2) systems. Only the absolute abundances of plant-parasitic nematodes ($F = p < 0.05$) was significantly higher in T2 than in the control (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Absolute abundances of plant-parasitic nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS9 (CRAW)

The experiment at CRAW compares 3 rotation systems with different residue management. In the control (T3) crop residues are exported, while in T1 farmyard manure is used as organic amendment and in T2 residues remain in the field and cover crops are sowed. Only the ratio beneficial to pest nematodes responded significantly, with lower values at the agroecological treatment (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Ratio beneficial to pest nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

Conclusions

Considering all the obtained results, it is evident that the T2 treatment (the management practices with a higher agroecological component) exerted a stronger effect on the nematode community than T1 (Table 1). In general, both treatments reduce the absolute abundances of bacterivores and fungivores, leading to a decrease in the total number of nematodes in the community. In five of the CS experiments, the tested agroecological treatments included the reduction in the tillage intensity. In previous studies, it was found that the reduction of tillage implies a significant reduction of the amount of organic matter incorporated into the soil after the crop cycle ends. Such reduction of organic inputs might decrease available resources for soil microbes and consequently a reduction in the total abundances of bacterivore and fungivore nematodes. Oppositely, the absolute abundances on omnivore nematodes, more sensitive to physical perturbation than bacterivores and omnivores (ref) increased in T1 and T2. In T2, an increase of the total number of plant-parasitic nematodes was also detected, probably due to an increase in plant root biomass associated to such systems.

Table 1. Significant effects detected in the CS experiments. Each effect is a significant change detected in T1 or T2 compared to T3 at a given CS.

T1		T2	
Increase	Decrease	Increase	Decrease
Om_tot	tot	Om_tot	Ba_tot
Om_rel	Ba_tot	Om_tot	Ba_tot
Fu_rel	Ben_pest	Pp_tot	Ba1_tot
Ba1_rel	Fu_tot	Root_rel	Ben_pest
		Fu_rel	Ben_pest
		Pp_rel	Fu_tot
			Fu_tot
			tot
			tot

The percentage contribution of nematode trophic groups also changed in agroecological systems. An increase in the contribution of omnivores, root-associates, and plant-parasitic nematodes were also detected, probably due to a reduction in soil perturbation and the already mentioned increased resources available for herbivores. In general, the size of the whole nematode community decreased, so, despite the reduction in bacterivore and fungivore absolute numbers, the percentage contribution of such nematodes to the community occasionally increased. In both systems, the change in nematode community structure resulted in a reduction of the ratio beneficial to pest nematodes.

Task 3.2. Soil mesofauna functional diversity - CSIC-EEZA, CSIC-INIA

The two main groups of soil mesofauna (Acari and Collembola) were counted in core sites. Collembola abundances reached a maximum of 587.2 individuals per 100g of soil, and Acari presented a maximum total abundance of 488.9. However, Acari mean abundances were higher (94.6) than that of Collembolans (65.4). Difference across countries were large and significant ($p < 0.05$), and CS3 (INRAE) and CS7 (LAMMC) presented the higher abundances of both groups (Fig. 12). In CS7, Acari abundances were marginally ($p < 0.01$) affected by treatments.

Fig. 12. Absolute abundances of Acari and Collembola (no. individuals per 100g of soil) in each treatment at each CS.

Acari were further identified into main orders/suborders (Oribatida, Endeostigmata, Prostigmata, Heterostigmata, Mesostigmata and Astigmata). Not all groups appeared in all core sites. The groups with highest absolute abundances per 100 g of soil of each group was Mesostigmata (368.4 individuals), followed by Oribatida (325.9) and Prostigmata (280.3), while the other groups were less abundant (Heterostigmata 48.7, Astigmata 12.2, and Endeostigmata 9.2) (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Abundances of Acari orders/suborders per 100g of soil at each CS.

Considering the overall dataset, treatments had a marginal ($p < 0.01$) significant effect on Oribatida. Prostigmata were marginally affected ($p < 0.1$) by treatments in CS7.

Task 3.3. Soil macrofauna functional diversity - CSIC-EBD, CSIC-IPE

Soil macroarthropods were sampled with pitfall traps in cereal crops at four core-sites: CS3 (Mauguio-INRAE, France), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, Netherlands), and CS9 (CRA-W, Belgium). Traps (2.5 cm \varnothing , 5 cm deep, with a mixture of 70 % ethanol and 30 % monoethylene glycol) were active during four days in spring and all the caught arthropods were preserved in

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alcohol. All ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) were counted and identified. Using the data of the presence and abundance of the different ant species from the pitfall traps, a matrix of species abundance was constructed for the 48 different plots sampled in this study (12 plots/site x 4 sites). For each plot we used the total abundance for each species (the sum of five pitfalls). Other ecological indexes calculated were: species richness (S, number of ant species), Shannon's diversity index (H) and Pielou's evenness index (J) (details of calculations in Cerdá et al. 2012). All analyses were run on the R software (R core team, 2022).

Ant **species richness** at the study plots ranged between 11 species (CS5, Spain) and only one species (CS9, Belgium), and an absolute mean (\pm SD) of 3.1 ± 2.5 species per plot. Ant richness significantly varied across core sites (GLM, $\text{Chi}^2=366.52$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences, the highest richness value being that of CS5 (Spain), followed by CS3 (France) and then the very low values at CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (between which there are no significant differences) (Fig. 14A)

Fig. 14. Mean values (\pm SD) of different ant ecological indices per plot (each plot with 5 pitfall traps) at different core sites, CS3 (INRAE, France), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, The Netherlands), and CS9 (CRAW, Belgium). Different letters above the error bars indicate significant statistical differences between groups (GLM and contrast analysis). A. Total no. of ants (abundance). B. Ant species richness. C. Shannon diversity index. D. Pielou evenness index

Total **ant abundance** at the study plots ranged between 327 and 0 worker / 5 pitfall traps. Mean ant abundance per plot at the core sites ranged between 3.25 (CS9, Belgium) to 156.6 workers (CS3, France) (Fig.14B) and an absolute mean (\pm SD) of 92.6 ± 95.1 workers per plot. Ant numbers significantly varied across core sites (GLM, $\text{Chi}^2=78.87$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences, the highest mean abundance values being those of CS5 (Spain) and CS3 (France) (between which there are no significant differences), followed by CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (Fig. 14B).

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Mean **ant diversity** (measured with the Shannon-Weaver index) at the study plots ranged between 1.570 (CS5, Spain) and 0.00 (CS9, Belgium), and an absolute mean diversity (\pm SD) per plot of 0.643 ± 0.616 . Ant diversity significantly varied across core sites ($\text{Chi}^2=562.41$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences, the highest diversity value being that of CS5 (Spain), followed by CS3 (France) and then the very low values at CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (between which there are no significant differences) (Fig. 14C).

Mean **ant evenness** (measured with the Pielou index) at the study plots ranged between 0.774 (CS5, Spain) and 0.00 (CS9, Belgium), and an absolute mean evenness (\pm SD) per plot of 0.414 ± 0.377 . Ant evenness significantly varied across core sites ($\text{Chi}^2=446.73$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences between two groups of core sites: the higher evenness values being those of CS5 (Spain) and CS3 (France) and the lower values at CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (between which there are no significant differences) (Fig. 14D).

The Shannon diversity index considers both the number of species (richness) and their relative abundance. The Pielou evenness index ranges from 1 – when all species are equally abundant, to 0 – when all individuals in the sample belong to the same species. From our results, it is evident that there are two sites with a high ant abundance, species richness and diversity: CS5 and CS3; and the other two northernmost sites (CS9 and CS6) have much less abundance, richness and diversity of ants. Concerning the evenness of ant assemblages, in the southern core sites evenness have higher values (higher than 0.7), which means that the species present have a fairly homogeneous distribution (similar relative abundances), while in the northern core sites evenness values are very low, in CS9 (Belgium), because there is only one ant species (*Lasius niger*), and in CS6 (Netherlands) there are two ant species (*Lasius niger* and *Myrmica specioides*), but *L. niger* is much more abundant.

These differences between core sites could also be related to the local faunas (Table 2). Local ant faunas of the countries of the core sites follow a latitudinal gradient, with higher species richness in the southernmost sites (Spain and France, with 296 and 181 ant species, respectively) and lower

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richness in the northernmost sites (Belgium and Netherlands, with 97 and 78 ant species, respectively).

Table 2 – Comparison between the total ant species richness in the different countries and the local ant richness at the study core sites

Country	Number of ant species ¹	N of ant species at CS ²	Total abundance at CS ³	Local precipitation (mean total values at each CS)
Spain (CS5)	296	11	1852	389 mm/year
France (CS3)	181	7	1879	740 mm/year
Belgium (CS9)	97	1	39	730 mm/year
Netherlands (CS6)	78	2	674	895 mm/year

¹ Source: https://www.antwiki.org/wiki/Diversity_by_Country (Access 15 August 2024)

² Total number of ant species in the 12 plots at each core site.

³ Sum of worker abundance in the 60 pitfall traps / core site.

Total species richness, ant abundance, ant diversity and ant evenness did not vary across **treatments**. Mean values of all analysed ant ecological indices did not show statistically significant differences between T1 (*first agroecological practice*), T2 (*second agroecological practice*) and T3 (*conventional practice*) (GLM, see details in Figure 15).

Fig. 15. Mean values (\pm SD) of different ant ecological indices in the different treatments: two agroecological practices (T1, T2) and conventional practice as standard control (T3) A. Total no. of ants (abundance). B. Ant species richness. C. Shannon diversity index. D. Pielou evenness index.

According with their main food items (Arnan et al., 2015), the ant species were classified into three functional (trophic) groups:

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- Seed-eaters. Granivorous ants. The most important component of the diet is seeds. As they are seed predators, these ants can have a negative effect on plant populations.
- Insect-eaters. Scavenger ants. Mainly collect arthropod corpses. Scavenging has a positive ecosystem effect through nutrient redistribution
- Liquid food eaters. Sources of liquid food are Homoptera honeydew (aphid-tending ants) or nectar of flowers (nectarivorous). The effects of this trophic group can be negative (ants defend aphids against predators and aphids can be a problem for the plant by transmitting viruses) or positive (during nectar collection, ants can act as plant pollinators).

In order to detect differences in the structure of the communities in a multidimensional space we graphically represented the taxonomic (by species abundance, Fig. 16A) and functional (by trophic group abundance, Fig. 16B) community structure of each core site by performing a non-metric multidimensional scaling test (NMDS).

Fig. 16. Results of the NMDS analysis of (a) community taxonomic composition and (b) functional composition for ant plots. Each point represents a plot, the ovals depict the standard deviation of the point scores and the core site. Different core sites are represented with different colors: CS3 (INRAE, France), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, The Netherlands), CS9 (CRAW, Belgium).

The different study core sites present significant differences in the taxonomic composition of the ant communities ($F= 53.193$, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 16A) and in their functional traits related to ant diet ($F = 37.863$, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 16B).

Fig. 17. Logarithmic abundances of ant trophic groups at different agroecological management practices in each core site.

Ant abundances did not show statistically significant differences between treatments, but due to the different taxonomic composition of ants in each core site, there are also some different trends in the abundance of the different trophic groups (Fig.17).

CS3 and CS5 are the only core sites with scavenger (insect-based diet) and granivorous (seed-based diet) ant species. At **CS3 (France)**, the most abundant species was *Tetramorium semilave* (48%), an omnivorous ant with a 75% insect-based diet and 25% seed-based diet. *Cataglyphis piliscapa* (22%) the second in abundance, is a thermophilous scavenger species with near 100% insect-based diet. The third more abundant species is *Pheidole pallidula* (16%), another omnivorous species with a similar diet than *T. semilave* (75% insect-based and 25% seed-based diet). And the fourth species is the Mediterranean granivorous *Messor barbarus* (12%), with its 100% seed-based diet. At **CS5 (Spain)**, the most abundant species is the granivorous *M. barbarus* (44%), followed by the two omnivorous species *Aphaenogaster senilis* (20%) (50% insect-based and 50% seed-based diet) and *Tetramorium caespitum* (11%) (75% insect-based and 25% seed-based diet). Other two relatively abundant species are the Mediterranean scavengers *Proformica nasuta* (9%) and *Cataglyphis iberica* (8%) (both with 100% insect-based diet).

However, in the northernmost areas, **CS6 (The Netherlands)** and **CS9 (Belgium)** the dominant ant species is *Lasius niger* (99.5% in CS6 and 100% in CS9), an aphid-tending ant (25% insect-based diet and 75% liquid food-based diet). At CS6 there is a second species in very low abundance, *Myrmica specioides* (0.5%), an omnivorous species with a 50% liquid food-based diet and 50% insect-based diet.

In Belgium and the Netherlands, *Lasius niger* is a pioneer species during forest succession (Boer 2004, Dekoninck et al 2008), it is the only ant species that colonized and became established in the young forests resulting from natural succession on former grassland. On the other hand, in the Netherlands, Boomsma & van Loon (1982) observed a negative relationship between ant species diversity and the abundance of this pioneering ant *Lasius niger* in the dune grasslands. This negative relationship could probably explain the lack of an ant assemblage in the cereal crops at CS6 and CS9 sites. On the contrary, the absence in CS3 and CS5 of a dominant ant species provides to the ant species with a space that is, if not free, at least with a low level of competition, allowing the coexistence of different species forming ant assemblages, something that is usual in Mediterranean ant communities.

Finally, it seems that ant assemblages are relatively independent of local agroecological practices, because no significant differences have been detected between T1 (*first agroecological practice*), T2 (*second agroecological practice*) and T3 (*conventional practice*).

Plate 1. The most abundant ant species in CS3 and CS5 sites. A. Queen and workers of *Tetramorium semilaeve*. B. Queen and workers of *Cataglyphis piliscapa*. C. Workers and a big-headed soldier of *Pheidole pallidula*. D. *Messor barbarus* carrying a panicle. E. *Aphaenogaster senilis* workers cooperatively carrying a dead bee. F. *Tetramorium caespitum*. G. *Proformica nasuta*. H. *Cataglyphis iberica*. Credits: A and G, F. Rodríguez (Faluke); B, N.J. Veerecken; C and D, X. Cerdá; E and H, F. Amor; F, Alex Wild. Blue bar is ~3 mm length.

Plate 2. The ant species present in CS6 and CS9 sites. A. *Lasius niger* (credit: hormigueando.com). B. *Myrmica specioidea* (credit: Quentin Willot). Blue bar is ~1.5 mm length.

Soil earthworms were sampled in CS1 (CREA), CS6 (WUR) and CS9 (Belgium), where plot sizes were large enough as to permit earthworm sampling. In total, 229 earthworm individuals were recorded in the three CS. Three nematode species were found in CS1: *Lumbricus castaneus*, *Aporrectodea rosea*, and *Microscolex phosphoreus*, two nematode species were found in CS6: *Aporrectodea caliginosa* and *Lumbricus terrestris*, and 3 species were found in CS9: *Allolobophora chlorotica*, *Aporrectodea caliginosa*, and *Lumbricus terrestris*.

Abundances per plot ranged between 0 and 24 individuals per plot. Average abundances per plot were 0.83 (CS6), 6.83 (CS1) and 11,42 (CS9). While CS significantly affected earthworm abundance ($p < 0.05$), treatments did not ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18. No. of earthworms found per plot at three core sites.

Task 3.4. Identification of key attributes of soil food web structure which drive C cycling.

Several elements of the soil fauna presented significant relationships with TOC, which will be explored in further analyses. In relation to the nematode community, TOC was related to the relative abundance of predator and omnivore nematodes ($r=0.49$, $p>0.05$) (Fig. 19), while the total abundances of bacterivores and fungivores presented negative relations ($r= -0.31$ and $r= -0.26$ respectively, $p<0.05$) (Fig. 19).

Fig. 19. Correlations between the proportion of predator and omnivore nematodes, total bacterivores, and total fungivores, with TOC in bulk soil.

Only the total abundance of Endeostigmata mites presented a significant (and negative) correlation with TOC ($r = -0.36$, $p > 0.05$).

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WP4 - Soil microbial functional diversity – CEBAS-CSIC, CREA

Task 4.1 Soil microbial functional diversity: Identification of the major drivers of C cycle to use as indicators of C use efficiency.

Subtask 4.1.1 Agroecological practices effect on soil microbial community (CEBAS-CSIC)

DNA from soil samples have been sequenced (bacteria and fungi) by CEBAS (CSIC-INIA) corresponding to only one sampling at maximum nutrient uptake (MAX) according to the sampling plan. Soil samples were representative of several pedo-climatic EU Regions (Atlantic-Continental (Denmark-CS4); Atlantic (France-CS2; Netherlands-CS6; Belgium-CS9); Nemoral (Lithuania-CS7); Mediterranean north (Italy-CS1; France-CS3; Turkey-CS8); Mediterranean South (Spain-CS5)) and a gradient of agricultural practices, ranging from the most intensive (e.g. intense tillage, monocropping, mineral fertilization) to the most disruptive ones (e.g. agroforestry). Each field experiment showed three treatments, two sustainable managements (high intensification practices (T1) and low intensification practices (T2) and the conventional (T3).

Extraction of DNA, sequencing, analysis of sequences, prediction of functionality and statistical analysis is already described in deliverable 4.1.1.

In general, the alpha diversity index (Shannon index, CHAO, Simpson and observed ASVs) measured as Response Ratio (LRR) showed that the different agro-ecological intensifications did not increase significantly ($p < 0.05$) the diversity of bacterial and fungal community compared to control soil.

Both bacteria and fungi were influenced by interaction between treatment and site (Fig. 1A-1B) which indicates that soil microbial diversity is not only related to agro-ecological intensification, but also closely related to the site of the case study. We observed clustering of soils based on their distribution from Denmark/Netherlands in the north to Spain/Italy in the south (Fig. 1A-1B).

Fig 1A- Bacterial (A) PCoA analysis representing the beta diversity of all case studies and treatments. (Denmark-CS4); (France_1-CS2); (Netherlands-CS6); (Belgium-CS9); (Lithuania-CS7); (Italy-CS1); (France_2-CS3); (Turkey-CS8); (Spain-CS5). T3: control; T1: lower intensification (ECO); T2: higher intensification (SUST).

Fig 1B- Fungi (B) PCoA analysis representing the beta diversity of all case studies and treatments. (Denmark-CS4); (France_1-CS2); (Netherlands-CS6); (Belgium-CS9); (Lithuania-CS7); (Italy-CS1); (France_2-CS3); (Turkey-CS8); (Spain-CS5). T3: control; T1: lower intensification; T2: higher intensification.

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Beta diversity showed the differences in the microbial composition between different agro-ecological intensifications in each case study. For bacteria, only four out of nine case studies (CS7, CS9, CS2 and CS1) showed significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between agro-ecological intensifications, while for fungi, six out of nine case studies (CS5, CS7, CS6, CS9, CS2 and CS1) showed significant differences. Differences were found between treatments but not always between T3 and the other agro-ecological treatments (T1 and T2).

Among the nine case studies and different agro-ecological intensification treatments (T1 and T2), bacteria were dominated by Actinobacteria (11-38 ~28%), Proteobacteria (19-26 ~22.5%), Acidobacteria (9-16 ~13%), Firmicutes (1.3-24 ~9.6%), Chloroflexi (3.2-9.0 ~6%) and Verrucomicrobia (1.4-7 ~6%), accounting for the 85% of all ASVs observed.

Regarding fungi community, treatments were dominated by Ascomycota (37.6-79 ~61%), Mortierellomycota (6.86-45.0 ~22%), Basidiomycota (4.27-10 ~10.20%) and Chytridiomycota (3.18-8.27 ~5.18%) accounting for the 98% of all ASVs observed.

For each case study the significant increase of bacterial and fungal phylum of different agro-ecological intensification treatments (T1 and T2) compared to control (T3) measured by LRR were different. Globally, higher number of phylum increased by T1 than T2 treatment.

At genus level, the higher abundance bacteria were *Bacillus* (~6.39), *Candidatus Udaeobacter* (~3.6), *Arthrobacter* (~2.8), *Gaiella* (~1.94%), *Sphingomonas* (~1.55%), *Nocardiodes* (~1.54%), *Rubrobacter* (~1.24%), *Microvirga* (~1.21%) and *Streptomyces* (~1.05%) (Fig. 2A). For fungi the predominant fungal were *Mortierella* (~13.13%), *Fusarium* (~6.40%), *Gibellulopsis* (~6.65%), *Podila* (~4%), *Cladosporium* (~3.56%), *Alternaria* (~2.72%), *Exophiala* (~2.98%) or *Pseudorotium* (~2.52%) (Fig 2B)

In each case study, bacteria with growth promoting activity, biocontrol activity, and key nutrient cycles had significant increased according to the agro-ecological intensification treatment (T1 and T2). Also, according to bacteria, the increase of fungi was higher in T1 treatment for CS5 and CS9, while for CS1, CS2, CS6, CS7 and CS8 the increase was higher in T2 treatment.

The two main types of beneficial fungi below ground are mycorrhizae and saprophytes (biostimulants and biocontrol agents) and plant pathogens. We observed in general no increased in beneficial fungi in these treatments, although some plant pathogens were observed.

Fig 2. Bacterial (A) and fungal (B) stacked bar plot representing the mean relative abundances at the genus taxonomic level. (Denmark-CS4); (France_1-CS2); (Netherlands-CS6); (Belgium-CS9); (Lithuania-CS7); (Italy-CS1); (France_2-CS3); (Turkey-CS8); (Spain-CS5). T3: control; T1: lower intensification; T2: higher intensification.

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Influence of different intensifications on bacterial and fungal functional abundance

Carbon, nitrogen and sulphur cycles and their function in terrestrial ecosystems are hot topics in soil carbon cycling and ecology. Identifying the structure and functions of soil microbial communities is necessary because microorganisms play a vital role in the nitrogen, sulphur, and carbon cycles. In our study 19 ecological functional groups related to C, 13 ecological functional groups related to N and 7 ecological functional groups related to S cycle were detected (Fig. 3) The abundances of functional groups related to S cycle was quite low for all treatments and in all sites of study with values ranged 0.01-0.1 %.

The abundance of functional groups involved in C cycle showed different behaviour depend on the functional group and site of sampling (case study), indicating a change in the specific pathways. The increase of this functional gene contributes to assimilation and utilization of carbon by soil bacteria. However, the variation due to change of agro-intensification management was low.

Chemoheterotrophs showed the highest abundance of all C genes in all treatments and all case studies. At the same time all soil samples showed lower abundance of hydrocarbon degradation values ranged 0.01-0.1 %. However, aromatic compounds degradation showed values ranged 1-10% in all case studies except CS1. Case studies CS5, CS3 and CS8 showed higher activity, in general, independently of the agro-ecological intensification treatment. Lignolysis showed the humus formation related to lignin degradation and from cellulose and hemicellulose degradation products. This activity was higher in CS9 and CS3 (1-10%) while in CS8 this activity diminished completely (0.01-0.1%) independently of treatments (Fig 3). The other case studies showed values around 1%. This could indicate high C fixation in soils that can be also due to the case study.

Cellulolysis showed contrasting results. CS3 and CS9 showed lower values ~1%, while CS1, CS4, CS7 and CS9 showed values 0.01-0.1%, considering that Cellulolysis groups are the most abundant nitrogen-free soil organic matter, enhancing the breakdown of stable humus to release nutrients (Zhou et al., 2020). In all case studies the values of methanotrophy were 0.01-0.1% (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Heat map of the abundance of predicted bacterial functional groups (C, N and S cycle). (Denmark-CS4); (France_1-CS2); (Netherlands-CS6); (Belgium-CS9); (Lithuania-CS7); (Italy-CS1); (France_2-CS3); (Turkey-CS8); (Spain-CS5). T3: control; T1: lower intensification; T2: higher intensification.

Oxygenic photoautotroph and photoautotroph showed that in CS5 the agro-ecological intensification SUST treatments showed higher abundance than CONV and ECO. While in the other treatments no differences were observed between treatments (Fig. 3). Case study CS1, CS2 and CS8 showed abundance ranges 0.01-0.1%, followed by CS4, CS6 and CS7. The highest abundance was showed in CS3 and CS9.

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Functional genes related to N showed that N fixation did not show differences between agro-intensification treatments but showed differences between case study. The abundance was $CS8 < CS5 < CS1 \sim CS7 < CS6 < CS3 \sim CS2 \sim CS4 \sim CS9$ (Fig. 3). It means that they are a gradient of limitation for plant N acquisition. The nitrification was in general for all case studies quite low (0.01-0.1%). It means that it was a reduction of negative impact on the environment, because of nitrification is directly involved in the emission of the greenhouse gas nitrous oxide, nitrate contamination of freshwater resources, eutrophication, and loss of nitrogen from agricultural fields (Norton and Ouyang 2019; Prosser et al. 2020). While denitrification was quite low in CS5, CS6, CS8, CS1, CS2 and CS3, and higher in CS7 and CS9 (Fig 3). It means that probably in CS7 and CS9 the efficacy of convert NO_3^- in N_2 is higher than in the other case studies.

The fungal community in our study showed that all case studies showed higher abundance of saprophyte (5-25%) independently of the agro-ecological intensification treatment (Fig. 4). The highest values of arbuscular mycorrhizal was only observed in CS5, where the higher abundance was observed in treatment T1 ~5% compared to T3 and T2~1%, while the other case studies showed an abundance of this functional groups between (0.01-0.1 %). At the same time all case study showed abundance of ectomycorrhizal between (0.01-0.1 %) (Fig.4).

In addition, all case study independently of the treatment showed high abundance of plant pathogen 25% that means that none of the agro-ecological intensification treatments reduced plant pathogen and even all case study showed plant pathogens in high intensity.

Fig. 4. Heat map of the abundance of predicted fungal guilds. (Denmark-CS4); (France_1-CS2); (Netherlands-CS6); (Belgium-CS9); (Lithuania-CS7); (Italy-CS1); (France_2-CS3); (Turkey-CS8); (Spain-CS5). T3: control; T1: lower intensification; T2: higher intensification.

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In conclusion, the results showed that the magnitude of response of bacterial and fungal communities and functionality to agro-intensification managements differs between case studies. In each case study bacterial and fungal community are strongly affected by the different intensification treatments. Treatment T1 increased abundance on phyla for Fungi and Bacteria compared to T2 treatment. However, abundance of genera related to C and N cycling, biocontrol activity and plant growth were in general higher in T2 treatment than in T1 treatment. The most considerable abundance of C and N functional genes depends on functional pathways and cases study, although in the most of case studies the C-related functionalities are associated to agro-intensification treatments. The dominant fungal guilds were saprophytic and plant pathogens. Fungal guilds also depend on case study, independently of agro-intensification treatment.

Subtask 4.1.2 Identification of functional genes as indicators of C use efficiency (CREA)

Results of a study on the combined evaluation of soil C enzyme activities and functional genes, performed in the LTE site of CREA-AA Bologna, have been published in the manuscript: Saccà ML, Caputo F, Ceotto E, Fornasier F (2024) Fungal β -glucosidase gene and corresponding enzyme activity are positively related to soil organic carbon in unmanaged woody plantations. *Soil Ecology Letters* 6:240238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42832-024-0238-2>.

***Task 4.2 Effect of agroecological practices on microbial biomass and activity* (LAMMC - CREA)**

Promoting agroecological management practices such as minimal soil disturbance and greater plant diversity significantly enhances the soil microbial community. The current focus on the composition and structure of the soil microbial community, and the changes it undergoes due to various environmental factors, is noteworthy. Furthermore, microbial activity is a reliable indicator of soil health because soil microorganisms are crucial for the breakdown of organic matter and the biogeochemical cycles that affect soil fertility.

Objective

To assess the soil microbial biomass carbon (SMBC), functional diversity and metabolic activity of the microbial community of soils under different sustainable agricultural practices.

Methods

SMBC was analysed at LAMMC (Lithuania) using the fumigation-extraction method (Vance *et al.*, 1987). For this analysis soil samples were received from CS1, CS2, CS3, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7, CS8. Microbial community-level physiological profiles (CLPPs) for samples from two of the core sites (CS6 - WUR, The Netherlands, and CS8 - TAGEM, Türkiye) were taken during the peak period of plant nutrient uptake but were received later than those from the other core sites and were analysed in the early months of the year. The CS6 (WUR) samples were analysed by personnel at MBG Santiago-CSIC (Spain), while the CS8 (TAGEM) samples were analysed by personnel at LAMMC (Lithuania). Samples from the remaining six core sites - CS1 (CREA, Italy), CS2 (INRAE-Clermont Ferrand), CS3 (INRAE-Montpellier), CS4 (AU, Denmark), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), and CS9 (CRAW, Belgium) - had been previously analysed by the MBG Santiago and LAMMC teams. Upon receipt, all long-term experiment (LTE) samples were immediately prepared and processed in the respective laboratories. CLPP analyses were then performed using Biolog Ecoplates™, adhering to a harmonised and unified protocol established by both MBG Santiago-CSIC and LAMMC. Once the CLPP analysis of all samples from the LTEs was completed, personnel at LAMMC and MBG Santiago-CSIC processed the results to calculate several key metrics, including the AWCD (Average Well Colour Development), microbial richness (R), Shannon's diversity index (H), and Pielou's evenness index (J'). Normalised absorbance values, reflecting the degradation of different carbon sources in the Biolog Ecoplates™, were also estimated. All these data were compiled into a database template provided by the project coordinators. The AWCD, normalised absorbance values, and the three indices (R, H, and J') are going to be used to assess the impact of sustainable agricultural practices on the metabolic potential of microbial communities during the period of maximum nutrient uptake by plants, when the soil functions as a carbon source.

Data analysis

Shapiro–Wilk and Levene tests were performed to check normality and homogeneity of variance, respectively. Depending on the results, ANOVA or Kruskal–Wallis test followed by Tukey's HSD or Dunn's post hoc tests were used, respectively.

Results

As shown in Fig. 4.2.1, the highest SMBC value reaching $428.9 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ was observed in CS6 (Netherlands) and the lowest ($137 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) - in CS5 (Spain). SMBC values in CS1 (Italy) and CS 2 (France) were close to those observed in CS6 (Netherlands). Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the agroecological intensification levels (T1 - 1st agroecological intensification level, T2 - 2nd agroecological intensification level and T3 - control) were revealed only in CS4 (Denmark) and CS9 (Belgium). The data demonstrated the SMBC increase in the T2 treatment, where six-species mixture was used for cover cropping, compared to *Lolium perenne* L. and white clover mixture (T1 treatment) at site CS4 (Denmark). Similarly, in CS9 (Belgium), the highest SMBC was also observed in T2 (Crop residues restitution + cover crop), but significant differences were obtained with T3 (Residue exportation).

Figure 4.2.1. The soil microbial biomass carbon ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) in bulk soil, under diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at experimental sites. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences between treatments.

The metabolic activity of soils subjected to diverse agroecological practices across the core study sites was analysed, with the results revealing expected variations in AWCD (Average Well Color Development) values across these locations (Fig. 4.2.2). Significant differences in AWCD values between treatments were observed at two core sites CS2 (France) and CS8 (Türkiye), with statistical significance noted at $p < 0.05$. Notably, at the CS2 site, the control treatment exhibited the highest AWCD value, whereas at CS8, the control treatment showed the lowest AWCD value.

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Figure 4.2.2. Average well colour development (AWCD) of the soil community from diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at core sites. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences between treatments.

As in AWCD, normalised absorbance values (Fig. 4.2.3), microbial richness (R) (Fig. 4.2.4), and Shannon’s diversity index (H) (Fig. 4.2.5) also showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments only at CS2 and CS8 sites. Furthermore, a significant difference in Pielou’s evenness index (J’) (Fig.4.2.6) was observed only at CS8 site, indicating variability in the distribution of the microbial community. These results underline the site-specific impact of agroecological practices on soil microbial activity.

Figure 4.2.3. Normalised absorbance values of the soil community from diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at core sites. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences between treatments.

Figure 4.2.4 Richness index (R) of the soil community from diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at core sites. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences between treatments.

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Figure 4.2.5. Shannon's diversity index (H') of the soil community from diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at core sites. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences between treatments.

Figure 4.2.6. Pielou's evenness index (J') of the soil community from diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at core sites. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences between treatments.

Enzymatic activity and dsDNA (CREA-VE)

Objectives

Based on the workflow of the AGROECOseqC, the two main activities programmed in the task 4.2 and fitting into deliverable D.4.2.2 are:

1. Enzymatic activity (several enzymes related to the C, N and P cycles) and microbial biomass as dsDNA will be evaluated on samples from the Core sites and on those from those in which functional genes will be developed.
2. Determinations on microbial biomass C and indirect quantification of C-stock in living woody deciduous species and in deadwood considering the different components and decay classes.

Sampling and methods

A total of 288 samples from both the 8 core sites and other sites identified at the beginning of the project, were processed at the CREA VE in Gorizia (Italy). The samples were sent to CREA by each partner between September 2022 and June 2023 by refrigerated shipment and stored at -20 °C until processing. The samples were processed in three batches from June 2023 to November 2023.

Fifteen enzyme activities (Table 1- D 4.2.2) were quantified in soil extracts as described in (Cardelli et al., 2019). Enzymes were extracted by heteromolecular exchange using a 3% lysozyme solution (Cowie et al., 2013); then their activities were quantified in microplates using fluorogenic substrates as reported in Table 1 – D4.2.2. The enzyme activities which were evaluated were those most widely used to assess soil functionality variation in response to land use or changes in the environmental variables (Cardelli et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020; Fanin et al., 2022). The original sample code was maintained up to the final dataset. When completed, the final dataset of enzyme activity was submitted to the coordinator for data analysis.

All the 288 soil samples were subjected all the analysis of double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) which was assumed as a measure of soil microbial biomass. This analysis was carried out as described by Fornasier et al. (2014) and data were expressed as $\mu\text{g dsDNA g}^{-1}\text{dry soil}$. When completed, the final dataset of dsDNA was transferred to the shared the dataset of soil features of the eight cores of the AGROECOseqC project.

Relationship between enzyme activity and functional genes

In D4.2.2 on enzyme activity, the evaluation of functional genes encoding enzymes involved in the C cycle was performed, and the results have been described in D7.1.1.1. and D4.1.2.

Briefly, six enzyme activities (α -glucosidase, β -glucosidase, α -galactosidase, β -galactosidase, xilosidase and β -D-glucuronidase) and five functional genes (cellulase, endoglucanase, endoxylanase, bacterial β -glucosidase and fungal β -glucosidase) were evaluated in four treatments (tree plantations in short forest and arable soil). A positive correlation of the β -glucosidase enzymatic activity was found with the fungal gene encoding β -glucosidase, while not with the corresponding gene of bacterial origin, thus revealing the distinct contribution of microbial taxonomic groups to organic C turnover. Results of this study are reported in Saccà et al. 2024.

Microbial biomass C and indirect quantification of C-stock in woody plantations- C stock and soil fungi

In a study on soil fungi as indicator of C metabolism in soil carried out in T 7.1 (Manici et al. 2024b), based on next generation sequencing analysis, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota were the most represented phyla and fungal community composition which significantly differed for both vegetation cover (plantations with three woody species which were abandoned for 20 years) and soil management (arable soil vs no tillage of the abandoned plantations).

Arable soil, characterised by a significantly lower SOM than woody plantations, showed the lowest enzyme activity, but the enzyme activity significantly differed also between the woody plantations. Cluster analysis (Fig. 1) showed a clear separation of the enzymatic profile of arable soils from that of woody plantations, which clustered together with more than 90% similarity. This figure clearly showed that land use (tillage vs no tillage) deeply affects C metabolism and accumulation, but also

that the latter vary also between different vegetation covers.

Fig. 1 Cluster analysis (UMPGA) of the 10-enzyme profile of the four treatments using Bray-Curtis distance and 1000 bootstrap replicates. The base of the triangles represents the 3 replicates of each treatment. (Manici et al., 2024. Appl. Soil Ecol.)

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In vitro study on the functional role of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota in soil

This is an *in vitro* study carried out to investigate functionality of the two main group of fungi, Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes, inhabiting the upper soil which are most involved in C- Cycle. Basidiomycetes are generally considered more active in the degradation of lignin, whereas Ascomycetes (or microfungi) are primarily responsible for the degradation of plant cell wall polysaccharides (cellulose and hemicellulose, pectins). Although soil microbial community composition has been associated with specific enzyme activities and soil carbon chemistry, the relationship between community structure and specific soil processes is commonly found in literature to be non-linear due to the complexity of the interaction among the microbial consortia. Therefore, enzymatic profile of two synthetic populations of Ascomycota (or microfungi) and Basidiomycota were compared to better understand the functional significance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota changes in soil and their role on C-cycle when different vegetal cover and soil management are applied.

The activities of twenty-five enzymes (Table 1- D4.2.2) extracted from the mycelium of a total of 29 pure fungal colonies belonging to 26 species (8 *Basidiomycota* and 21 *Ascomycota* species) were quantified in microplates using fluorogenic substrates already above described for soil enzyme activity. According to multivariate analysis of variance (AMOVA), *Ascomycota* and *Basidiomycota* differed significantly ($P=0.0001$) in enzyme profile.

Table 1 D.4.2.2. List of the enzyme with the relevant substrate and the activity expression.

acronym	enzyme	substrate	enzyme activity
aryS	arylsulfatase	4-methylumbelliferyl sulfate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
betaG	beta-glucosidase	4-methylumbelliferyl-beta-D-glucopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
xilo	xilosidase	4-methylumbelliferyl beta-D-xilopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
chit	chitinase	4-methylumbelliferyl-N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminide	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
APROT	aspecific protease	fluorescein-labeled casein	fluorescence units
CBZ	serin-like protease	N-alpha-CBZ-L-Arginine 7-amido-4-methylcoumarin hydrochloride	nanomoles of 7-amino-4methyl coumarine)* g-1 dry soil* hour-1
leu	leucine-aminopeptidase	L-Leucine 7-amido-4methyl-coumarine hydrochloride	nanomoles of 7-amino-4methyl coumarine)* g-1 dry soil* hour-1
acP	acid phosphomonoesterase	4-methylumbelliferyl phosphate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
bisP	phosphodiesterase	bis(4-methylumbelliferyl)phosphoric acid	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
piroP	pirophosphate-phosphodiesterase	bis(4-methylumbelliferyl)pyrophosphoric acid	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
alkP	alkaline phosphomonoesterase	4-methylumbelliferyl phosphate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
inositP	phytase	4-methylumbelliferyl myo-inositol-1-phosphate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
FDA	fluorescein diacetate hydrolysis	5,6-carboxyfluorescein	nanomoles of 5,6carboxyfluorescein * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
OX	oxidase	10-Acetyl-3,7-dihydroxyphenoxazine	picomoles of resorufin * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
PEROX	Peroxidase	10-Acetyl-3,7-dihydroxyphenoxazine + H2O2	picomoles of resorufin * g-1 dry soil* hour-1

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Ascomycetes (or microfungi) showed a broader enzymatic profile than *Basidiomycetes*. In the latter seven out of the twenty-five enzyme activities detected in *Ascomycetes* were missing, including the enzymes of phosphorus and sulphur metabolisms and alpha galactosidase. Contrastingly, many enzymes responsible for plant polysaccharide degradation, such as alpha-galactosidase, beta-mannosidase or xilosidase were detected in the isolates of both fungal phyla. This indicates likely underestimated ability of *Basidiomycetes* (typical wood fungi) to degrade plant polysaccharides; to the contrary, the widest enzyme profile of *Ascomycota* (microfungi) and their highest enzymatic inter- and intra-genus variability indicates their higher adaptability to metabolize different crop residues and litters.

Datils of these findings can be found in (Manici et al. 2024a).

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WP5 - Level of synchrony between plant nutrient demand, soil nutrient fluxes and soil organic matter dynamics – INRAE, AU

Task 5.1: Measurements of plant nutrient demand at different moments

Plant demand corresponds to the amount of nutrients needed to convert the photosynthesis-derived carbon in biomass. The plant demand is a potential that is not necessarily satisfied by the soil offer of soluble nutrients.

We estimated plant nutrient demand from 1) the plant net photosynthesis under non-limited conditions of nutrients (biomass growth under fertilizer conditions) and 2) the critical nutrient content of plant growth, that can be specific of the species, plant functional type or even the isolation of the plant respect to others.

Material and methods

On each plot of the AGROECOseqC project, subplots A and B were dedicated to the estimation of the plant nutrient demand.

Approximately 3 weeks before the sampling (Time 0), plant biomass was collected, dried and weighted in the subplot A, and we added an amount of fertilizer in subplot B that ensured no nutrient limitation for plants. After three weeks (Time 1), we collected, dried and weighted the plant biomass in subplot B, being the difference between subplots B and A the main indicator of plant net photosynthesis under non-limited conditions of nutrients.

Figure 1. Principle sketch for estimating net plant photosynthesis involving two biomass sampling times and two fertilization levels (the standard and a sub-plot with optimal/unlimiting nutrient supply). By standard we mean the fertilization level (+ nutrient supply by the soil) that is already included in the studied practices/treatment. In this plot, T0 and

T1 refer to Time 0 and Time 1, respectively.

Calculations

We calculated plant nutrient demand (PND, in g N/m²) with the general equation of C3 plants following Louarn et al. (2021) and references therein:

$$\text{PND} = \text{N}_{\text{crit}} * \text{TW}$$

Being TW the plant biomass in the whole plot (in g/m²) and N_{crit} the critical N content (in %), which is calculated with the Eq. 1 of Louarn et al. (2021):

$$\text{N}_{\text{crit}} = a * \text{TW}^b$$

Being a and b the parameters of the critical dilution N curve. We decided a = 4.8 and b = -0.34 for a general plant C3 approach Lemaire (1990).

However, at low biomass levels (i.e. 100 g/m²) it is preferable to use equations for individual plants to represent reduced plant competition (Louarn et al. 2021). These equations normally have b parameters closer to 0 than the ones used for multi-individual crops. As these equations are quite scarce in literature, we have replaced the b parameter by -0.12 as a consensus value.

Results

Plant nutrient demand was calculated for all the sites except for CS4 (Denmark), who were not able to collect and send the samples due to logistic reasons.

Figure 2: Accumulated plant dry biomass (in g m^{-2}) between Time 0 and Time 1 on the different sites (CS1, CREA (Italy); CS2, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand (France); CS3, INRAE-Montpellier (France); CS4, AU (Denmark); CS5, INIA-CSIC (Spain); CS6, WUR (The Netherlands); CS7, LAMMC (Lithuania); CS8, TAGEM (Türkiye); CS9, CRAW (Belgium)) and treatments (T1 and T2 are different agroecological practices, control (T3) is a business-as-usual control). Coloured points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

Concerning the plant biomass accumulation (Figure 2), we can observe that it depends mainly on the site, being CS3 the one with highest values and CS2 and CS8 the ones with lowest values. Unsurprisingly, biomass was higher at the maximum demand period than at the minimum demand period. However, there are exceptions like CS7, or CS8. These are surely originated by the characteristics of the site. For instance, CS7 considered autumn as the maximum demand period and spring as the minimum demand period due to the characteristics of their main crop. In fact, in this site the business-as-usual treatment (control; T3) presented higher biomass accumulation values in the maximum demand period.

In general, the effects of the treatments were different among sites. For instance, in CS2 and CS6, the business and usual treatment (T3) is lower than the others, but in CS1 it presents the highest values. Moreover, we can appreciate how in some sites the effect of the treatment is different depending on the demand period. This is especially remarkable in the sites where no plant biomass was collected in the minimum demand period in the T3 plots (e.g. CS2, CS5, CS7). In CS8, T3 showed higher biomass accumulation in T2 and T3 during the minimum demand period than in T1, but this pattern disappeared in the maximum demand period, control (T3) seemed to have slightly lower values than T1 and T2.

Figure 3: Critical N content (in %) on the different sites (CS1, CREA (Italy); CS2, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand (France); CS3, INRAE-Montpellier (France); CS4, AU (Denmark); CS5, INIA-CSIC (Spain); CS6, WUR (The Netherlands); CS7, LAMMC (Lithuania); CS8, TAGEM (Türkiye); CS9, CRAW (Belgium)) and treatments (T1 and T2 are different agroecological practices, control (T3) is a business as usual control). Coloured points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

Focusing on the critical N content (Fig. 3), our results were consistent with the biomass data we used for the estimation. Hence, for the plots with high biomass, we obtained low critical N values, whereas for the plots with low biomass, we obtained high critical N values, except for the plots with no plant biomass, where the critical N was obviously 0.

Figure 4: Plant N demand (in g m^{-2}) on the different sites (CS1, CREA (Italy); CS2, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand (France); CS3, INRAE-Montpellier (France); CS4, AU (Denmark); CS5, INIA-CSIC (Spain); CS6, WUR (The Netherlands); CS7, LAMMC (Lithuania); CS8, TAGEM (Turkey); CS9, CRAW (Belgium)) and treatments (T1 and T2 are different agroecological practices, control (T3) is a business as usual control). Coloured points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

The combination of plant biomass and critical N in our equations allowed us to obtain an estimation of plant N demand (Fig. 4). This estimation allows a better comparison between sites than the raw biomass accumulation, as the range is always between 0 and 6 grams of N per m^2 . This is a noticeable achievement as the sites are different experiments with different sizes. For instance, CS1 was an agroecological crop, where each sample was taken from a parcel, and CS2 was a mesocosm experiment.

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Except CS8, all the business-as-usual plots (Control) showed higher plant nutrient demand in the maximum demand period than in the minimum demand period. This suggests the definition of maximum and minimum demand periods was accurate and consistent between sites. Note that CS8 (TAGEM; Türkiye) is a particular site for its climate and for the main crop (tomatoes). Besides, plant nutrient demand showed different responses to agroecological treatments depending on the site, for instance, during the high nutrient demand period, plant demand was lower in T1 and T2 than in Control in CS1, but this trend was reversed in CS6. This suggests that the different agroecological practices in the different sites had highly diverse effects at the plant and (probably) the soil level.

Plant N demand estimations were finished and put available for all the project members in the dataset. The definition of maximum and minimum demand periods was accurate and consistent.

Take-home message (task 5.1) - The differences in plant N demand showed between sites, demand period and agroecological treatments are a promising indicator of differences in other plant and soil variables, which would allow to perform a deep and detailed study of the synchrony between plant nutrient demand and ecosystem processes. Hence, plant N demand will be an interesting explanatory variable to test and try to explain the experimental variables measured in the different WP of AGROECOseqC.

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Task 5.2: Quantification of soil nitrogen supply and carbon use efficiency

This task is divided in 2 subtasks:

Task 5.2.1: Soil nitrogen fluxes as affected by plant demand, microbial functioning and agricultural practices

Task 5.2.2: Measurement of carbon use efficiency

Task 5.2.1: Soil nitrogen fluxes as affected by plant demand, microbial functioning and agricultural practices

The soil nitrogen supply is determined by two opposed soil nitrogen fluxes generated by soil microbes, the N mineralization and immobilization. These two fluxes are quantified using the ^{15}N pool dilution technique (Davidson et al., 1991; Recous et al., 1995; Mary et al., 1998).

Material and methods

Soil incubation: 100 g (dry weight basis) of fresh soil is sprayed with a solution (3 ml) composed of ^{15}N labelled NH_4Cl ($\delta^{15}\text{N} = 2500\text{‰}$) and KNO_3 . The solution is prepared to bring an equivalent of 30mg N- NH_4^+ kg^{-1} soil and 13.3mg N- NO_3^- kg^{-1} soil. The soil moisture is initially adjusted to reach a water potential of -100kPa after the addition of labelled N solution. Soil is mixed to homogenize the labelled solution in the soil. Two sets of incubated flasks are prepared from ^{15}N labelled soils. For each set, an aliquot of 30 g (dry weight basis) of soil is transferred in glass bottles (100 ml) closed with a rubber septum. A first set is sampled after for 2 hours (T+2h) and the second one after 26 hours of incubations (T+26h). Content and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of mineral N: Soil inorganic N content (N- NH_4^{++} and N- NO_3^-) is measured before and after the addition of labelled N at T0 and T1. Inorganic N content is extracted in tubes with KCl 2M (62.5 mL of solution in 25g of dried soil). Tubes are shaken during 30 minutes at 300 rpm and then centrifuged at 3000 rev min^{-1} for 5 min. Extracts are filtered (0.45 mm) and analyzed. For the ^{15}N measurements, NH_4^{++} and N- NO_3^- are separated by distillation with MgO and Dewarda's alloy. To this purpose, the excess of KCl extraction solution is transferred into closed bottle diffusion traps in the presence of either MgO or Dewarda's alloy and NH_4^{++} and N- NO_3^- are collected using acidified filter paper disks. Inorganic ^{15}N is measured using an isotope-ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS; EA; Carlo Erba, Rodana, Italy). Content and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of soil organic nitrogen: following the mineral N extraction with KCl, soils are washed with water to eliminate more than 99% of the residual KCl and mineral N. For the washing, the aliquot of 30 g of soil is shaken with 140 ml water for 30 seconds. The water is removed after centrifugation. The procedure is repeated 3 times. Soils are dried at 60°C for 24h and grounded. Organic N and its isotopic composition are determined using an isotope-ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS; EA; Carlo Erba, Rodana, Italy).

Soil N mineralization and immobilization potentials were calculated following the method of Davidson et al. (1991).

Calculations

Calculations were done following Davidson et al. (1991).

Nitrogen mineralization

We defined N mineralization (m) as:

$$m = \frac{(M_0 - M_1)}{t} \frac{\ln(H_0 M_1 / H_1 M_0)}{\ln(M_0 - M_1)}$$

Where:

M_0 = N content in NH_4^{++} (mg N kg^{-1} dry soil) after 2 hours of incubation.

M_1 = N content in NH_4^{++} (mg N kg^{-1} dry soil) after 26 hours of incubation.

H_0 = ^{15}N content (mg N kg^{-1} dry soil) after 2 hours of incubation.

H_1 = ^{15}N content (mg N kg^{-1} dry soil) after 26 hours of incubation.

m = mineralization rate in mg N kg^{-1} dry soil d^{-1}

t = time (24 hours).

Nitrogen immobilization

We defined N immobilization (i) as:

$$i = \frac{v_{t=1}}{\left(\frac{y_0}{x_0}\right) \frac{1 - e^{-k}}{k}}$$

where:

$v_{t=1}$ = ^{15}N excess of the organic pool (mg N kg^{-1} dry soil); that is

$$v_{t=1} = \frac{N_{t_1} + N_{t_2}}{2} (A_{t_2} - A_{t_1})$$

We used the mean of the organic N pools as it is not possible to use the difference because the values are highly variable.

y_0/x_0 is the initial enrichment of the NH_4^+ pool, that is

M_0/M_1 according to the mineralization equations.

k is the rate constant of exponential declining of the initial NH_4^+ pool.

$$k = -\ln \left(\frac{y_t x_0}{y_0 x_t} \right) / t$$

or

$$k = -\ln \left(\frac{H_1 M_0}{H_0 M_1} \right) / t$$

where:

i = immobilization rate in mg N kg⁻¹ dry soil d⁻¹

t = time (24 hours).

Results - We experienced some issues with the isotope-ratio mass spectrophotometer analysis, which are leading us into a delay in the obtention of results. We expect to finish de data table in few weeks. Despite these issues, we have obtained some results where we can observe some interesting patterns.

We obtained full results for four sites at the minimum demand period (CS1: CREA-Italy; CS4, AU (Denmark); CS6, WUR (The Netherlands)) and CS8, TAGEM (Turkey). To explore the data, we ordered these sites following the agroecological intensity gradient we established at the beginning of the project.

Fig. 5.2.1: AGROECOseqC site locations and agroecological intensification gradient.

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Figure 5.2.2: Soil N mineralization at the minimum plant nutrient demand period in 4 AGROECOseqC sites. These are ordered following a gradient of agroecological intensification according to their specific management practices. Colored points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

We observed a trend between sites in soil mineralization (Fig. 5.2.2). This seemed to increase across the agroecological intensity gradient. This suggests the increase of agroecological intensity is related with some increase in soil microbial activity.

Figure 5.2.3: Soil N immobilization at the minimum plant nutrient demand period in 4 AGROECOseqC sites. These are ordered following a gradient of agroecological intensification according to their specific management practices. Colored points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

This gradient was even more evident when we look at N immobilization (Fig. 2). In this case, we also can observe a within-site effect: the difference of the agroecological treatments (T1 and T2) with the business-as-usual practice (T3) also increased with the agroecological gradient between sites.

Figure 5.2.4: Difference between soil N mineralization and immobilization at the minimum plant nutrient demand period in 4 AGROECOseqC sites. These are ordered following a gradient of agroecological intensification according to their specific management practices. Colored points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively. Values above and below 0 indicate net N mineralization and immobilization, respectively.

When observing the difference between N mineralization and immobilization (Fig. 5.2.4), we can appreciate that:

- at the minimum demand period, immobilization prevails over mineralization. This is an unsurprising result, as we hypothesized that immobilization process mainly happens at the low demand period.
- We observed a lower difference between mineralization and immobilization in the T3 (business as usual) sites, and this difference increased with agroecological intensity, except for T1 in CS1.

Finally, Fig. 5.2.5 shows how, in the Denmark experiment, the differences between treatments seemed to be reduced or even disappeared during the maximum demand period. This was specially noted for N immobilization, which is coherent with our hypothesis that immobilization has its greatest importance during the low plant nutrient demand period.

Take-home message (task 5.2) - Despite we delay in results reception, the obtained data show highly interesting and promising patterns. Hence, when the database is complete, the measurements of N mineralization and immobilization will provide us valuable information of soil nutrient dynamics across plant nutrient demand periods and the diverse agroecological conditions studied in AGROECOseqC.

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Task 5.2.2: Measurement of carbon use efficiency

Carbon use efficiency (CUE) of microbes is the fraction of C taken up by microbial cells and retained in biomass as opposed to being respired (Domeingoz-Horta et al. 2020). In the AGROECOseqC project, we estimated the CUE of soil microbes by the O method (Spohn et al., 2016), that measures the O- incorporated to microbial DNA. This method has the advantage of being direct and subtract independent (Geyer et al., 2019).

Material and methods

For each soil sample, we prepared four 2 ml centrifuge tubes with the the equivalent of 0.25 g of dry soil. We used three of these replicates to be labelled with O- at 20 atom% enrichment at their matrix potential at -55 kPa. We added non molecular labelled water to reach the humidity at matrix potential at -55 kPa to the fourth replicate to use it as natural abundance control. After 24 hours incubation, we froze the samples with liquid nitrogen and stored them at -80 °C until DNA extraction. DNA was extracted with Qiagen PowerSoil kit. The quality of the extractions was evaluated by spectrophotometry with NanoDrop™ Lite Spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Wilmington, DE, USA), using A260/A280 and A260/A230 indicators. DNA concentration was measured by fluorometry with Qubit 4™ Fluorometer with dsDNA HS Assay Kit™ for Qubit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Wilmington, DE, USA).

For measuring the O content and the O signal of the DNA extraction, we used an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS). We prepared the samples by adding 35 µL of DNA extraction into a silver capsule, and after drying it with a vacuum concentrator, we added 200 µg of salmon DNA as spike, to ensure an O content higher than the detection limit of the IRMS, and we dried the sample again. Microbial biomass carbon content was determined using the chloroform fumigation extraction method (Vance et al. 1987).

To estimate the respiration activity of soil microbes, another set of four replicates of 15 g of fresh soil was incubated in flasks of 100 ml for 24 h at 15 °C. The flasks were flushed with CO₂-free air at the beginning of incubation. The CO₂ concentration in gas sample after incubation is determined by gas chromatography (Gas Chromatograph Clarus 480, PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA).

Calculations

We calculated DNA produced as

$$DNA_{prod} = Q_o \frac{100 \text{ at}\%_{total} - \text{at}\%_{nonlabel}}{31.2 \text{ at}\%_{label} - \text{at}\%_{nonlabel}}$$

Where Q_o is the mass of oxygen in the sample (μg), $\text{at}\%_{total}$ is the abundance of % of ^{18}O measured in the DNA extraction (%), $\text{at}\%_{nonlabel}$ is the abundance of % of ^{18}O in the non-labelled samples and $\text{at}\%_{label}$ is the ^{18}O abundance in the water of labelled samples, which is calculated as

$$\text{at}\%_{label} = \frac{\text{at}\%_{added} * A + 0.2 * W}{W + A}$$

where $\text{at}\%_{added}$ is the % of ^{18}O of the added water, A is the amount of labelled water (ml) and W the soil water content (ml). 0.2 is the natural % of ^{18}O in water.

Then, DNA turnover is defined as

$$DNA_{turnover} = \frac{DNA_{prod}}{DNA_{total}}$$

where DNA_{total} is the total soil DNA. Turnover is the microbial biomass turnover during incubation time. For example, a value of 0.2 indicates that the microbial biomass has increased 20% during incubation.

Then we can calculate Carbon growth ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1} \text{ DW h}^{-1}$) as

$$C_{growth} = \text{Microbial C} * \text{turnover} * t^{-1}$$

where Microbial C is the microbial Carbon content in μg .

Carbon respiration was calculated as

$$C_{resp} = \frac{[CO_2] p V_{hs} n}{(R T DW t)}$$

where $[CO_2]$ is the measured CO_2 concentration in ppm; p is the atmospheric pressure in kPa (101 kPa); V_{hs} is the air volume of the soil flask (0.6 L); n is the molecular mass of C (12.01 g); R is the ideal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ j mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$); T is the absolute room temperature (293 K); DW is the dry weight of soil (g) and t are the hours of incubation (24 hours).

Finally, we calculated CUE as:

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$$CUE = \frac{C_{growth}}{C_{growth} + C_{resp}}$$

Results

Microbial carbon growth and respiration, and Carbon Use Efficiency (CUE) were measured for all the sites planned (CS1, CS2, CS3, CS4, CS7) at both plant nutrient demand periods.

Figure 5.3.1: Microbial growth (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry soil h^{-1}) between on the different sites (CS1, CREA - Italy); CS2, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand (France); CS3, INRAE-Montpellier (France); CS4, AU (Denmark) and CS7 LAMMC (Lithuania) and treatments (T1 and T2 are different agroecological practices, T3 is a business as usual control). Colored points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

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Concerning the microbial carbon growth (Fig. 5.3.1), we can observe different patterns across plant nutrient demand period and treatment, depending on the site.

- In CS1, values were higher in the minimum demand period. Besides, we observed a decreasing pattern from T1 to T3, only in the high demand period.
- In CS2, the maximum values were observed at T2 at both periods. The case of CS2 is a singular one because T1 and T3 are two different controls: T1 is wheat alone (crop control) and T3 is rye grass and clover (grassland control).
- CS3 presented higher microbial carbon growth at maximum demand period in the T2 treatments.
- In contrast, CS4 showed lower microbial carbon growth rates during the maximum demand period.
- Finally, CS7 presented higher microbial growth values in T2. Additionally, values in T3 during the maximum demand period were higher than during the minimum demand period, in opposition to the other treatments. This is probably because at CS7 we considered autumn as the maximum demand period and spring as the minimum demand period due to the characteristics of their main crop. However, tillage was applied at T3 in the minimum demand period, in contrast with T1 and T2.

Concerning carbon respiration (Fig. 5.3.2), we observed the following patterns:

Figure 5.3.2: Carbon respiration (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry soil h^{-1}) on the different sites (CS1, CREA (Italy); CS2, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand (France); CS3, INRAE-Montpellier (France); CS4, AU (Denmark) and CS7, LAMMC (Lithuania)) and treatments (T1 and T2 are different agroecological practices, T3 is a business as usual control). Colored points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

- CS3 and CS7 showed lower carbon respiration rates at the business-as-usual treatment (T3). CS2 presented higher respiration values in the grassland control T3, the wheat control (T1) presented the lowest values and T2 (wheat and grassland) presented intermediate carbon respiration.
- CS4 presented clear differences in carbon respiration between the two plant demand periods. Additionally, during the maximum demand period T1 showed higher respiration rates than during the minimum demand period.
- In CS1, respiration seemed to be lower in T2.

The combination of microbial carbon growth and carbon respiration in our equations allowed us to obtain an estimation of carbon use efficiency (CUE, Figure 5.3.3.). The different characteristics of the sites and their agroecological treatments probably lead to the different patterns observed. For instance, CS4 was the only site with a clear contrast in CUE values between the two plant nutrient demand periods, whereas CS7 presented slight differences between treatments. Other sites (e.g. CS1, CS2) seemed to have differences in the plant demand period, based on the treatment.

Figure 5.3.3: Carbon use efficiency (CUE) in the different sites (CS1, CREA (Italy); CS2, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand (France); CS3, INRAE-Montpellier (France); CS4, AU (Denmark) and LAMMC (Lithuania) and treatments (T1 and T2 are different agroecological practices, T3 is a business-as-usual control). Colored points represent actual values whereas black points and lines represent the mean and the standard deviation, respectively.

Take-home message (task 5.2.1) - Soil microbial C growth, respiration and CUE presented different patterns across treatments in the different sites. Hence, they will be interesting variables to test hypotheses about the synchrony between plant nutrient demand and ecosystem processes in the frame of the AGROECOseqC project, as both response and explanatory variables.

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Task 5.3.1: Improvement of the method used to quantify the carbon use efficiency of soil microbes

For achieving this task, the Deliverable D.5.3.1 was uploaded to the project repository.

Take-home message (task 5.3.1): A manuscript about improvements over the ^{18}O method to quantify carbon use efficiency will be prepared in the next months. The main lines of this study will be the DNA extraction kit used, the replicability of the measurements, the need of the spike with salmon DNA when increasing the total oxygen content and a clarification of the equations used for the required calculations.

Task 5.3.2: Potential microbial C stabilization

Task 5.3.2 investigates the incorporation of rhizodeposited C into microbial biomarkers to estimate if plant diversification enhances potential microbial C stabilization.

Materials and methods

In three selected sites (CREA, AU, LAMMC) where $^{13}\text{C}\text{-CO}_2$ was conducted to estimate C rhizodeposition (e.g. in the MixRootC project) soil samples was collected to determine ^{13}C incorporation into biomarkers for living (PLFA) and dead (Amino sugar) microbial biomass. From this incorporation the potential microbial C stabilization is calculated as described in Peixoto et al. (2022).

Results

The amino sugar data are undergoing final quality checks, therefore presently PLFA results are presented.

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862695.

CS1 (Italy)

Different levels of agroecological intensification did not significantly affect the living microbial biomass (Figure 5.3.2.1A), where the business-as-usual treatment (BAU) exhibited the highest living microbial biomass compared to the two improved agroecological practices. Similarly, there was no significant effect of the different levels of agroecological intensification on the incorporation of ^{13}C into microbial PLFAs, with no clear trend between treatments (Figure 5.3.2.2A).

CS4 (Denmark)

Different levels of agroecological intensification did not have a significant effect on the living microbial biomass. However, there was a noticeable trend showing an overall increase in the living microbial biomass with increasing intensification (Figure 5.3.2.1B). Different levels of agroecological intensification had a significant effect on the incorporation of ^{13}C into microbial PLFAs (Figure 5.3.2.2B). In particular, Lp75N showed a significantly greater ^{13}C incorporation into microbial PLFAs compared to other levels of agroecological intensification.

CS7 (Lithuania)

Different levels of agroecological intensification significantly influenced the living microbial biomass, where both the no-tillage (NT) and no-tillage with cover crop (NT+CC) treatments had higher microbial biomass compared to the tilled control (Figure 5.3.2.1C). Conversely, different levels of agroecological intensification did not significantly affect the incorporation of ^{13}C into microbial PLFAs (Figure 5.3.2.2C). However, consistent with the trend observed in living microbial biomass, there was an increase in ^{13}C incorporation from the tilled treatment (T) to no-tillage (NT), followed by a decrease in the no-tillage with cover crop (NT+CC) treatment.

Figure 5.3.2.1. PLFA content ($\mu\text{g PLFA g}^{-1}$ soil) between different levels of agroecological intensification for CS1 (CREA, A), CS4 (AU, B), and CS7 (LAMMC, C). Orange represents the control treatment; light green represents the first improved agroecological practice; dark green represents the second improved agroecological practice. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean ($n = 4$).

Figure 5.3.2.2. ¹³C into microbial PLFAs (µg ¹³C PLFA g⁻¹ soil) between different levels of agroecological intensification for CREA (A), AU (B), and LAMMC (C). Orange represents the control treatment; light green represents the first improved agroecological practice; dark green represents the second improved agroecological practice. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean (n = 4).

Take-home message (task 5.3.2) - A manuscript about potential microbial C stabilization is being prepared. The PLFA data show that at two sites the agroecological intensification treatments results in more recent C incorporated into the living microbial biomass, whereas at the organically managed site, the organic farm management as business-as-usual is so optimal that it does not allow further C-incorporation.

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WP6 - Soil C retainment through stable aggregates and microbial biomass activity – CREA,
LAMMC

Task 6.1 - Physical stabilization of organic soil C pools and aggregate stability

Soil C pools and aggregate stability (LAMMC)

Objective

The aim of this study was to assess the effect of the agroecological intensification, introduced in different EU agricultural cropping systems, on soil carbon (C) pool and aggregate stability. We hypothesized that the reduction of soil disturbance and the increased plant diversity in field may improve soil C retainment and soil aggregate stability.

Soil sampling and methodology

The following parameters were measured under diversified agroecological practices across different environmental conditions: water stable aggregates (WSA, %) within 0.25-1 mm soil aggregates, soil organic carbon (SOC, %) in bulk soil and in different soil aggregates (fine: 0.25-1 mm and coarse: 1.0-2.0 mm), water extractable organic carbon (WEOC, g kg⁻¹) in bulk soil and in different soil aggregates (fine: 0.25-1 mm and coarse: 1.0-2.0 mm).

Sampling was carried out at plant growth, when soil functions as “C source” (MAX nutrient plant demand). Soil samples from CS1, CS2, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 were received for this analysis. Soil samples were collected from four blocks in three treatments: T1 - 1st agroecological intensification level, T2 - 2nd agroecological intensification level and T3 - control. Undisturbed soil samples (0-20 cm in depth) were taken for the aggregate stability analysis, following the protocol reported in AGROECOseqC handbook (see: Chapter “Schemes for soil/biomass/root sampling”, pp.14-16; Chapter “Soil C retainment through stable aggregates and microbial biomass activity, pp. 561-65). Dry sieving was performed by Retch sieve shaker: mesh sizes 8.0, 5.6, 4.0, 2.0, 1.0, 0.5, and 0.25 mm and soil aggregates of 0.25-1 mm and 1.0-2.0 mm were subjected to SOC and WEOC analysis. Aggregates from 1 mm sieve were wet sieved by Eijkelkamp apparatus. Bulk soil samples for the SOC and WEOC analysis were sieved through a 2 mm sieve. The content of SOC was

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determined according to the Nikitin-modified Tyurin method, WEOC - by the IR detection method after UV-catalyzed persulphate oxidation.

The observed data were statistically processed using R Studio 4.3.2 software. The assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance were assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test and Levene's test, respectively. Data were analyzed using ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc tests or Dunn's tests.

Results

The percentage of WSA varied across the experimental sites and treatments ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 6.1.1). The data distribution between sites was closely related to the European-scale gradient of agroecological intensification. The lowest WSA was determined at site CS5 (Spain), while higher WSA values were observed at sites CS2 (France), CS4 (Denmark), and CS1 (Italy) respectively. Significant differences among treatments were found at sites CS7 (Lithuania), CS9 (Belgium) with the lowest WSA in the control group. In contrast, WSA at the CS1 (Italy, organically managed system) site was greater during the control treatment compared to T1 and T2.

Figure 6.1.1. Water stable aggregates (%) within 0.25-1.0 mm soil fractions, under diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions in tested sites. The sites are arranged according to European-scale gradients of ecological intensification (Figure 5.2.1).

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862695.

The mean soil SOC stock differed among sites at all analyzed fractions (Fig.6.1.2), following the decreasing order concerning SOC in bulk soil (CS2 France > CS1 Italy > CS Denmark); SOC in > 1.0 - 2.0 mm soil fractions (CS6 Netherlands > CS7 Lithuania > CS2 France); SOC in 0.25 - 1.0 mm soil fractions (CS2 France > CS1 Italy > CS8 Türkiye). With respect to SOC in the bulk soil, significant differences were found in CS9 and CS1 treatments, with T1 treatments significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from T3 and T2 treatments in the two core sites, respectively. Furthermore, CS9 was statistically different ($p < 0.05$) among the treatments when the two SOC fractions (1.0 - 2.0 mm; 0.25 - 1.0 mm) were considered.

Figure 6.1.2. Soil organic carbon (SOC, %) a) in bulk soil, b) fine (0.25 - 1.0 mm) and c) coarse (1.0-2.0 mm) macroaggregates, under diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at experimental sites. The sites are arranged according to European-scale gradients of ecological intensification (Figure 5.2.1).

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The WEOC in the bulk soil and soil aggregates (0.25-1.0 mm; 1.0-2.0 mm) showed variation across the site scale of ecological intensification (Fig. 6.1.3), highlighting the dynamics of labile soil carbon and the spatial variability of these properties. This variation underscores the instability, or lability, of soil WEOC.

The average WEOC content in the bulk soil was highest in CS2 (France) - 0.3 g kg⁻¹ and CS1 (Italy) - 0.3 g kg⁻¹, with the lowest WEOC values in CS4 (Denmark) and CS8 (Turkey). WEOC in bulk soil significantly differed among the treatments at sites CS2, CS7, and CS9. For CS2, T1 differed from T3 (control), while in CS7, T2 differed from T1. In fine (0.25-1.0 mm) and coarse macro-aggregates (1.0-2.0mm) revealed similar trends, except the higher WEOC average values found in CS4 and CS8. Only CS2 showed a difference in fine and coarse macro-aggregates when considering the effects of agricultural practices among the treatments, with T1 significantly higher compared to T3. Furthermore, the WEOC fractions offered similar trends of lower levels in the organic matter pool in CS7, CS9, and CS6.

Figure 6.1.3. The Water - extractable organic carbon (WEOC), g kg⁻¹ in a) bulk soil, b) fine (0.25-1.0 mm), and c) coarse (1.0-2.0mm) macroaggregates, under diversified agroecological practices and different environmental conditions at experimental sites. The sites are arranged according to European-scale gradients of ecological intensification (Figure 5.2.1).

Pearson's correlation analysis showed a positive correlation between the WSA, and all C pool sources tested (SMB-C, C-stock in bulk soil, SOC, and WEOC in 0.25–1.0 mm and >1.0 mm soil aggregates). C-stock in bulk soil positively correlated with SMB-C, SOC in bulk soil, and SOC in >1.0 mm and WEOC in bulk soil, 0.25–1.0 mm, and >1.0 mm soil aggregates, respectively. Soil microbial biomass carbon also correlated with SOC in bulk soil and fractions and WEOC in bulk soil. SOC in >1.0 mm soil aggregates showed a correlation with SOC in bulk soil and 0.25–1.0 mm soil aggregates, and WEOC in bulk soil. WEOC in >1.0 mm soil aggregates correlated with WSA, C-stock in bulk soil, SOC in bulk soil, and in the 0.25–1.0 mm soil aggregates of WEOC and SOC.

Take-home message (task 6.1.1) - This study emphasizes the complex relationship between soil structure, microbial biomass, and carbon cycling across diverse environmental conditions and agricultural practices. The strong correlations observed among SMBC, WEOC, SOC, and WSA highlight the pivotal role of soil organic matter stability in regulating soil carbon processes. Integrated agricultural management strategies are essential for improving soil carbon dynamics in response to these findings.

Semi-quantitative C content in fine and coarse macro-aggregates by SEM-EDS (CREA).

Objective

Different soil aggregate fractions are dominated by different microbial consortia. It was found that microbial PLFAs are higher in 0.25-1.00 mm aggregates (fine macroaggregates), mainly dominated by fungi community (Fray, 2005; Wang et al, 2017).

The objectives of this work were:

- to verify if the agroecological intensification affected the soil aggregate composition (in terms of soil aggregate diameters) and C% relative abundance in soil aggregates by using SEM-EDS technique.
- to compare results obtained by applying SEM-EDS instrumental analysis with those collected by LAMMC using consolidated methodologies.

Sampling and methodology

In core-sites CS1, CS2, CS3, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7, CS8, CS9, the effect of applied agroecological practices, based on reduced soil disturbance (no tillage) and higher plant diversity in field (cover crop, crop rotation), were evaluated for soil aggregates size (e.g., diameter, in μm) and semi-quantitative analysis of Carbon (%), as mediated by root mycorrhization.

From 2023 to April 2024, undisturbed soil samples were sent to CREA-AA from the core-sites and then analyzed using SEM EVO MA10 Zeiss coupled with X-ray Electron Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). Database generated from the analysis are reported into AGROECOseqC overall dataset (Experiment A). Per each SEM image, ~20 records (on average, depending on number of aggregates per SEM image) were performed (Fig. 6.1.4).

Figure 6.1.4. Determination of soil aggregate diameter (mm) and C relative abundance on aggregates' surface (%) using SEM-EDS. Here, a soil sample from CS7 (LAMMC) was observed.

The obtained database is related to soil aggregate diameter (in μm) and semi-quantitative C content in soil aggregate, expressed as relative abundance, given as 100% the total absorbance of all the elements of periodic table. The C% data are not absolute values, while reflecting the amount of Carbon [^{12}C] detected on soil aggregate surface. In each experimental site under T1, T2 and T3, the recorded soil aggregate diameters were grouped to form three sub-classes of soil aggregates, given as 100% their sum:

- microaggregates ($\varnothing < 250\mu\text{m}$)
- fine macroaggregates ($\varnothing = 250 \mu\text{m} - 1.0 \text{ mm}$)
- coarse macroaggregates ($1.0 \text{ mm} < \varnothing < 2.0 \text{ mm}$)

This analysis allows to associate to each aggregate observed by SEM the related C% relative abundance.

Results

Firstly, we comment the results obtained in Experiment B on CS1, CS5 and CS7 core-sites, where the following practices were tested: the aim was to verify the effect of reduced soil disturbance (no tillage) and increase of plant diversity (cover crop or crop rotation) on soil aggregates sizes and related organic C content, mediated by root mycorrhization.

Despite the different soil texture in CS1, CS5 and CS7 experimental sites, the agricultural practices affected the distribution of soil fine ($250\ \mu\text{m} < \varnothing < 1.0\ \text{mm}$) and coarse ($1.0\ \text{mm} < \varnothing < 2.0\ \text{mm}$) macroaggregates.

In apricot orchard, where soil was sampled in the trees interrow (CS1), the highest percentage of soil fine macroaggregates was recorded in no-tilled system under spontaneous cover (T1), and in CS5 in no-tilled wheat cropping system (T1), where soil microaggregates ($< 250\ \mu\text{m}$) in tilled plots were 100% (CS5-T3). In CS1, under T2 treatment, the tillage followed by cover crop introduction gave the highest percentage of fine macroaggregates and microaggregates. Contrastingly in CS7, where no tillage and cover crops were applied in oilseed rape cropping cycle, the highest percentage of soil fine macroaggregate were found in tilled plots (T3-control), while no-tillage under cover crop gave the highest percentage of soil microaggregates (T2).

An overall decreasing trend of soil microaggregates in favour of $250\ \mu\text{m}$ - $1.0\ \text{mm}$ fine macroaggregates was observed under no-till and crop diversification. This finding was also supported by microscopic analysis, which evidenced how the absence of tillage in CS1-T1, CS5-T1-T2 and CS7-T1-T2 maintained intact the root mycorrhizal extra-hyphal mycelium (Task 2.2). In fact, it was found that average diameter of soil aggregates was positively correlated to plant mycorrhizal colonization intensity ($r = 0.6106$).

Considering all the experimental sites (Experiment A), the distribution of aggregate diameters in function of the T1, T2, and T3 treatments are reported in Figure 6.1.5.

Figure 6.1.5. Soil aggregate diameters (in mm) distribution in T1, T2, and T3 treatments recorded in CS1, CS2, CS3, CS4, CS5, CS7, CS9.

As expected, aggregates distribution in size classes differed among the core sites in function of soil texture and applied treatments. In CS1-T3 (control) an increase of aggregate class with diameter > 1.0 mm was observed, while in CS5-T3 (control) aggregates shifted towards microaggregates, compared to T1 and T2 treatments (where fine macroaggregates were well represented). In CS4, microaggregates were predominant in T1, T2 and T3.

Going to C% detected in soil aggregates by EDS, significant differences were found only in CS2 (France – CF): the highest values were recorded under T1 and T2 (differently mixed grasses, compared to sole wheat – T3, control), confirming the effectiveness of the agroecological practice's introduction on promoting soil C accumulation in soil aggregate surface in this experimental site (Figure 6.1.6.).

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Figure 6.1.6. C% obtained by SEM-EDS in CS2 under T1, T2 and T3. Different letters mean significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

A similar trend was observed in CS1 also, although not statistically significant.

Considering all the studied systems, the aggregate diameters were positively correlated to the corresponding C% (linear correlation: 0.5952), showing how SEM technique allows to put in relation the measured C% relative abundance and the diameter of each observed aggregate (as shown in Figure 6.1.4). Finally, C% was positively and strongly correlated to the C-stock in fine macroaggregates indicator (r_s : 0.86979 - Task 6.1.1), testifying the good performance of this new instrumental approach, compared to consolidated methodology.

In Figure 6.1.7, PCA analysis shows clearly the correlation found in the experimental sites (under different pedo-climate conditions), among aggregate diameters (mm), C% and P% relative abundances in soil aggregates and mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%).

Figure 6.1.7. Principal components analysis (PCA) biplot and confidence polygons ellipses ordering the AGROECOseqC experimental sites related to soil aggregate diameters, C%, P%, and M%.

The first component explains 40.2% of the parameters' variance in the experimental sites, while the second component counted 23.3%, for 63.5% of a total explained variance. Overall, PCA does not separate all the experimental sites, although the first component separated CS4 (DK) from CS1 (IT), CS5 (ES) and CS9 (BE). Along with the positive value of component 1, CS2, CS3 and CS4 are associated to C% and P% in soil aggregates, while CS1 and CS9 site to M% and aggregates diameters. This result confirms the hypothesis that a high mycorrhizal fungi colonization, as in CS1 and CS9, may favor the increase of soil aggregates size, while a high plant diversity, as in CS2, CS3 and CS4, promotes the C and P accumulation in soil aggregates.

Take-home message (task 6.1.2) - No-tillage not only increased plant root mycorrhization in field (WP2- Task 2.2) but also the percentage of soil fine macroaggregates ($\varnothing = 250 \text{ mm} \div 1.0 \text{ mm}$). We argue that this correlation may be due by the development of mycorrhizal extra-hyphal mycelium, able to increase the soil particles adhesion, although these results are site dependent. The found linear relationship between the soil aggregate diameter and C% relative abundance in the same aggregates shows how soil disturbance can cause a decrease of SOC. Anyway, each agroecosystem behaves differently and requires the introduction of "tailored" approaches to obtain a measurable result over time.

Task 6.2. Microbial C-respiration dynamic and mitigation of greenhouse gas emission -
Leader: CREA, Co-leader: AU

CO₂ emissions during stationary phase of soil microbial biomass

Objective

The objective of this task was to assess the effect of considered management practices in AGROECOseqC on soil CO₂ emissions during the stationary phase of soil microbiota, corresponding to the soil basal respiration rate. The soil respiration tests were performed on soil collected at two moment of plant demand (MAX and MIN), with the aim to measure the microbial activity (soil basal respiration):

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- at the moment of minimum competition between plants and soil microbiota (MIN);
- at the moment of maximum competition for water and nutrient resources between plants and soil microbiota (MAX).

Soil sampling and methodology

A total of n. 300 soil samples (Experiment A and Experiment B), collected from the nine core sites (CS1-IT, CS2-FR₁, CS3-FR₂, CS4-DK, CS5-ES, CS6-NL, CS7-LT, CS8 -TK and CS9-BE) identified at the beginning of the project, were processed.

In each core-site, 100 g of each soil samples were collected in field in two moments: at minimum plant demand (MIN) and at maximum plant demand (MAX), as described in the AGROECOseqC Handbook. In Experiment A, T1 and T2 treatments, at increasing level of agroecological intensification (T₂>T₁), were compared to T3 as control treatment (no agroecological intensification, or business as usual). Per each treatment, in each of the four blocks, four elementary samples were collected to form one composite one (3 treatments x 4 blocks = 12 composite samples/core-site).

In Experiment B, T1 and T2 treatments, at increasing level of agroecological intensification (T₂>T₁), were compared. Per each treatment, in three blocks only, three elementary samples were collected and maintained separated to consider soil spatial effect (2 treatments x 3 blocks x 3 replicates/blocks = 18 samples/core-site). All the soil samples were sent to CREA-VE by each partner between September 2022 and October 2023 by refrigerated shipment and stored at -20 °C until processing, following the protocols defined in the AGROECOseqC Handbook.

Sample processing started June 2023 and terminated in June 2024.

The CO₂ emissions were quantified as following: the received frozen soil samples were first put in refrigerator a 4 °C for two days to allow them to thaw slowly and sieved at 2 mm and checked for water content determination. Then they were conditioned at 40% of water holding capacity (WHC) and left for two days at room temperature (25 °C), to monitor the CO₂ efflux rates on time without altering microclimate inside the measurement chamber.

50 grams of soil (dry basis) were put in small polypropylene mesh (100 mm) bags (Figure 1) which, in turn, were allocated in boxes and put in thermostat at 25 °C at 100% relative humidity for preventing desiccation (soil incubation).

Figure 1. Soil sample in 100 mm-polypropylene mesh bags.

The measurement of CO₂ emission started 2 days after incubation at 25 °C and performed every three days. After 8-11 days from the incubation start, a constant emission rate was reached, and basal respiration was therefore quantified (in $\mu\text{g C g}_{\text{soil}}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$).

The device used for AGROECOseqC measurements is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Device used by CREA-VE to measure CO₂ emission from soil samples.

Each sample to be measured was taken from thermostat and equilibrated at 380 ppm/vol CO₂ for 10 minutes, then put in measurement chamber and emission rate recorded for 10 minutes. A typical emission curve is reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example of dynamic curve of CO₂ concentration evolved from soil sample in 1 hour (in ppm).

The CO₂ emission rate (as soil basal respiration rate) was calculated, according to Delle Vedove et al. (2007). This measurement allows to evaluate the soil microbial basal respiration after reaching the stationary state, thus giving an indication of the soil attitude to fast or slowly mineralize organic substrates in soil, as affected by agroecological management practices (T1 and T2), compared to T3 (control).

Results and discussion

When all the analysis were completed, the final dataset for soil basal respiration (CO₂ emission rate, in $\mu\text{g C g}_{\text{soil}}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) was submitted for following data analysis (M6.2.1). A first, preliminary descriptive evaluation is reported in Figure 4. Per each core-sites, the histograms represent the CO₂ emission rate in function of the applied agronomic practices T1, T2 and T3-control), recorded at the minimum and maximum demand of nutrients by the plant species (crops/cover crops/prairie) coexisting in each studied agroecosystem.

Figure 4. CO₂ emission rate (in $\mu\text{g C g}_{\text{soil}}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) registered in all the core-sites, as affected by the agroecological treatments (T1 and T2), compared to control (T3). Soil samples were collected at nutrient minimum plant demand (MIN, in grey) and maximum plant demand (MAX, in green). Different letters represent significant differences (Tukey HSD test for mean comparison). Statistical difference at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results shows a significant difference of CO₂ emission rate in all the core-sites, except in CS4 (DK) and CS6 (NL). In CS1, the highest rate of soil respiration was recorded at MIN-T2 samples (fallow, before CC sowing) and the lowest one at MAX-T2, when CC were introduced. In CS2, as expected the CO₂ emission rate was higher at MAX sampling, while the minimum recorded value was at MIN-T2, where plant diversity was the highest one among T1, T2 and T3. In CS3, the soil respiration rate decreases significantly in T2, both at MIN and MAX, probably due to the soil no tillage, compared to tillage in T3 (tilled control). No effects were observed in CS4 and CS6, while in CS5 the lowest CO₂ emission rate was in T1 and T3 at MIN plant demand: here, the introduction of vetch and barley in the wheat rotation apparently increased the SOM mineralization compared to the wheat monocropping, regardless the soil no tillage vs minimum tillage factor. In CS7 and CS8, the sampling moment made the difference, being highest the soil respiration rate at MIN plant demand, corresponding to the fallow (before sowing), regardless the tested agroecological practices. In CS9, at MIN plant demand the lowest CO₂ emission rate was found in T1, where cover crops were not introduced in field and farmyard manure was applied.

Take-home message - The introduced agronomic practices played a role on affecting soil basal respiration rate (as CO₂ emission) in function of the sampling moment. We underline the system diversity (plant species in field with associated soil microbiota) and the applied agronomic practices to make the difference in recorded results, giving sometimes opposite trends when comparing the considered AGROECOseqC experimental sites. Pedoclimate conditions and alternative managements practices applied along the EU agroecological intensification gradient fully justify these results.

JUSTIFICATION - Although a delay in completing it, on the end of August 2024 the D6.2.1 was concluded, whilst D6.2.2 did not, due instrumental problems: in particular, this issue emerged after the unavailability of the old respirometer at CREA VE, needed for performing the planned analysis. A new respirometric system was necessary, but the AGROECOseqC budget was not planned to cover this new acquisition. CREA-VE charged completely the costs for analysis using an IRGA system (Infrared Gas Analyzer), following method described by Delle Vedove et al. (2007). Some unforeseen problems during the new setup delayed the onset of respiration tests.

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In addition, the high number of samples of core sites to be processed in AGROECOseqC and the overlap with other laboratory EJP Soil activities, further delayed the completion. However, the analysis of the CO₂ emission during stationary phase was completed and a dataset, required for the interpretation of soil C emissions rate in sampled soils, was made available to allow their proper statistical evaluation.

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WP7 - Multivariate analysis and modelling soil organic matter dynamics – INRAE, WR, CREA
Sub-task 7.1.2 Integration of EU functional plants, soil microbial and faunal parameters with soil properties by MVA^[1] - CREA

Introduction

Plant and soil biodiversity are vital for maintaining soil health and ensuring ecosystem stability. The interactions between plant and soil biodiversity regulate key processes that support a range of ecosystem services. In recent decades, the study of functional biodiversity has emerged as a valuable approach to analyze, monitor, and enhance the role of soil organisms and plant communities in providing these services. However, the mechanisms driving these interactions, and the ways in which farmers can manage biodiversity to balance both environmental sustainability and agricultural productivity, remain poorly understood.

In the AGROECOseqC project, we collected data on plant and microbial biodiversity to investigate their effects on soil organic carbon (SOC) dynamics across various European locations. We also assessed the impact of different farming practices on functional diversity related to SOC. This research aims to address the following key questions:

1. Is functional diversity relevant in explaining the variance of soil carbon in agricultural fields?
2. Given the complexity of the functional microbial groups and plants' traits, how do they interact in the context of SOC dynamics?
3. Do farming practices affect the plants and microbial functional groups?
4. What is the impact of farming practices on the plant and microbial functional groups that are relevant for SOC dynamics?

Material and methods

The study was carried out in eight experimental sites located in Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Belgium, France, Denmark and Türkiye. The locations covered a wide range of European pedoclimatic areas and different degree of agroecological intensification ranging from cereal monocropping to organic fruit systems. All experiments were carried out in randomized complete block designs with four blocks. In Belgium, Denmark, Türkiye, France 1 and France 2 we collected one sample per block in each treatment (n=12 for all core sites, but France 2 where 8 samples were collected).

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862695.

In Italy, Spain, and Lithuania we collected three sample per block in two treatments (INC, ICC in Italy; NT, NTR in Spain; NT, NT+CC in Lithuania) in order to compile an additional dataset (n=18 per core site) to test more robustly the effect of farming practices on specific plant traits and functional groups.

We conducted a phytosociological survey of plant communities and performed Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) analysis on microbial communities (see WP4). Using these data, we examined the functional diversity of these communities, selecting traits associated with soil carbon dynamics. For plant communities, the functional traits studied included crop height (CH), specific leaf area (SLA), percentage of perennial species (PER), percentage of grass species (GRASS), support for arbuscular mycorrhiza (SAM), and percentage of taproot species (TAPROOT). In terms of microbial communities, we categorized functional groups based on their roles related to:

- C degradation bacteria: cellulolysis, chitinolysis, fermentation;
- Recalcitrant C degradation bacteria: xylanolysis, aromatic compound degradation, hydrocarbon degradation;
- C fixation bacteria: photosynthetic_cyanobacteria, nonphotosyntheticcyanobacteria;
- Mycorrhizal fungi: arbuscular_mycorrhizal, ectomycorrhizal;
- Saprotroph fungi: dung_saprotroph, litter_saprotroph, unspecified_saprotroph, wood_saprotroph.

Milestone M7.1.2.1 was completed at M50.

Statistical analysis

We applied redundancy analysis (RDA) to identify which microbial functional groups and plant functional traits were most strongly associated with soil organic carbon (SOC) and water-extractable organic carbon (WEOC), and to visualize the relationships between these variables. Prior to analysis, the data were standardized. The significance of RDA axes and all the functional traits and groups were tested through permutation test. The adjusted R² was calculated to obtain the variance explained by the RDA (*vegan*, package).

We employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) to explore the causal relationships between plant functional traits, fungal and bacterial functional groups, and their mediation of SOC dynamics. Specifically, we tested the following three hypotheses: (i) plant functional traits have a direct effect on SOC, (ii) fungi functional groups have a direct effect on SOC, (iii) bacteria functional groups have a direct effect on SOC (iv) plant functional traits influence microbial groups related to SOC. All plant and microbial data were incorporated as factors to construct the model. To address multicollinearity, we calculated the variance inflation factor (VIF) and performed a stepwise exclusion of factors starting with those having VIF values greater than 5. Subsequently, we screened the model for indicator weights, excluding factors with non-significant weights and non-significant loadings below 0.5 (Hair et al., 2017). VIF, variable selection and bootstrapping were carried out with SmartPLS4.0 while we use the *semnr* package in R to plot the model.

We also evaluated the selective effect of farming practices on all microbial and plant functional traits at the Italian, Lithuanian and Spanish sites using Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) (*vegan* package). The stress values of the NMDS ordination were assessed, and non-significant dispersion was tested. Additionally, to assess the significance of the farming treatments, we used PERMANOVA with core sites treated as “strata” to account for site-specific effects (*vegan* package). We further examined how farming practices influenced the functional traits and microbial groups identified in the PLS-SEM analysis. For each functional trait or group, we fitted both linear models (LMs) and generalized linear models (GLMs) using farming treatment and block as factors, with and without interaction terms. Beta regression was also tested for the perennial crop trait. Data concerning non photosynthetic cyanobacteria and arbuscular mycorrhiza in the Lithuanian site and dung saprotroph in the Spanish site, were square root transformed before the analysis. We selected the model with the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). Anova type II was used to assess models without interactions, while type III Anova was employed for models with interactions. To test for normality of residuals in linear models, we applied the Shapiro-Wilk test, while residual diagnostics for generalized linear models were evaluated using the *DHARMA* package. Pairwise comparisons of treatments were conducted using the Tukey HSD test (*emmeans* package), with a significance threshold of 0.05.

All statistical analyses, unless otherwise mentioned, were conducted in R.

Results

Is functional diversity relevant in explaining the variance of soil carbon in agricultural fields?

The RDA revealed that functional diversity accounted for about 60% of the total variance (Adjusted $r^2 = 58.1\%$), and the overall model was statistically significant ($p \leq 0.001$). Table 7.1 presents the results of the ANOVA permutation test for the included factors while Figure 7.1 offers a graphic representation of the RDA. The RDA revealed that functional diversity accounted for about 60% of the total variance (Adjusted $r^2 = 58.1\%$), and the overall model was statistically significant ($p \leq 0.001$). Significant plants functional traits influencing SOC and WEOC included GRASS, SLA ($p \leq 0.001$) and PER ($p \leq 0.01$). Concerning microbial groups, Figure 1 suggested also that arbuscular mycorrhiza ($p \leq 0.01$), dung saprotroph ($p \leq 0.01$), litter saprotroph ($p \leq 0.001$), hydrocarbon degradation bacteria ($p \leq 0.01$) and fermentation bacteria ($p \leq 0.001$) had a significant negative relationship with SOC.

Table 7.1 Significant test of factors affecting SOC and WEOC in the redundancy analysis

Functional Trait/Group	Df	Variance	F	Pr(>F)	Significance
CH	1	0,000984	0,4137	0,52	ns
GRASS	1	0,054938	230.883	0,001	***
SLA	1	0,047788	200.832	0,001	***
PER	1	0,082021	344.701	0,001	***
arbuscular_mycorrhizal	1	0,017059	71.694	0,01	**
dung_saprotroph	1	0,023786	99.964	0,002	**
ectomycorrhizal	1	0,000386	0,1624	0,762	ns
litter_saprotroph	1	0,080239	337.211	0,001	***
unspecified_saprotroph	1	0,001676	0,7042	0,438	ns
wood_saprotroph	1	0,001825	0,7669	0,368	ns
chitinolysis	1	0,000571	0,2401	0,626	ns
cellulolysis	1	0,000799	0,3357	0,575	ns
xylanolysis	1	0,001734	0,7287	0,404	ns
fermentation	1	0,051008	214.368	0,001	***
photosynthetic_cyanobacteria	1	0,008774	36.872	0,059	ns
nonphotosynthetic_cyanobacteria	1	0,0002	0,0842	0,781	ns
hydrocarbon_degradation	1	0,020006	84.078	0,004	**

Figure 7.1 Redundancy analysis of the AGROECOseqC dataset (n=108).

Given the complexity of the functional microbial groups and plants' traits, how do they interact in the context of SOC dynamics?

The results of the PLS-SEM are presented in Figure 7.2. The construct representing plant functional traits was significantly constituted by the SLA trait, the presence of Grass-like and perennial species ($p \leq 0.001$). The plant community showed a negative significant effect ($p \leq 0.001$) on both fungal and bacterial functional groups while its contribution to SOC, despite positive, was not significant. The fungal functional group construct was defined by litter saprotroph ($p \leq 0.001$), arbuscular mycorrhiza ($p \leq 0.01$) and dung saprotroph ($p \leq 0.001$). Those groups had a significant negative effect ($p \leq 0.01$)

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on SOC. In the bacterial functional construct, fermentation ($p \leq 0.001$) and non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria ($p \leq 0.01$) were the two significant determinants. The bacterial functional groups showed a stronger significant negative effect ($p \leq 0.001$) on SOC than fungi ($p \leq 0.01$). Overall, the model explained 50% of the SOC variability (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.503$).

Figure 7.2 PLS-SEM of the dataset AGROECOseqC on functional diversity ($n=108$).

Do farming practices affect the plants and microbial functional groups?

The NMDS analysis of plant traits and microbial functional groups demonstrated that farming practices had a significant impact on plant and microbial functional traits especially in Italy (Figure 7.3). Results of the PERMANOVA (Table 7.3) clearly showed that treatment ($p \leq 0.001$) had a significant effect on plants traits and microbial functional groups related to soil C, independently of the experimental site.

Figure 7.3 NMDS on the effect of farming practices on plant and microbial functional traits associated with SOC. CS1= Italy; CS5= Spain, CS7=Lithuania. T1 refers to INC, NT, NT In Italy, Spain and Lithuania, respectively. T2 refers to ICC, NTR, NT+C in Italy, Spain and Lithuania, respectively. Stress=0.13.

Table 7.3 Results of Permanova analysis. Data were stratified by experimental site

	Df	Sum of square	R2	F	Pr(>F)
Treatment	1	0,0611	0,0458	2,4992	***
Residual	52	1,2706	0,9541		

What is the impact of farming practices on the plant and microbial functional groups that are relevant for SOC dynamics?

Table 4 shows the results of the regression models used to analyse plant traits and microbial functional groups which significantly formed the construct of the PLS-SEM (Figure 7.2). Treatments had a strong effect on plant traits only in the Italian site (Table 7.4). Both perennials and SLA ($p \leq 0.001$) were higher under INC (Table 7.5). Perennials were almost 7 times higher under INC (Perennials = $57.7 \pm 4.4\%$) compared to ICC (Perennials = $7.3 \pm 2.1\%$), while a lower difference

between the treatments was observed for SLA (Table 7.5). No perennial plants were found in the Spanish experimental sites. Treatment did not affect Grass-like species in the experimental sites under study.

Table 7.4 Results from the Analysis of variance for the plant, bacteria and fungi functional groups which resulted significant in the PLS-SEM model (n=18 per each site)

	Functional trait/group	Treatment	Block	Treatment x Block	Model distribution
Italy	Perennials	***	ns	-	Betaregression
	Specific Leaf Area	***	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	Betaregression
	Fermentation	***	ns	-	Gamma Log
	NP Cyanobacteria	***	ns	**	Normal
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	ns	*	*	Normal
	Dung Saprotroph	**	***	*	Gamma Log
Spain	Perennials	-	-	-	-
	Specific Leaf Area	ns	ns	ns	Normal
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	Betaregression
	Fermentation	ns	ns	*	Normal
	NP Cyanobacteria	**	ns	-	Normal
	Litter Saprotroph	**	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	***	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Dung Saprotroph	***	ns	-	Normal
Lithuani a	Perennials	ns	ns	-	Betaregression
	Specific Leaf Area	ns	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	Normal
	Fermentation	ns	***	***	Gamma Log
	NP Cyanobacteria	ns	*	**	Normal
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	Normal
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	*	*	*	Normal
	Dung Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	Gamma Log

All the bacterial functional groups were significantly affected by the management practices in Lithuania and Italy (Table 7.4 and 7.5). Overall diversification practices tended to increase the fermentation bacterial groups across all the three sites. Higher abundances of this bacterial functional group were found under cover

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cropping in Italy and Lithuania (only in block 2) and crop rotation (only in block 3) in Spain (Table 7.5). Non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria were higher under ICC compared to INC in Italy only in the first block, while a significant reduction of this bacterial group under crop rotation was observed in Spain (Table 7.5). Not clear trends were observed in Lithuania, where non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria abundance varied according to both treatment and block, recording higher and lower abundances under cover cropping in block 2 and 3, respectively. Concerning fungal groups, litter saprotrophs were significantly affected by the management practices only in Spain, where crop rotation boosted this fungal groups by almost 55% (Table 7.5). Diversification practices significantly affected arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi in all the experimental sites. In Spain we observed a negative effect of crop rotation on mycorrhizal groups. A similar effect was found in Lithuania and Italy under cover cropping. Nevertheless, in these sites the effect of the treatment was found only in one block (Table 7.5). Despite the ANOVA underlined a significant effect of practices on dung saprophytes fungi, in Italy the post-hoc test did not highlight any significant differences. A different scenario was observed in Spain where dung saprophytes decreased by 63% under crop rotation, while no differences were recorded in Lithuanian site (Table 7.5).

Table 7.5. Results of the Tuckey HSD test carried out on functional traits/groups where treatment or the interaction between treatment and block was significant. Treatments indicated by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$. Bars denote standard errors of the mean. INC= Natural Cover and Compost; ICC= Cover crop and Compost, NT= No tillage, NTR= No tillage + crop rotation, NT+CC= No tillage + Cover crop. ns= not significant; -= factors or interactions not included in the regression model (See Table 4); Nd= functional trait/group not detected in the samples.

	Functional trait/group	Treatment		Treatment x Block						
		INC	ICC	INC X Block 1	INC X Block 2	INC X Block 3	ICC X Block 1	ICC X Block 2	ICC X Block 3	
Italy	Perennials (%)	57.7±04.40 a	7.3±2.10 b	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Specific Leaf Area (m ² g ⁻¹)	28.17±0.46 a	23.91±0.39 b	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Fermentation	1.54±0.11 b	2.33±0.16 a	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	NP Cyanobacteria	0.008±0.003 b	0.023±0.003 a	0.00±0.005 b	0.009±0.005 a	0.015±0.005 a	0.044±0.005 a	0.009±0.005 a	0.015±0.005 a	
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	ns	ns	0.16±0.04 a	0.20±0.04 a	0.02±0.04 a	0.07±0.04 a	0.01±0.04 b	0.02±0.04 a	
	Dung Saprotroph	2.74±0.27 a	2.49±0.25 a	4.51±0.77 a	1.50±0.26 a	3.05±0.52 a	2.31±0.39 b	1.87±0.32 a	3.60±0.61 a	
			NT	NTR	NT X Block 1	NT X Block 2	NT X Block 3	NTR X Block 1	NTR X Block 2	NTR X Block 3
	Spain	Perennials (%)	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd
Specific Leaf Area (m ² g ⁻¹)		ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Grass-like		ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Fermentation		ns	ns	4.95±0.32 a	4.09±0.32 a	4.00±0.32 b	4.41±0.32 a	4.95±0.32 a	5.47±0.32 a	
NP Cyanobacteria		0.038±0.005 a	0.011±0.005 b	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Litter Saprotroph		13.55±1.37 b	21.01±2.13 a	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Arbuscular Mycorrhiza		2.48±0.46 a	0.55±0.10 b	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Dung Saprotroph		1.86±0.15 a	0.68±0.15 b	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		NT	NT+CC	NT X Block 1	NT X Block 2	NT X Block 3	NT+CC X Block 1	NT+CC X Block 2	NT+CC X Block 3	
Lithuania	Perennials (%)	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Specific Leaf Area (m ² g ⁻¹)	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Fermentation	ns	Ns	2.55±0.91 a	2.45±0.9 b	2.08±0.07 a	2.69±0.10 a	3.46 ±0.12 a	2.00 ±0.07 a	
	NP Cyanobacteria	ns	Ns	0.103±0.031 a	0.000±0.031 b	0.154±0.031 a	0.071±0.031 a	0.109±0.031 a	0.000±0.031 b	
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	Ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	0.10±0.03 a	0.06±0.03 a	0.24±0.05 a	0.00±0.05 a	0.07±0.05 a	0.03±0.05 b	0.10±0.05 a	0.03±0.05 a	
	Dung Saprotroph	ns	Ns	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Conclusion

Our preliminary results indicate that specific plant traits, such as SLA and Perennials, significantly influenced both bacterial and fungal groups, particularly: (i) Non photosynthetic cyanobacteria, fermentation and cellulolytic bacteria, and (ii) arbuscular mycorrhiza, dung and litter saprotrophic fungal communities. Those groups showed significant negative effects on soil carbon levels. Furthermore, farm management practices were found to impact both plant and microbial functional groups.

Take-home message - This functional approach provides a valuable framework for investigating the relationships between plant and soil microbial biodiversity and their effects on soil health and ecosystem services. A deeper understanding of these interactions can guide the development of strategies for managing biodiversity to simultaneously promote environmental sustainability and agricultural productivity.

A publication on sub-task 7.1.2 results is under drafting.

Task 7.2 - Modelling soil organic matter dynamics - WR, INRAE

This task aims to model soil organic matter dynamics. A preliminary work was done by doing a literature review on plant-soil and plant-plant interactions controlling soil organic matter dynamics and NP fluxes in ecosystems. The literature review has been conducted and published in *Global Change Biology* (Fontaine et al., 2024 – D7.2.1).

Based on this work and in order to start a modelling process, two main approaches were used:

- In task 7.2.2, following a state-of-the-art review of existing soil models and processes already modelled, we selected a simple model of canopy dynamic (ModVege) and coupled it to a soil model (Symphony). The aim of the canopy model is to integrate the intra-annual dynamics of plant growth into the Symphony model, which until now has only integrated a constant flow of biomass input by plants. By using groups of plants with different phenology and different nutrient requirements over time, it will be possible to model the effects of synchrony or asynchrony between demands. The two models have now been coupled. Initial results from the first internship period were encouraging, but highlighted the need to integrate new processes, e.g. root pools and exudates. This was done during a second internship supervised by the engineer recruited for the project.

This work will be continued as part of a thesis. In task 7.2.3, we decided to use a widely used model in EU Member States and the EU level, RothC. The aim here was to realize the calibration of the model on the different situations investigated by the AGROECOseqC project. The working hypothesis was that the soil microbiome has an impact on carbon sequestration. From a theoretical point of view, there are several options for the inclusion of the soil microbiome. Preliminary calculations showed perspective for a rate modifying factor (RMF) called 'BIO', next to the other RMFs for temperature, moisture and soil cover in the model. To explore the possible use and impact of a modifying factor for the soil microbiome (RMFBIO) on SOC-stocks, comparison was made of model results for LTEs CS6, 7, 8, and 9 to BAU (the model 'as is'). The optimal RMF per treatment was defined as the RMF with minimal RMSE for that treatment and correlations analysis was performed between the optimal RMF and microbiome indicators. The threshold for a substantial correlation was set at 0.4 (abs) and for significance a p-value of 0.001. Finally, the impact of the soil microbiome on SOC-dynamics was assessed as the difference between the models BAU and with RMFBIO, over a period with known weather data. From the results it was inferred that the optimal RMF might be explained, at least partially, by the soil microbiome. However, the threshold for p-value was not met for any of the indicators. Consequently, adaptation of the RothC-model for the soil microbiome with a RMFBIO could only be made in general terms. It was concluded that, with model adaptation as described in this research, the impact of the soil microbiome on SOC built-up may be both positive and negative, depending on, e.g., soil texture.

These both tasks will be detailed in the deliverable 7.2 which is in a final step. It will be delivered in October 2024.

State of Task 7.2 milestones and deliverables:

- D.7.2 Report on classical and next generation models => Delivered in October 2024
- D.7.3. Scientific publications on modelling microbial carbon use efficiency and C-sequestration => Publication to be submitted within 31st December
- D7.1.2.0 Delivered as D7.1.2.0 final report. Publication on functional plants and some soil fungi groups integration with soil properties to be submitted within 31st December.
- M7.2.1.1 Evaluation and selection of classical and next generation models => Completed. The description of the work delivered as D.7.2

- M7.2.1.2. Evaluation of new process to improve SOM dynamics representation by using simple models => Completed. The description of the work delivered as D.7.2
- M7.2.2.3 Impact of soil biome on C-sequestration => Publication to be submitted within 31st December

WP8 - Communication, dissemination of results and stakeholders' engagement – CREA, CEBAS-CSIC

The main objective of the work package was to communicate the importance of agroecological strategies for soil health and sustainability, and to identify and target diverse stakeholder groups across Europe. Our specific objectives were threefold:

1. Building a Network of stakeholders across Europe.
2. Public Communication, in order to facilitate communication flow with the general public as well.
3. Develop joint scientific publications and datasets, with this last objective being more closely related to activities performed in Work Package 1.

Fig. 1 AGROECOseqC Website (M8.1)

During this last period of project activity, while the social media accounts on Facebook and Twitter were running regularly, covering key scientific topics (#soilscience, #agroecology and #biodiversity streams) and all events of interest to the project, all partners started to focus on exploitation activities by getting involved in writing and publishing scientific results.

WP8 was divided into three tasks. The first one, led by CREA, involved planning the communication strategy for the project and opening the website. Both of these were successfully completed on time.

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Fig. 2 AGROECOseqC Communication Plan (D8.1)

The website, hosted by EJP Soil’s main site (Fig. 1), is still working. It contains all the necessary information to identify project aims and methodologies, work packages, project partners, and so on. It also contains some pictures, graphs and a couple of videoclips.

Fig. 3 AGROECOseqC Social media account on Facebook and Twitter (M8.2)

Task 8.2, led by LAMMC, focused on the various activities targeting our different stakeholder groups, such as workshops, scientific events, and in-field activities. The Task 8.3, was about social media and publication. All activities were successfully completed on time, the main results will be discussed hereafter.

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Fig. 4 Contribution of each project partner to the total number of CDE activities performed: different colors represent different types of activities, bubble size indicates the amount of activities performed.

To date, we have performed a total of 96 activities (Tab. 1), and additional activities are scheduled for the upcoming months, primarily focusing on the exploitation of results which typically continue beyond the end of research projects. All CDE activities included: Field day, Magazines, News, PhDs, Post-docs, Poster, Presentation, Press release, Radio Interview, Res Exchange, Scientific paper, Stage, Training, Videoclip, Virtual academy, Webinar, Social media, Website. In fig. 4, the contribution of each project partner to the total number of activities performed is highlighted, the size of the bubbles indicates the amount of activities, allowing us to see how well each partner diversified. CREA and LAMMC had the most activities and best diversification among all partners.

Table 1 Overview of all CDE activities for AGROECOseqC until October 2024

Count of Type	General Scientific Technical		
	General	Scientific	Technical
Field day		4	9
Magazines			2
News	5		
PhDs		1	
Post-docs		4	
Poster		2	1
Presentation		32	
Press release	11		
Radio Interview	1		
Res Exchange			2
Scientific paper		9	
Stage		2	
Training			2
Videoclip	3		
Virtual academy		2	
Webinar		1	
Social media	2		
Website	1		
Grand Total	23	57	16

Deepening into the data, we can subdivide the total amount of activities into three main categories according to the type of content they delivered: General content (23), Scientific content (57), Technical content (16) (Fig. 5).

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Fig. 5 Categorization of AGROECOseqC CDE activities

There is a net prevalence of communication activities delivering scientific content, with 57 entries. Unfortunately, fewer activities focused on producing technical content to target sectoral experts, *id est* farmers and advisors. This aligns with the very nature of AGROECOseqC, which is a pure scientific project, with a kind of conclusions and findings which are complex and difficult to immediately transfer to the field. At the outset of the project, we identified target stakeholder groups: academia, farmers and advisors, and the general public. We successfully engaged all three groups, with academia being the primary focus. The general public emerged as the second most engaged group, surpassing farmers and advisors (Fig. 5).

Regarding the activities delivering scientific content, their main objective was to disseminate research findings and knowledge to drive innovation. The primary audience for these activities is a scholarly audience, and the content can be challenging for non-researcher stakeholders to understand. In this group, we can observe a broad range of communication activities typically performed by researchers.

These activities include the publication of scientific papers. While we initially committed to producing six papers, we have already published nine and more are planned, which is a significant achievement. Additionally, presentations and posters were delivered at conferences, workshops, and hubs such as national soil hubs. Field days, intended here as opportunities for knowledge exchange among research projects, were also organized.

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We coordinated one European webinar and participated to several virtual academies. High-level scientific training, including 1 PhD and 4 postdocs engagement, were carried out at research institutions.

Among the total number of ‘scientific content’ entries, project presentations at workshops were the most frequent. This category also includes our several

contributions to the EJPSOIL ASDs.

Fig. 6 Amount and type of CDE activities with scientific content, main scope and utilized media until October 2024

Fig. 7 Types across Countries, scientific content, for better visualisation only values >2 are shown.

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A non-exhaustive list of published and planned papers is given below:

Table 2 Published and planned papers

Title of the manuscript	DOI	Submission
Plant-soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: learning from natural ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems (Preprint)	https://hal.science/hal-04056769/document	2023
Plant-soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: learning from natural ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems	https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17034	2023
Weeds: An Insidious Enemy or a Tool to Boost Mycorrhization in Cropping Systems?	10.3390/microorganisms11020334	2023
Bioenergetic control of soil carbon dynamics across depth	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34951-w	2023
The enzyme patterns of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi reveal their different functions in soil.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2024.105323	2023
C stocks in abandoned short rotation forestry (SRF) plantations in Central Italy.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11056-023-10004-y	2023
The Content and Stratification of SOC and Its Humified Fractions Using Different Soil Tillage and Inter-Cropping.	https://doi.org/10.3390/su16030953	2024
Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungal phyla as indicators of land use efficiency for soil organic carbon accrual with woody plantations	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111796	2024
Fungal β -glucosidase gene and corresponding enzyme activity are positively related to soil organic carbon in unmanaged woody plantations	https://doi.org/10.1007/s42832-024-0238-2	2024
A Comparative Study of Agroecological Intensification Across Diverse European Agricultural Systems to Assess Soil Structure and Carbon Dynamics	https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14123024	2025
The role of tillage practices in wheat straw decomposition and shaping the associated microbial communities in Endocalcaric– Epigleyic Cambisol soil	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-024-01879-w	2024
Disentangling the influence of different agroecological practices on dominant and rare microbial community in a gradient of European countries		Submitted to <i>Agr.Ecosyst.& Env.</i> - AGEE45623 - on Jan. 2025
Context-Driven Agroecological Intensification to support Soil Health and C accrual: Insights from Multi-site Experiment		Submitted to <i>EJSS</i> –868-24-Special Issue III “Soil Health: Current Status and Future Challenges” on Dec. 2024
Evaluation of Soil Health in Agroecosystems for Turkiye and Europe: Investigating Phosphorus-Solubilizing Fungi in Sustainable Agricultural Practices	10.5281/zenodo.1458682 (under embargo up to 31 Oct 2025)	Submitted to <i>EJSS</i> –on Jan.. 2024

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On 4 March, the project hosted the online scientific forum "Agroecological Intensification and Functional Biodiversity", open to researchers as well as farmers and practitioners, which reached 47 participants at its peak. Several presentations by AGROECOseqC partners illustrated methodologies and first results on plant-soil-fauna-microbial functional diversity, biomass production, N leaching, C sequestration, with a nice discussion between the presenters and the participants, indicating a fair interest of the audience.

Scientific Forum
Agroecological intensification and functional biodiversity
March 4th, 2024, 9:00-11:00 CEST
To participate, [click here](#)

Alessandra Trincherà (CREA)
Plant and soil diversity as drivers of agrosystem functioning:
AGROECOseqC project

Sebastien Fontaine (INRAE)
Plant-soil synchrony in nutrient cycles:
Learning from ecosystem to design sustainable agrosystems

Dylan Warren Raffa (CREA)
Role of plant community diversity and traits on agrosystem functioning

Sara Sanchez - Moreno (CSIC - INIA) Soil invertebrate functional diversity across European agroecological experiments

Margarita Ros (CEBAS - CSIC)
Assess the impacts of sustainable soil management on soil biodiversity

Ludovica Saccà (CREA)
Combined evaluation of soil C enzyme activities and functional genes in woody plantations

Contacts: alessandra.trincherà@crea.gov.it
valentina.baratella@crea.gov.it

Graphic: Francesco Ambrosini

The collage features several scientific publications:

- microorganisms** (MDPI): *Weeds: An Insidious Enemy or a Tool to Boost Mycorrhization in Cropping Systems?* by Alessandra Trincherà.
- nature communications**: *Bioenergetic control of soil carbon dynamics across depth* by Ludovic Honneron et al.
- Ecological Indicators** (Elsevier): *Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungal phyla as indicators of land use efficiency for soil organic carbon accrual with woody plantations* by Luisa M. Manici et al.
- Applied Soil Ecology**: *Some patterns of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi reveal their different functions in soil* by Francesco Caputo et al.
- SOIL ECOLOGY LETTERS** (RESEAF): *Fungal β -glucosidase gene and corresponding enzyme are positively related to soil organic carbon in unmanaged woody plantations* by Maria Ludovica Saccà et al.
- sustainability**: *The Content and Stratification of SOC in Different Soil Tillage and Inter-Cropping* by Alvyra Slepetiene et al.
- Applied Soil Ecology**: *The enzyme patterns of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi reveal their different functions in soil* by Luisa M. Manici et al.
- Soil Ecology Letters**: *C stocks in abandoned short rotation forestry (SRF) plantations in Central Italy* (Research published 30 September 2023).

Fig. 8 A showcase of scientific papers published so far (sept 2024)

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AGROECOseqC contributed to the organization of the EJPSOIL Annual Science Days 2024, where the project convened the breakout session C2 - Soil biodiversity & ecosystem services. This last and all events where the project was represented by oral presentations or posters are listed below (Tab. 3):

Table 3 Scientific events in which AGROECOseqC has been represented

Date	Event	Presentation title	Partner Acronym and/or contact person
31th July 2022	World Congress of Soil Science WCSS2022	Poster "Grounds for assessing regional reference values for organic carbon contents in soil"	Marjoleine Hanegraaf
June 2-3, 2022	5th International Symposium of Soil Physics	Oral presentation "Tillage and cover crop management impact on soil quality and pest pressure"	Gražina Kadžienė
June 20-21th 2022	AB HORIZON 2020 EJP SOIL Program National Workshop on Sustainable Soil Management	Oral Presentation "AGROECOSeqC - Agroecological Strategies for an Efficient Functioning of Plant - Soil Biota Interactions to Increase SOC Sequestration-Turkey"	Akin UN / Abdulkadir BAL / Saddam Kalkan
February 04th 2022	TAGEM Annual Project Evaluation Meetings	Oral Presentation "AGROECOSeqC - Agroecological Strategies for an Efficient Functioning of Plant - Soil Biota Interactions to Increase SOC Sequestration-Turkey"	Akin UN / Abdulkadir BAL / Saddam Kalkan
December 07th 2022	Workshop "Stocktake study and recommendations for harmonising methodologies for fertilisation guidelines"- International Fertiliser Society Conference, 7 – 9 December 2022, Robinson College, Cambridge, UK	Agroecological strategies for an efficient functioning of plant - soil biota interactions to increase SOC sequestration - The AGROECOseqC project	Alessandra Trinchera
December 09th 2022	EJP SOIL JOINT SOIL PROGRAM CONFERENCE	Agroecological strategies for efficient functioning of plant-soil biota interactions to increase soil organic carbon sequestration	S. Suproniene
June 8-9th 2022	EJP SOIL Annual Science Days 2022	AGROECOseqC project updates	Alessandra Trinchera

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	BO Session "Soil biodiversity and ecosystem services" A. Trinchera (CREA) Convener	Designing sustainable agrosystems to promote plant-soil synchrony	Fontaine, S.
		Modelling the impact of the soil microbiome on carbon sequestration in the AGROECOseqC-project	Hanegraaf M.C.
		Tuning the soil microbiome to support sustainable crop systems	Hernandez-Soriano, M.
		Microorganisms as biological indicators of soil quality under different tillage systems in Retisol	Vilkiene, M.
June 12-14th 2023	EJP SOIL Annual Science Days 2023 BO Session "Soil biodiversity and ecosystem services" A. Trinchera (CREA) Convener	Sculpting the soil microbiota: role of soil management and plant-diversity based farming practices	A. Trinchera
		Designing sustainable agrosystems by copying the biogeochemical organization of natural ecosystems	S. Fontaine et al.
		A guideline for appropriate estimates of carbon use efficiency with the 18O method	Rodríguez, A., Fontaine, S.
		Early detection of microbial carbon stabilization by biomarker-SIP	J.Ramussen
		Validation of microbial community-level physiological profiles (CLPP) analysis in LAMMC and MBG Santiago-CSIC	S.Supronienė et al.
		Variation in soil bacterial community structure under different tillage intensity	M. Vilkiene et al.
		Soil proteins as biochemical indicators of the plant-soil-microorganism system as a whole -	F.Delporte et al.
November 20th 2023	EJP SOIL Spanish National Workshop	AGROECOseqC	S.Sanchez-Moreno
October 18th 2023	National Workshop EJP SOIL - France	AGROECOseqC	S. Fontaine
December 21th 2022	Networking de Proyectos Europeos	EJP SOIL AGROECOseqC	INIA-CSIC
October 26th 2023	To be inserted	Markdag om bælgfrugter og blandingsafgrøder	AARHUS
31/08/2023	Wageningen Soil Conference	Poster, Clever Cover Cropping Experiment	WUR
July 4th 2023	EKOAgriTech exhibition of organic farming technologies	Ekologinės žemdirbystės technologijų Paroda - forumas EKOAgriTech	LAMMC
June 11th 2024	EJP SOIL Annual Science Days 2024 BO Session "Soil biodiversity & ecosystem services" Dylan Warren Raffa (CREA) Convener	Response of spontaneous flora to ecological intensification in a fruit and arable system in Mediterranean conditions: an overview of the communities' potential contribution to soil C input and storage	Elena Testani
		Soil nitrogen pool dynamics in an agroecological gradient	Antonio Rodriguez
		A guideline for estimating carbon use efficiency with the 18O method	Antonio Rodriguez

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		Regional assessment of soil organic matter stability under no-till and diversified agricultural management practices	Suproniene Skaidre
		Trying to answer burning questions on functional diversity and soil carbon that keep awake agroecologists overnight	Dylan Warren Raffa
		Assessing the influence of long-term agroecological practices on soil microbial functional diversity and metabolic activity	Shamshitov Arman
		Effect of agroecological intensification on root mycorrhization, soil aggregate dimension and related C content by SEM-EDS	Alessandra Trincherà
		Analysis of soil microbial community associated with cereal crop under sustainable managements in different European countries	Marga Ros
September 9-12th 2024	XIV National Congress of the Italian Society of Silviculture and Forest Ecology (SISEF)	Oral presentation "Il ruolo delle Short Rotation Forestry (SRF) nella mitigazione dei cambiamenti climatici: un caso studio in regione Emilia-Romagna"	Alessandro Paletto

In 2024, the project was also represented at the XIV National Congress of the Italian Society of Silviculture and Forest Ecology (SISEF), held in Padua, with an oral presentation by Alessandro Paletto of CREA-AA entitled "Il ruolo delle Short Rotation Forestry (SRF) nella mitigazione dei cambiamenti climati: un caso studio in regione Emilia-Romagna".

Table 4 provides a comprehensive overview of all the training activities carried out as part of our research project, designed to enhance the skills and knowledge of participants to ensure they are well equipped to contribute effectively to the project's objectives.

Table 4 AGROECOseqC training activities

Type	Host (Event, Editor, etc.)	Title	Year	Partner
stage	CREA	7-days stage of Dott. Akin Un (General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies TAGEM, Turchia)	2021	CREA
virtual academy	MaxRoot-C Virtual Academy (BOKU/AGES)	Presentation of AGROECOseqC objectives, hypothesis, adopted strategy and expected outcomes	2022	CREA
virtual academy	MaxRoot-C Monthly Virtual Academy (BOKU/AGES)	Presentation: Plant diversity: a driver to increase microbial functional diversity in soil	2022	CREA

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PhD engagement	LAMMC	PhD student participating to T2.2 of the project	2022	LAMMC
Post-doc engagement	INRAE	Pos doc participating to T5.1, T5.2, T5.3 of the project	2022	INRAE
Post-doc engagement	AU	Pos doc participating to Sub-task 5.3 of the project	2022	AU
Training	INIA-CSIC	Soil sampling in INIA experimental crop areas	2023	INIA-CSIC
Training	INIA-CSIC	Soil sampling in INIA experimental crop areas	2023	INIA-CSIC
Res Exchange	CRAW	4 days stay Soil sampling in INRAE experimental cereal crop	2023	CRAW
Res Exchange	INRAE	4 days stay Soil sampling in INRAE experimental cereal crop	2023	INRAE
Stage	CREA	5-days stage of Dott. Arman Shamshitov, working in Task 2.2 (LAMMC-LT)	2023	LAMMC
Post-doc engagement	MaxRoot-C Virtual Academy (BOKU/AGES)	Pos doc participating to the project as leader of sub-task 7.1.2	2024	CREA

Ranking second, the delivering of general content aimed to communicate in a clear and understandable way to a broad audience, that is society at large, including non-experts.

Fig. 9 Amount and type of CDE activities with general content, main scope and utilized media until October 2024

The main objective was to raise awareness about agroecology and soil health, and to promote social support for scientific research. These activities included the releasing of press releases, news and newsletters, video clips, radio interviews, website updates, and social media postings. In our case, all these activities were digital.

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Fig. 10 Types across Countries, general content

Our website and the two social media accounts were to spread information quickly and facilitate networking. We produced three engaging video clips and one radio interview with our coordinator. We released several press releases and updates to inform about our progress. In total, we conducted 23 activities, with the majority being press releases published on various websites.

A list of press releases, newsletter, national publications and/or interviews is given below (Tab. 5):

Table 5 Press releases, newsletter, national publications and interviews

Date	Publication type	Publication title	Partner Acronym	Link to the publication	Press Review if any
10/12/2021	Press release	Il Progetto AGROECOseqC per un'agricoltura all'insegna dell'intensificazione ecologica	CREA	https://www.crea.gov.it/en/news-eventi-feed/-/asset_publisher/SUWfIQ81JiSe/content/id/3168210	https://www.studiocasciaro.it/news/
					https://www.ecologiaambiente.com
					http://www.sinab.it/bionovita/agroecologia-il-crea-avvia-il-progetto-agroecoseqc
					https://www.finalmentelunedì.it
16/12/2021	Press release	INIA en el proyecto EJP SOIL: AGROECOseqC "Estrategias AGROECOLógicas para una interacción eficiente planta-biota edáfica para incrementar el secuestro de carbono", hacia la intensificación ecológica de la agricultura	INIA	https://www.inia.es/comunicacion/noticias/Pages/INIA-en-el-proyecto-EJP-SOIL-AGROECOseqC-%E2%80%9CEstrategias-AGROECOLógicas-para-una-interacci%C3%B3n-eficiente-planta-biota-ed%C3%A1fica-pa.aspx?csf=1&e=RoWZEX?IDPram=2033	

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16/12/2021	Press release	EJP SOIL projektas AGROECOseqC žemės ūkio ekologizavimui. EJP SOIL projektas AGROECOseqC žemės ūkio ekologizavimui	LAMMC	https://www.lammc.lt/lt/naujienu-archyvas/ejp-soil-projektas-agroecoseqc-zemes-ukio-ekologizavimui/3653	
16/12/2021	Press release	Fertilizzanti microbici biologici: indagine dell'effetto sulla crescita e sulla produzione delle piante	CREA	https://www.crea.gov.it/en/web/agricoltura-e-ambiente/-/investigation-of-the-effect-of-microbial-fertilizer-containing-biological-agent-on-growth-and-production-of-plants	
18/01/2022	Press release	Agroecologia: Il CREA avvia il progetto AGROECOseqC con il kickoff meeting	CREA	https://www.crea.gov.it/en/web/agricoltura-e-ambiente/-/il-crea-avvia-il-progetto-agroecoseqc-con-il-kickoff-meeting	https://esgdata.it/agroecologia-il-crea-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-agroecoseqc/
21/03/2022	Press release	Projektas AGROECOseqC įsibėgėja	LAMMC	https://www.lammc.lt/lt/naujienu-archyvas/projektas-agroecoseqc-isibegeja/3732	
14/02/2022	Press release	AB HORIZON 2020 EJP SOIL Projelerimiz	TAGEM	https://arastirma.tarimorman.gov.tr/gaptaem/Haber/110/Ab-Horizon-2020-Ejp-Soil-Projelerimiz	
26/05/2022	Press release	Todo lo que el suelo y la agricultura pueden hacer para evitar el cambio climático	CSIC	https://www.lavozdegalicia.es/noticia/somosagro/agricultura/2022/05/25/suelo-agriculturapueden-evitar-cambio-climatico/00031653487331215234872.htm	https://www.innovagri.es/actualidad/buscan-soluciones-sostenibles-para-la-gestion-del-suelo-agricola.html https://www.phytoma.com/noticias/noticias-de-actualidad/el-csic-investiga-la-adaptacion-de-los-suelos-agricolas-al-cambio-climatico https://www.campogalego.es/galicia-participa-en-dos-proyectos-europeos-para-estudiar-la-importancia-de-los-microorganismos-en-la-fertilidad-de-los-suelos-agricolas/ https://maxideza.com/la-importancia-de-los-microorganismos-en-la-fertilidad-de-los-suelos-agricolas/
29/05/2022	Newsletter	Towards ecological intensification of agriculture	CREA - INRAE	https://ejpsoil.eu/about-ejp-soil/news-events/item/artikel/towards-the-ecological-intensification-of-agriculture	

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13/09/2022	News - SoMe repost on websites		TAGEM	https://www.instagram.com/p/CicMI8vMXSR/?img_index=1	
02/11/2022	Press release	Il CREA su Radio Rai: l'agricoltura biologica fondamentale per la salute del suolo	CREA	https://www.crea.gov.it/-/il-crea-su-radio-rai-l-agricoltura-biologica-fondamentale-per-la-salute-del-suolo	https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKewiQ4orst6eAAxVrhv0HHdo8DBoQFnoECCYQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.crea.gov.it%2Fdocuments%2F20126%2F0%2FGreen%2BDeal_Trincher_a_Bussinello%2B%25281%2529.pdf%2F8be4d3d6-8b62-5747-b61c-37960d87654b%3Ft%3D1664977727602&usg=AOvVaw3UqZ28arAVM0EFVaKUOctZ&opi=89978449
09/12/2022	Press release	EJP SOIL renginyje kalbėta apie aktualias dirvožemio problemas	LAMMC	https://www.lammc.lt/lt/naujienu-archyvas/ejp-soil-renginyje-kalbeta-apie-aktualias-dirvozemio-problemas/3917	
12/05/2023	News - SoMe repost on websites		INIA-CSIC	https://www.ant-ecology.eu/	
June 2023	Press Release	De Groenbemesterdag 'De tijd zal het leren!'	WUR	https://www.akkerwijzer.nl/event/731539-thema-dag-de-groenbemesterdag-de-tijd-zal-het-leren--lelystad/	
2023	Publication on DENDRON ATURA Italian biannual magazine	Il ruolo delle Short Rotation Forestry (SRF) nella mitigazione dai cambiamenti climatici: il caso studio di Anzola dell'Emilia	CREA - AA	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375597472_Il_ruolo_delle_Short_Rotation_Forestry_SRF_nella_mitigazione_dai_cambiamenti_climatici_il_caso_studio_di_Anzola_dell'Emilia	
2024	Publication on Forest@ - Italian Journal	Microbial indicators as innovative methods to assess the performance of woody crops in soil organic carbon sequestration and natural resource valorisation	CREA - AA	https://foresta.sisef.org/contents/?id=efor4610-021	

In 2022, 3 videos and a radio interview on the National Radio and Television Service of Italy were produced to present the project and were also distributed through the official channels of EJP SOIL (Tab. X).

Date	Publication type	Publication title	Partner Acronym	Link to the publication
May 2022		Presentation of AGROECOseqC	CREA - AA	https://youtu.be/AV90kMFRDOA
2022	Interview with AGROECOseqC coordinator on during the Italian radio program "Me, Chiara and the Green" on ISORADIO - RAI	Organic agriculture and soil health in the frammwork of AGROECOseqC project	CREA - AA	https://www.raiplaysound.it/audio/2022/10/lo-Chiara-e-il-green-del-31102022-0ac594ac-4d40-4948-a8ad-e0923888cc36.html
June 2022		Presentation of AGROECOseqC and MIXROOT-C	AU-AGRO	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/jim-rasmussen-5551a5b_ejpabrsoil-mixrootc-agroecoseqc-activity-6947221444162433024-5R8?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
December 09th 2022		Video on JOINT EJP SOIL SOIL PROGRAM CONFERENCE	LAMMC	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5xPagDolPvs

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Lastly, we disseminated specialized knowledge and technical skills to sectoral experts to make research findings operational, and to aid decision-making for policy and experts.

Fig. 11 Amount and type of CDE activities with technical content, main scope and utilized media until October 2024

In this context, we organized field days, here not intended as knowledge sharing among peers, but as open days in fields to showcase innovative practices, so as to be knowledge transfer to sectoral experts. These events were held mainly in experimental fields or at agricultural national exhibitions.

Additionally, we conducted training activities and research exchanges to share methodologies, for example, at institutions or national hubs.

We published two technical articles in specialized national magazines and presented posters at agricultural exhibitions. Considering the total amount of these activities, we successfully organized most of them as field days, as promised at the beginning of the project.

As a core part of the project's communication activities, most of the planned field visits and workshops listed in Tab. 4, have taken place in the countries of the project consortium, with the last field visit of CREA, which took place during the final annual meeting of the project, 1-2 October 2024.

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Fig. 12 Types across Countries, technical content

During the field visits, the participants had the opportunity to deepen the project themes through a direct exchange with researchers and to personally approach the observation of agroecological practices in a real context, thus promoting a deeper understanding of environmental and agronomic dynamics for

professionals and at the same time stimulating awareness of the topic on the part of ordinary citizens or policy makers.

Table 4 field visits and workshops until september 2024

Date	Conference/Workshop/Seminar	Content	Event name	City, Country	Partner Acronym
29 June - 1 July 2022	AGROECOseqC (project presentation, Lithuanian)	Field Day - Presentation, Poster	Agrovizija (AGROVISION)	Lithuania	LAMMC
22 June 2022	AGROECOseqC (project presentation, French)	Field Day - Presentation, Poster	FA ² C = Festival of Agro-Ecology and Conservative Agriculture	Belgium Wallonia	CRAW
22/09/2022	Is de bodembiodiversiteit belangrijk voor koolstofvastlegging van groenbemesters?	Field Day - Presentation, Poster	De tijd zal het leren!	The Netherland	WUR
21/12/2022	EJP SOIL AGROECOSeqC	Field Day - Presentation	Networking de Projectos Europeos	Spain	INIA-CSIC

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10/06/2023	AGROECOseqC (project presentation, Danish)	Presentation	AU Viborg (<i>Research Center Foulum</i>) Open House	Denmark	AARHUS
26/04/2023	Project presentation at INIA experimental farm “LaCanaleja”	Field Day - Presentation	GRA GHG Global Research Alliance on Agricultural Greenhouse Gases visit at INIA experimental farm “LaCanaleja”	Spain	INIA-CSIC
26/10/2023	n/a	Field Day - Presentation	Markdag om bælgfrugter og blandingsafgrøder	Denmark	AARHUS
28/04/2023	AGROECOseqC (project presentation, French)	Presentation	Field visit - Clienfarms Project	Belgium Wallonia	CRAW
15/05/2023	AGROECOseqC (project presentation, French)	Field Day - Presentation	Field visit for students	Belgium Wallonia	CRAW
22/05/2023	AGROECOseqC (project presentation, French)	Field Day - Presentation	Field visit for students	Belgium Wallonia	CRAW
22/09/2023	Green Manure Day	Field Day - Presentation		The Netherlands	WUR
4th July 2023	Ekologinės žemdirbystės technologijų Paroda - forumas EKOAgriTech (project presentation, Lithuanian)	Field Day - Presentation	EKOAgriTech exhibition of organic farming technologies	Lithuania	LAMMC
31/08/2023	Wageningen Soil Conference	Poster, discussions	Clever Cover Cropping Experiment	Wageningen, Netherlands	WUR

In Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 the proportion of international vs national activities is reported, across categories, highlighting the contribution of the different partners, and across partners, by considering the different types of activity. Field Days were predominantly national activities, as we used open days, agricultural exhibitions, and field workshops to showcase our practices to national representatives of farmers and advisors. Press releases were also disseminated through national websites and media.

A slice of our Presentations were also performed at national events, such as at National Soil Hubs or EJPSOIL National workshop.

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Fig. 13 International vs national activities across categories

Fig. 14 International vs national activities across partners, lighter colours for national activities

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In Fig. 14 the amount and type of communication activities performed by the different partners is reported, with the total levelled to 100%. CREA, as the leader of the WP, performed nearly, if not all, the different types of dissemination and communication activities, followed closely by Lithuania, Spain, and the Netherlands. We can highlight (in green) that nearly all partners organized Field Days, as promised at the beginning of the project. There were some issues managing the field event in Turkey due to weather conditions.

Fig. 15 Communication activities performed by the different partners, the total levelled to 100%

Regarding social media activities, as previously said, we run two social media accounts: one on Facebook, which has primarily local (Italian) audience, and one on Twitter, which has a wider international reach. We will therefore focus on the results of our Twitter activities. We started our Twitter account in 2022 with just two members. Over less than three years, our community has grown to over 500 members (Fig. 15). We have a balanced gender distribution, with almost half male and half female members, mainly English-speaking, and 73% of them say that science is their favourite subject. Most come from Spain, Italy, the UK and France, but we have a few members from all over the world (Fig. 16).

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In terms of age demographics, while Twitter's baseline shows a majority of members under the age of 34, our project has attracted more representatives from older age groups. We have fewer members under 34 and more members over 35, including the

Fig. 16 Twitter demographics, sept 2024

very rare 'over 55' (Fig. 17). with the content we shared, which is more likely to capture the attention of experts and mature individuals who browse social media for information and updates. In fact, compared to the global audience of twitter, our members appear to be higher-level educated, and accessing our content in working days, working hours, from desktop, indicating they're working-class information seeker.

Fig. 17 Geographical span of Twitter followers, sept 2024

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Fig. 18 Twitter demographics and psychology

If we conduct an audience analysis of our members, we can identify three main clusters: soil scientists, Agroecology innovators, and ecology researchers (Fig. 18).

Fig. 19 Audience analysis – Twitter, September 2024

These results are very promising for project, they indicate that our struggling in managing social media accounts have paid off, as we have successfully reached and engaged our target stakeholders. During the peak of our Twitter activities, our engagement rate (N times users interacted with a tweet / N times users have seen the tweet) averaged 6%, and we received an average of 3 likes per day.

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Among our followers, apart from researchers and PhD students from around the world, we frequently interacted with medium to large institutional and private accounts, such as Eu_green Research (the official account of REA). Also, we managed networking with several European research projects focused on soil and sustainability topics.

Fig. 20 Some followers, randomly selected, september 2024

The project is contributing to the organization of the final EJPSOIL Italian workshop, to be held in Rome in person and online the 4 and 5 December 2024, in correspondence with the World Soil Day. At the event, the project coordinator Alessandra Trincherà will represent AGROECOseqC and will present the main results to two different target national audiences: farmers and consultants, and policy makers.

The final meeting of the project was held at the CREA Centre in Rome on 1 and 2 October. This meeting provided a comprehensive overview of the project's achievements. Each Work Package (WP) presented its main results, highlighting key findings and advances made during the project. Discussions also focused on exploring future collaboration opportunities to build on the project's success and foster ongoing

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partnerships. The event concluded with a field trip to CREA's long-term experimental field, MAIOR. This visit provided participants with a first-hand look at the experimental setups and ongoing research activities.

Fig. 21 Project final meeting, Rome, 1-2 October 2024

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Fig. 22 Field-days at CREA long-term experimental site MAIOR, 2 October 2024

To conclude, some conclusion as the take-home message from the communication work package of AGROECOseqC. As researchers, we excel in disseminating science in the traditional ways, such as preparing posters, doing presentations, and publishing scientific papers. However, is this what is expected of us today in order to communicate science? A key learning from this project for us: it is not. We are asked a bit more, we are asked to promote change, or at least to help in promoting change. That means, raising awareness in society at large by creating general content and using the digital transmission of knowledge. Also, we are expected to advance the knowledge transfer to the productive sectors, which requires us to produce technical content and make our findings operational. It's not just about building a flexible plan, diversified activities, targeting different stakeholders, using appropriate channels and tools—these are our fundamental learnings.

But there is a major insight that is: to be successful, we need a collective effort that goes beyond our individual expertise. We need Teamwork and the continuous support from professionals as the two pillars of success.

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None of the nice results you have seen for this WP would have been reached without your work and cooperation. So that, communicating science today is not a one-man mission, but a collective effort.

Photo credit to Sam Illingworth at ratbotcomic.com. Retrieved from

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Deliverables

Please complete/update the last four columns in the table. from M46 to M54

Internal research project title	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery due date, EJP SOIL month	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Estimate delivery date	Comments
AGROECOseqC	D1.1.1	AGROECOseqC Handbook on sampling and protocols for soil, plant and root analyses	M24	M30		Delivered Handbook_A GROECOseqC_D1.1.1_D2.1.1_D2.2.1_D2.2.2_D.2.3_D3.1.1_D3.2.1_D3.3.1_D4.1_D4.2.1_D6.1.1_D6.1.2_D5.1.1_D5.2.1_2208 23 (pages 1-19) INRAE repository

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AGROECOseqC	D2.1.1	Protocol for phytosociological surveys	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 20-22)
AGROECOseqC	D2.2.1	Protocol for plant mycorrhizal colonization intensity	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 22-24)
AGROECOseqC	D2.2.2	Protocol for SEM analysis of mycorrhizal mycelial network	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 24-26)
AGROECOseqC	D.2.3	Protocol for plant sampling, nutrient content analysis and PDB screening	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 26-29)
AGROECOseqC	D3.1.1	Protocols for soil microfauna sampling	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 30-31)
AGROECOseqC	D3.2.1	Protocols for soil mesofauna sampling	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 32-33)
AGROECOseqC	D3.3.1	Protocols for soil	M24	M27		Delivered

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		macrofauna sampling and key attribute of soil food web structure				Handbook (pages 33-36)
AGROECOseqC	D6.1.1	Protocols for C pools and soil aggregates analysis	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (pages 55-61)
AGROECOseqC	D6.1.2	Protocols for C/N semi-quantitative analysis by SEM-EDS	M24	M27		Delivered Handbook (page 62-63)
AGROECOseqC	D 8.1	Communication plan	M24	M24		Delivered (Y1, preliminary version)
AGROECOseqC	D5.1.1	Protocol of plant nutrient demand measurement	M25	M25		Delivered Handbook (page 47-51)
AGROECOseqC	D5.2.1	Protocol of pulse labelling	M25	M25		Delivered Handbook (page 53-54)
AGROECOseqC	D4.1	Protocol of bacteria	M27	M27		Delivered

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		and fungi diversity indexes and functional traits, target functional genes by PCR				Handbook (page 37-42)
AGROECOseqC	D4.2.1	Protocol of microbial biomass and activity, microbial CLPP analysis, C.stock in living wood, soil enzyme	M27	M27		Delivered Handbook (page 42-46)
AGROECOseqC	D.1.2.1	First Annual report	M32			Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D2.2.3.	Review about weeds and mycorrhizal infection relationship (Task 2.2.)	New	M34		Delivered Trinchera, A.; Warren Raffa, D. (2023) Weeds: An Insidious Enemy or a Tool to Boost Mycorrhization in Cropping Systems? Microorganism

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						ms, 11, 334. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms1020334 (opensource)
AGROECOseqC	D5.1.1.	Publication on soil carbon dynamics across depth	New	M34		Delivered Henneron L., Balesdent J., Alvarez G., Barré P., Baudin F., Basile- Doelsch I., Cécillon L. Fernandez- Martinez A., Hatté C.,& Fontaine S. (2022). Bioenergetic control of soil carbon dynamics across depth. Nature Communications. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34951-w (opensource)

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AGROECOseqC	D7.2.0 1	Synthesis paper on plant-soil synchrony and the design of sustainable agrosystems	M57	M38		Delivered Fontaine, S et al. Plant-soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: learning from natural ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems. Preprint. HAL (2023). https://hal.science/hal-04056769/document
AGROECOseqC	D7.1.2. 1	Selection of AGROECOseqC indicators	New	M38		Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D5.1.2	Report on plant nutrient demand	M42	M45		Delivered (WP5 AGROECOseqC overall dataset)
AGROECOseqC	D2.2.1. 2	Database for root mycorrhizal colonization intensity in	New	M41		Delivered

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		all core-sites				
AGROECOseqC	D4.1.2.1	Publication on function of forest sites on C-stock	New	M41		Delivered Paletto A., Ceotto E., Becagli C., Casagli F., Manici L. De Meo L. (2023) C-stocks in abandoned short rotation forestry (SRF) plantations in Central Italy“, New Forest https://doi.org/10.1007/s11056-023-10004-y
AGROECOseqC	D7.2.02	Synthesis paper on plant-soil synchrony and the design of sustainable agrosystems	M57	M38		Delivered S.Fontaine, L. Abbadie, M. Aubert, S.Barot, J M. G. Bloor, D. Derrien, O. Duchene, N. Gross, L. Henneron (2023). Plant–

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						soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: Learning from ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems. Global Change Biology, 30, 1, e17034 https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17034
AGROECOseqC	D2.1.2	Database for plant communities' functional traits	M45			Delivered (WP2 AGROECOseqC overall dataset)
AGROECOseqC	D3.1.2	List of nematode and tardigrade taxa present at core sites	M45			Delivered (WP3 AGROECOseqC overall dataset)

AGROECOseqC	D3.2.2	List of mites and collembola taxa present at core sites	M45			Delivered (WP3 AGROECOs eqC overall dataset)
AGROECOseqC	D1.4	AGROECO seqC Data Management Plan (DMP) rev_260124	New	M46		Delivered Last revised version submitted on 31 st october 2024
AGROECOseqC	D6.1.4.01	Paper on effect of soil tillage and intercropping on SOC and humified fractions	New	M46		Delivered Slepetiene, A.; Kadziene, G.; Suproniene, S.; Skersiene, A.; Auskalniene, O. The Content and Stratification of SOC and Its Humified Fractions Using Different Soil Tillage and Inter-Cropping.

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						Sustainability 2024, 16, 953. https://doi.org/10.3390/su16030953
AGROECOseqC	D4.1.1	Soil microbial communities (bacteria and fungi) by NGS sequencing (phylogenetic and functional approach)	M47	M49		Delivered (overall AGROECOseqC dataset)
AGROECOseqC	D.4.2.2	Soil microbial enzyme activity report	M49			Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D3.3.2	List of arthropod and earthworm taxa present at core sites	M45	M48		Delivered (overall AGROECOseqC dataset)
AGROECOseqC	D7.1.1.1	Definition of a set of common microbial	M47	M49		Saccà et al., 2024. Fungal β -glucosidase

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		indicators of C accumulation efficiency				gene and corresponding enzyme activity are positively related to soil organic carbon in unmanaged woody plantations. <u>Soil Ecology Letter, 6(4), 240238.</u> https://doi.org/10.1007/s42832-024-0238-2
AGROECOseqC	D1.2.1	Filled datasets by all partners	M47	M53		Delivered (overall AGROECOseqC dataset)
AGROECOseqC	D.5.1.2	Report on plant nutrient demand	M47	M49		Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D.5.2.2	Report on soil nutrient supply or a scientific publication presenting	M47	M49		Delivered

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		the ability of soils to supply nutrient to plant cover under conventional and agroecological practices				
AGROECOseqC	D.5.3	Report on Carbon Use Efficiency	M47	M49		Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D.6.1.3	Report on soil C pools and aggregate stability	M47	M49		Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D.1.3.3	Final AGROECO seqC report		M53		Delivered (Reporting action M11)
AGROECOseqC	D.6.2.1	Report on C emissions during stationary phase of microbes. .	M42	M53		Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D.6.2.3	Report on C emissions after substrate addition	M49	M54		DELETED JUSTIFICATION: Due to issues encountered

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		(and publication on C emissions				in equipment functioning and not satisfactory robustness of collected results, CREA will not consider publishable the dataset.
AGROECOseqC	D.1.5	Publication on agroecological intensification in EU	New		M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered as D1.5 “Report. On agroecological intensification in Europe). Publication will be submitted by 31 st December 2024(CREA)
AGROECOseqC	D.2	Publication on plant diversity and functional traits			M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered as D2 “Report on plant diversity and functional traits”
AGROECOseqC	D.8.2	Press review: EJP			M53	Delivered

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		SOIL newsletters, factsheets and press-releases				
AGROECOseqC	D.3.4.	Report on soil fauna and C sequestration	M47		M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D.3	Final publication on soil fauna			M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered as D3 report. Publication “Soil faunal response to an agroecological intensification gradient in Europe”. Publication will be submitted by Dec 24 (INIA).
AGROECOseqC	D4.	Publication on soil microbial community			M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered as D4 report. Publication will be submitted by Dec 24

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						(CEBAS-CSIC).
AGROECOseqC	D.7.2	Report on classical and next generation models			M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered
AGROECOseqC	D.7.3.	Scientific publications on modelling microbial carbon use efficiency and C-sequestration			M54 (Oct 24)	Publication will be submitted by Dec 24 (INRAE).
AGROECOseqC	D5.3.1	Publication of a methodological article on CUE calculation			M54 (Oct 24)	Publication will be submitted by Dec 24 (INRAE).
AGROECOseqC	D5.3.2	Publication on living microbial biomass and necromass			M54	Delivered as D5.3.2. report. Publication will be submitted by Dec. 31 st .
AGROECOseqC	D7.1.2.0	Publication on functional			M54 (Oct 24)	Delivered as D7.1.2.0 report

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		plants and some soil fungi groups integration with soil properties				Publication under drafting (CREA - extrabudget)
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c. Milestones

Please complete/update the last four columns in the table from M38 to M42.

Internal research project title	Milestone (WP, number)	Milestone name	Due date, EJP SOIL month	Achieved (YES/NO)	If not achieved, estimated achievement date	Comments
AGROECOseqC	M1.1.1	Advisory board institution	M22	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M1.3.1	AGROECOseqC kick-off meeting	M23	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M1.1.2	State of art of experimental sites and potential interconnection with other EJPSOIL projects	M24	YES		Completed

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AGROECOseqC	M1.1.3	Selection of experimental sites and agricultural practices	M24	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M1.2.1	AGROECOseqC mandatory/optional parameters (dataset)	M46	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.1.1	Definition of a protocol applicable to all sites	M32	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.3.1	Protocol of ¹³ C pulse labelling	M27	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M8.1	Website	M27	YES		Completed https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/agroecoseqc/
AGROECOseqC	M8.2	Social media	from M27 to M57	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M8.3	EJP SOIL workshops and field-days	from M33 to M57	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.2.2	Soil incubation with 18O2	M37	YES		Completed

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AGROECOseqC	M.6.2.1	Report on C emissions during stationary phase of microbes.	M37	YES	M53	Completed
AGROECOseqC	M1.3.2	AGROECOseqC Intermediate meeting	M39	YES		Completed Meeting was held in person on 12 June 2023 at Riga (before EJPSOIL ASD 2023)
AGROECOseqC	M5.1.2	Measurement of C/N/P content in plant	M49	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.1.3	Quantification of plant nutrient demand	M46	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.2.2	Isotopic analysis (¹⁵ N) of soil extracts	M48	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.2.1	Soil incubation with ¹⁵ N	M51	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.1.3	Quantification of plant nutrient demand	M52	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M.5.2.2.	Isotopic analysis	M52	YES		Completed

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		(¹⁵ N) of soil extracts				
AGROECOseqC	M.5.3.3.	Isotopic analysis (¹³ C and ¹⁸ O ₂)	M52	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M3.1	Identification of microfaunal drivers	M45	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M3.2	Identification of mesofaunal drivers	M45	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M3.3	Identification of macrofaunal drivers	M45	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M7.2.1.1	Evaluation and selection of classical and next generation models	M45	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M1.2.2	AGROECOseqC complete database	M47	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M2.1	Multivariate evaluation of plant communities ' C seq-related to functional traits	M45	YES		Completed

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AGROECOseqC	M2.2.1	Mycorrhizal colonization index	M41	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M2.2.2.	Mycorrhizal mycelial network	M47	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M2.3.	Evaluation of correlation between indices of beneficial plant-microbe symbioses and plant nutritional status	M47	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M3.4	Quantification of Identification of microfaunal drivers	M47	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.2.3	Quantification of soil nutrient supply	M48	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M7.1.1.1	Selection of relevant microbial variables for multivariate analysis	M50	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.3.4	Quantification of carbon	M50	YES		Completed

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		use efficiency and C and N sequestration				
AGROECOseqC	M6.1	WEOC, WSAs, C-content and C/N in fine macro-aggregates and coarse macro-aggregates	M50	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M7.1.2.1	Selection of WP2-WP6 variables for multivariate analysis	M50	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M5.4	Quantification of levels of synchrony and their dependence on practices and biodiversity	M53	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M6.2.2	GHG emission dynamics after plant material addition	-	YES	-	NOT AVAILABLE JUSTIFICATION: Due to issues related to equipment functioning and robustness

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						of collected results, this activity will be not reported by CREA as M6.2.2.
AGROECOseqC	M7.1.1.2	Identification of microbial indicators suitable to discriminate C sequestration and accrual.	M49	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M7.1.2.2.	Identification of main traits and indicators responsible for C sequestration	M54	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M7.2.1.2.	Evaluation of new process to improve SOM dynamics representation by using simple models.	M54	YES		Completed
AGROECOseqC	M7.2.2.3	Impact of soil biome on C-	M54	YES		Completed

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		sequestratio n				
AGROECOseqC	M1.3.3	AGROECOs eqC Final meeting	M54	YES		Completed on 1-2 October 2024. Meeting will be held in person on 1- 2 October 2024 in Rome (Italy)

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